
**A FRAMEWORK FOR ROLLING OUT DATA PROTECTION REGULATION IN
NIGERIA: CASE STUDIES FROM TRAVEL AGENCIES.**

By

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Declaration of Originality

I, understand and hereby certify that this thesis which I submit for the degree of Doctor of Business Administration to the school of Business and Enterprise at the University of the West of Scotland is my work.

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Abbreviations

Abbreviations	Meaning
NDPR	The Nigerian Data Protection Regulation
DPCOs	Data Protection Compliance Organizations
IPA	Information Privacy Awareness
NITDA	National Information Technology Development Agency
AU	African Union
EFCC	Economic and Financial Crimes Commission
EU GDPR	European Union General Data Protection Regulation
DPO	Data Protection Officer
SMEs	Small to Medium-Sized Enterprises
CRM	Customer Relationship Management
CKM	Customer Knowledge Management

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Abstract

Data protection has become a trending subject since the introduction of the EU GDPR. Several works in past literature focused on consumer behaviour towards privacy in the western context. However, little research has been done to ascertain the effectiveness of data protection regulation in emerging economies like Nigeria.

To cover the gap in the literature, this thesis explores the data protection practices in Nigerian travel agencies given the recently introduced Nigerian data protection regulation (NDPR).

A case study approach was adopted to gain deep insight into the data protection practices in Nigeria. The case study was carried on four travel agencies covering international student recruitment and leisure travel. A cross-case analysis of the themes generated from the interviews and desk research was discussed.

The main findings suggest all four agencies were not fully compliant based on varying criteria. In addition, data collected from desk research suggests that out of 155 registered travel agencies, 59% did not have a data protection policy in place, 20% had a policy but only 3% were partly compliant due to lack of awareness of the Nigerian data protection regulation (NDPR). Hence, an implementation framework is proposed to aid effective data protection practice within organizations in Nigeria.

This thesis concludes that more effort needs to be made in sensitizing data controllers and data subjects on the need for effective data protection practices. This research brings immense benefits suggesting a possible improvement to NDPR regulation which affects all citizens of Nigeria. The implications of this research for the policymakers (Nigerian government), data controllers (travel agencies), data processors, and the data subject (consumers), limitation, and future research have been discussed appropriately.

Chapter One: Introduction

1.1 Research Background

The issue of data protection has become a trending subject in past and present research. The introduction of the EU General Data Protection Regulation (EU GDPR) was a light at the end of the tunnel for customers and companies alike. For customers, it was a means to safeguard their data; while for companies, it would mean a reduced number of breaches with more workload.

For many companies, access to data generated about customers can be used to make insightful decisions on how to serve people better, especially in the marketing of products or services. When targeted marketing is used for the right purposes, it is safe to say that there is no harm to customers. This is because they can get what they want just when they need it. For market leaders and businesses, big data is a veritable key to a new epoch of business insight, intelligence, and individualized business delivery of services (Gadatsch, 2017), but it poses a threat and concern to customers about the security of their personal information. These concerns have been termed “privacy issues”. Privacy concern is being used because of the magnitude and volume of varied information produced by and about people – by things or through the interactions between individuals and things – at an increased and staggering amount in recent years. Westin (1968) gave an initial definition of information privacy as the ability of an individual to have control of the terms and conditions through which his or her information and personal details are collected and used. However, if we consider a pregnant lady who wanted to keep the news of her pregnancy a secret but went online to shop for a pregnancy test strip, then a few days later gets an email notification which says, ‘*what to do when you are expecting a baby*’. If her dad or anyone else stumbles upon such information, then her privacy is breached. Such a customer would be furious, but the questions that may arise would be:

- How did the advertiser know she was pregnant?
- Who gave out her personal information?

As business organizations increase their efforts to gain and use customer information for better marketing decisions, customers in turn get more concerned about the security of their privacy and the potential harm that can stem from the abuse of their data. The EU General Data Protection Regulation makes it clear that personal data is anything that can be used to identify a person. This can be email, name, gender, home address, phone number, etc., (Commission, 2016). These kinds of information have become very important to companies because it aids targeted marketing. However, several issues have arisen because of personal data access. These issues range from identity theft, data breaches, unsolicited marketing, internet fraud, and lots more.

Likewise, some series of recent high-worth data security breaches and scandals like Edward Snowden's NSA leaks (Lyon, 2015), (Gudmundsdottir, 2014) and the data breach that occurred at the USA retail chain, Target Corp (Plachkinova & Maurer, 2019), have revealed that breach of data by unauthorized access to sensitive datasets carried out legitimately or not have a great devastating effect for individuals and data holding firms. Notable challenges to data security and privacy revolve around the heightened potential for breach of sensitive data like; large volume theft, loss of Individual control over one's data, long term availability of delicate datasets, quality of data integrity and provenance concern, unwanted inferences of correlation of data, dearth of transparency and limited management consent and algorithmic accountability, forms the bedrock of issues as far as data is concerned (Fhom, 2015).

Furthermore, in recent years, fear of unauthorized data access, malware, and phishing pose concerns for e-commerce users across the world. Unauthorized data access occurs where internet fraudsters breach unsecured sites and steal databases of user information ranging from payment data, and other sensitive information (Lowry et al., 2017). Fraudsters could also send malware such as viruses that infect user websites which cause the software to be downloaded to customer's devices without permission and perform functions such as stealing user data, encrypting, or deleting delicate information, hijacking, or altering computing functions, and worse of, monitoring the user's activity. Likewise, phishing is another threat e-commerce users are posed with, whereby fraudsters create websites identical to an existing site, invite users to the site for the reason of obtaining their data, payment details, usernames and passwords, and any other personal data (Lowry et al., 2017; Martin et al., 2017). Similarly, concerns have risen over data replication at minimal cost, storage of data in databases that can be searched and easily accessed by the public over the internet (Fhom, 2015). In offline markets,

particularly brick and mortar stores, the concern for the privacy of personal details is acknowledged as a principal factor (Martin & Murphy, 2017).

These ongoing privacy issues resulted in four years of preparation and debate leading to the formation of the EU GDPR. The European GDPR was approved by the European Parliament in April 2016 and in May 2016. The official texts and regulations of the directive were published in all the official languages of the European Union. Then on May 25th, 2018 the legislation came into force across the European Union. To further expand the range of the regulation, the EU GDPR restricted businesses from dealing with countries that did not have a data protection policy in place (Commission, 2016). Consequently, in the wake of GDPR, many countries – Including Nigeria – started adjusting to suit the GDPR requirements. Since the introduction of the EU GDPR, a study by (Schulze, 2018) postulated that 63% of companies were not ready to adjust to the new changes, while a further 26% speculated that it would take time for them to become fully compliant with GDPR. In another study by (Brodin, 2019), it was concluded that Small and Medium-sized companies struggled with GDPR compliance. Despite these challenges, the GDPR takes no hostages as compliance is compulsory for all data controllers, the default being a €20million fine or 4% turnover –whichever is greater (Governance, 2020). In 2019, the Information Commissioners Office (ICO) published an intention to fine British Airways £183.39M for GDPR infringements (ICO, 2019) and Marriot International £99,200,396 for a cyber-incident leading to the exposure of 339 million customer personal data (ICO, 2019). In the face of the explosion of data, the challenge of data privacy spreads across various parts of the world but, studies have underrated the role of privacy concerns in the context of e-commerce, particularly in an emerging market like Nigeria. These privacy issues no longer exist only in the western context but are now gaining momentum in Nigeria due to issues of fraud and cybercrimes.

Despite Nigeria being classed as a developing economy, addressing data protection issues is crucial because, with the speedy growth of technology, there is an increasing demand for personal data in Nigeria. Several online businesses are abandoning the traditional style of conducting business, instead, they are adopting the online business trend (Martin & Murphy, 2017). In Nigeria, many customers are choosing convenience over the old style of shopping. Nigerian businesses now have online stores with the help of platforms like Instagram, Facebook, Whatsapp, and Flutterwave. Social media platforms have brought a convenient way for businesses to interact with customers and travel agencies are not left out. Before online businesses gaining momentum in Nigeria, travel agencies operated offline. Customers had to

visit their physical offices to purchase tickets and, in few cases, where the customer consistently patronizes the travel agency, they could order a ticket over a phone call. Convenience may mean different things to several customers but for most, it is getting what they need within the comfort of their home without having to visit a physical store. Likewise, marketing has seen a change in past trends – unlike the old method of marketing which greatly depended on customers being physically present to view an advert; the new method can get to the right customer through targeted advertising. For example, the popular media giant, Facebook, contributed towards making advertising easy for companies through the provision of target selection, within its advert manager software. Companies can now define a target market by choosing who they want to reach specifically – by selecting factors such as age, gender, location, interests, mutual friends, pages visited and liked, etc.

In Africa, Nigeria is known as one of the most populous countries, hence, it would not be surprising how quickly automated marketing technology is welcomed into its borders. With Nigeria's ever-growing population, data protection is a growing concern. As of the 5th of April 2020, Nigeria's population was estimated to be 204,870,084 million (WorldOmeter, 2020), and in 2014, 77 out of 100 residents were smartphone users who subscribed to a telecommunication provider (UNdata, 2020). Data from research suggests an exponential growth of smartphone users to over 140million by 2025 (Statista, 2020).

The use of smartphone devices with internet access opened a great window of opportunity for medium and small-scale businesses to reach their customers online. As an incentive to support the growth and small businesses in Nigeria, the Corporate Affairs Commission (CAC), in 2019 introduced a 50% reduction in business registration fees from about \$25 to \$13 (Vanguard, 2019). Consequently, many businesses sprung up on social media, which became a meeting arena for non-business owners, entrepreneurs, influencers, business enthusiasts, and travel agencies alike. Increased access to smartphones will subsequently lead to more data access for many businesses. We see a clear example when opening a regular social media account on Instagram – users are requested to submit their email address, full name, date of birth, phone number, gender, address (for business account), and profile picture (Instagram, 2020). Such data without doubt can identify a person. While users can decide to use a fake name or modify their names by adding figures or numbers, for example (Nami987), Facebook demands real names when opening a Facebook account (Facebook, 2020). The key to successful marketing is knowing what your customer's functional and emotional needs are, which will influence their buying decision (Stringfellow, et al., 2004).

In Nigeria, increased access to sensitive data brought along with it a rise in fraudulent activities. Internet fraudsters, popularly known as ‘Yahoo Boys,’ took advantage of customers’ trust at the influx of technology. Crimes such as bank frauds, email scams, impersonating government officials to sell multinational companies, etc skyrocketed (Timothy, 2017). Likewise, the 2019 email fraud scam carried out by some Nigerians in the USA, amounting to the sum of \$46million, which the USA claims to be the biggest in history, could not have been possible without the flow or breach of data (BBC, 2019). In addition, on the 25th of June 2020, a criminal complaint was filed against a popular Nigerian celebrity, Ramon Olorunwa, addressed as ‘Hushpuppi’ on Instagram (BBC, 2020). He had allegedly conspired to defraud the premier league, a US law firm, and a foreign bank of \$124 million (Justice, 2020). The fraud allegation was issued months after the introduction of the Nigerian Data Protection Regulation which raises concerns about the effectiveness of the policy. Though Hushpuppi and another fraudster by the name ‘Mr. Woodberry’ – a friend to Hushpuppi – was apprehended in Dubai where they resided at the time, they frequented Nigeria and are nationals of the country (BBC, 2020). Such fraudulent acts involving the use of a massive amount of personal data make the need for effective data protection practices more pressing. On January 25th, 2019, Nigeria introduced the Nigerian Data Protection Regulation (NDPR), which laid down rules for how all controllers and processors handle data. However, the impact of the new regulation is unknown. Unlike other industries in Nigeria, the travel industry controls more data. Therefore, to ascertain the effectiveness of the New Data Protection Regulation, this research considers exploring the use of personal data in the travel industry among selected registered travel agencies in Nigeria.

1.2 Research Findings

After reviewing secondary and primary data, the findings reveal that with more than a year of the Nigerian data protection regulation (NDPR) coming into force, only a few data controllers or processors have complied with the new regulation. In addition, from the interviews conducted with four travel agencies, it was revealed that none of these agencies were aware that there was a data protection regulation that they had to comply with. Few out of the selected travel agency already had data protection habits rather than policies that were influenced by their interaction with international organizations who were bounded by GDPR law. In addition, it was discovered that data protection practices were not decentralized within some of the travel agencies – it was only practiced at the headquarters. Furthermore, none of these organizations had data protection officers rather, everyone who handled data was saddled with the

responsibility of protecting the data without adequate training to do so. In conclusion, these travel agencies comply with data protection policies based on international influence and head knowledge not by the standards of the Nigerian data protection regulation. The findings are discussed in detail in this research.

1.3 Contribution of research

Evidence from literature and findings show that there is a low level of awareness concerning data protection in Nigeria's populace. To effectively spread out data protection awareness in Nigeria would be a tedious process for the government because is greatly dependent on the political will of the government (Abdulrauf, 2015). Notwithstanding, since the introduction of the Nigerian data protection regulation, the government introduced Data Protection Compliance Organizations (DPCOs) to act as a licensed body to provide the following services to data controllers: advisory services, training and awareness, contract drafting, breach remedies, and support, privacy breach impact assessment, outsourced data protection officer (DPO) and information privacy audit. However, some challenges with the introduction of the DPCOS are: will the DPCOS be able to reach out to all organizations? How will the organization reach out to the DPCOS when they are not aware that they exist? Furthermore, existing frameworks are focused on the western context. Therefore, the contribution of this research is to develop a framework that is a step-by-step guideline that will enable organizations to incorporate data protection practices in all areas of their organization without necessarily relying on the intervention of DPCOS at the beginning of the implementation process. One of the challenges of GDPR implementation highlighted by Brodin (2019) is that organizations do not fully understand what GDPR requires from them. Hence, to solve this problem in the Nigerian context, the current NDPR compliance guideline will be reorganized into three levels (compliance level I -III) to help all types of organizations in Nigerian implement NDPR step-by-step. The framework will provide clarity to organizations because it will explain what needs to be achieved in each phase of the implementation process.

1.4 Aim of the Research

The research aims to propose a framework for rolling out Nigerian Data Protection Regulation (NDPR) practices effectively within organizations in Nigeria.

1.5 Objectives of the Research

- ❖ To examine the data protection law existing for online and independent travel agencies in Nigeria
- ❖ To critically analyze the challenges associated with the implementation of data protection law for online and independent travel agencies in Nigeria
- ❖ To ascertain the awareness and compliance level of travel agencies in Nigeria
- ❖ To recommend a framework that would enable effective data protection practice in Nigeria.

1.6 Research Questions

- ❖ To what extent does legislative backing, direct towards governing data protection exist in Nigeria for online and independent travel agencies?
- ❖ What are the challenges associated with effective legal framework implementation of the Nigeria Data Protection regulation for online and independent travel agencies?
- ❖ Has the government sensitized travel agencies enough to ensure awareness and compliance with NDPR in Nigeria?

1.7 Justification of Research

To provide well-covered and detailed research of the target area (Nigeria), the researcher had to consider the industry that handles more sensitive data, which is the travel agency in Nigeria. According to the statistics obtained from the Nigeria Civil Aviation Authority, in 2019, there are 145 registered travel agencies, and this number excludes non-registered travel agencies. In 2016, the total contribution of Travel and Tourism to employment including jobs indirectly supported by the industry – was 9.6% of the total employment (292,220,000 jobs) and it is expected to rise by 2.5% per annum to 381,700,000 jobs in 2027 (11.1% of total) (Ibrahim Orekoya 2018). A travel agency is versatile, covering tours, hotel booking, tickets, airport pickups, education abroad, and lots more. Offering such services requires a large amount of data to be processed. Hence the researcher has chosen to focus on the travel industry which is

a big sector in the industry due to the vast volume of data it handles. Using selected travel agencies in Nigeria, the researcher discovered that with more than a year of the regulation coming into force, only a few data controllers or processors have complied with the new regulation. This might be due to many reasons such as lack of awareness, the ambiguity of regulation rules, lack of resources to implement and manage the process (Brodin, 2019). All of these were investigated in this study.

1.8 Research Methodology

The researcher adopted a qualitative research approach only. The data was collected through primary and secondary sources using interviews and desk research. The data was collected from four registered Nigerian travel agencies. The table below depicts more information on the interviewees' background:

Table 1: Information on the interviewees' background

Agency	Position in Company	Age Group	Years in Company	Level of Access to Sensitive Information
A	Business Manager	35-50	3	High Level
B	Founder & CEO	40- 45	15	High Level
C	Customer Service (Sales)	27-35	4	Moderate
D	Head of operations	29 -35	8	High Level

The table above contains details about the interviewees representing the agencies who participated in the case study.

1.9 Outline of the Thesis

The research has been structured as follows: Part two introduces the literature review on data protection laws in western countries and Nigeria; Part three specifies the methodology used to collect data; Part four and five shows the empirical and theoretical evaluation; Part six concludes the research.

1.10 Motivation for Research

At the inception of this thesis, data protection was a trending subject in western context because of some researchers like; (Crossler, 2011), (Booth & Ho, 2017), (Kokolakis, 2017), (Martin & Murphy, 2017), and (Markkula, 2018). It was interesting to know during a soft search that while the EU was strongly pushing the GDPR, Nigeria at the time only had a guideline for data protection which, had no legislative backing. In addition, with the constant increase in cybercrime, there was a need to make a theoretical contribution that can be applied in the Nigerian context.

Chapter Two: Literature Review

1.1 Introduction

The issue of data privacy is a concern that affects the world of data providers and users. Nowadays, consumers' data is being used by companies across different industries to influence profitability outcomes. Hence, there has been a constant rise in customers' concern about how their data is used and how long it is used. Holding customer data with adequate protection in place brings susceptibility to harm. While the issue of data privacy concern is more prominent in western cultures, it is beginning to gain momentum in emerging markets in Africa. The recent rise in the concern for data privacy draws attention to the importance of reviewing literature and conducting extensive research on the topic. How customers react to the use of their data directly affects companies' profitability outcomes. In emerging markets, specifically in Africa, the issue of privacy concern has not been brought to light or researched by academia. Hence, the purpose of this research is to bridge the gap in the literature by focusing on emerging markets such as Nigeria.

1.2 Travel agency overview

Travel agencies process a vast amount of data that is needed in rendering services to customers in tourism and hospitality. In our world today, travel arrangements can hardly be made without the assistance of travel agencies. More so, the growth in the industry has allowed independent travel agents (non-IATA licensed) to partake of the market share.

Simply put, travel agencies deal with anything travel-related. As such, different travel agencies deal with varying travel-related requests. There are travel agencies whose services are focused on leisure or work while others are on education. Travel agencies often partner with other third-party companies to deliver services that may be indirectly related to their service offerings. For example, they partner with universities to offer services on school admissions that require traveling. They also partner with hotels should the case arise where some of their serviced travelers need hotel services. The list goes on and on.

Unlike old times when travel arrangements had to be made face to face, the introduction of technology made business simpler for travel agents. Travel agencies now have websites where almost all their services can be purchased online without them physically being present. Companies like Expedia.com, Bookings.com, Travelstart. ng etc, now benefit from the

dividend of technological advancement. With the growth in demand for travel and increase in business process automation, travel agencies like other businesses now focus on utilizing customers' data to provide more tailored experiences to customers. For example, a customer who travels frequently would have such information retained by travel agencies to send more targeted ads containing travel vacation deals to the customer. Nonetheless, these benefits of access to customers' data come with implications. Due to the size and diversity of the travel industry, travel agencies can access and process large data sets which are not only personal data but sensitive personal data. In the wake of data protection policies, traditional and non-traditional companies are rising to take advantage of this consumer awareness. Nigeria has since witnessed the introduction of e-commerce companies and more so, an increase in travel agencies online and offline. To specifically gain insight into data protection issues in Nigeria, it was paramount that this research focuses on an industry that deals with much data such as the travel industry. In the wake of the GDPR, many countries --including Nigeria --have formulated a data protection law to avoid being side-lined by the GDPR law which restricts business with countries without data protection law. The Nigeria Data Protection Law was introduced on January 25, 2019 (after the commencement of this research). The travel agency is one of the oldest forms of business in Nigeria, being that it is linked to transportation (a movement of people from one destination to another). To make this possible, these travel agencies require data from customers to fulfill travel requests. Hence, data protection is a very broad topic and considering the population of Nigeria, making the whole populace aware may be far reached. However, these populace deal with organizations daily. Therefore, putting efforts into ensuring that these organizations are trained, prepared, and equipped with the necessary tools to implement data protection policies should be the starting point. Research must be carried out to cover this gap. With the widespread of social media, consumers have encountered knowledge on how to do many things and this access has made technology adoption faster. The Nigerian Communications Commission (NCC), Nigeria's telecoms regulatory commission report shows that the number of internet users on the country's telecom networks increased to more than 93 million as of July of that year (Chidozie & Olutosin, 2015). A close look at what personal data is according to GDPR will provide better insight into the concept of personal data.

1.3 What is personal data

The term personal data surprisingly has over 339,000,000 million search results on google which clearly shows the importance of the term. To understand the relevance of this research, a simple definition of ‘personal data’ has been included. Personal data is any information that can identify a person. However, for data to constitute personal data, it must be combined with other information which, is known as ‘*personally identifiable information*’ (GDPR, 2021). Such information includes name, email, phone number, etc. There are certain implications for having access to such information, but the kind of information held about a person determines the implication thereof.

1.3.1 Sensitive and non-sensitive data

The European Union general data protection regulation (GDPR) provides further clarity in understanding how data differ in categories. The categories of personal data are sensitive data sets that reveal sensitive information about a data subject. Some information is considered ‘*special category data*’ such as biometric data for identification, data concerning health, sexual orientation, religious or philosophical beliefs, political opinions, racial or ethnic origin, and trade union membership (Information Commissioner's Office, 2021). Any other information apart from criminal data is not classified as sensitive but rather personal data.

In today’s world, we see that the growth of the internet has brought about the need for a vast amount of data set to be processed daily. Organizations are beginning to make meaning of these data sets; hence, they implement marketing practices that make use of these data for better business performance. What we refer to as personal information today goes beyond basic identifiers such as names, gender, address, etc. It is now a blend of information and identifiers that enable organizations to track an individual's behavior online, profile them and come up with accurate inferences about the consumer. One of the ways we build consumer trust in their journey online is to assure them of the security and privacy of their data, (Jarvenpaa, 2017).

There have been arguments regarding the similarity and use of both terms ‘privacy and data protection’. Many people cannot distinguish between both. However, the Forbes Expert Technology Council Identify 6 key differentiating factors between Data Privacy and Data Protection (Council, 2018).

Table 2: Differences between data protection and data privacy

Data Protection	Data Privacy
Protection of personal data from unauthorized use	Defines who is authorized to access the data.
It centers on the mechanisms and procedures for enforcing regulations	It centers on regulations and policies for data access
It places protection responsibility on data controllers	It gives the power of control to the data subject and user
It protects data from hackers	It restricts the sale or sharing of personal data
Data subjects can know how data controllers intend to protect their data.	The data subject can access and know who their data is shared with.
Focuses on protecting data that is already obtained	Clarifies why data should be collected and what amount of data should be collected

(Source: Forbes, 2018)

The table above shows the difference between data protection and data privacy.

Forbes (2018) further stated that data privacy and data protection cannot be interchanged rather they should be used together because, you cannot protect what you cannot access (Council, 2018). The notion and value of consumer data privacy began with (Warren & Brandeis, 1890) in a piece of article that was published on Harvard Law Review, where they made a case of privacy intrusion by the activities of the journalists of their day. Verginadis (2017), suggested several factors that make organizations’ networks prone to being violated or compromised which, will make the customers’ data in their custody susceptible to violation. These factors include a client software application that is not upgraded, a lack of existence of security architecture, phishing that is well-targeted to comprise a user's system when opened, a management system that is poorly configured, detachable-like which can be compromised, and any other non-technical security means. Consumers’ concerns for the safety of their data are triggered by several factors which may include: the extent of personal information they are requested to disclose; how mandatory some particular information fields are e.g. phone number and email; how relevant the data being supplied is concerning the particular context; the control given to consumers that allows them to opt-out when they wish to; how the data is made use

of; the necessary support information; the incentives that go with data exchange; credibility, familiarity, and trust consumers have built with the firm requesting the information; and strategies for risk reduction, all play important roles (Waldman, 2016).

1.4 Why data is important

Data has become an integral part of our world today which is seen in the way organizations use it to provide services to consumers. The usefulness of data to businesses became evident in the rapid change of many business operations from traditional brick stores to a more modernized way of conducting business through the internet. However, some businesses transited late resulting in the shutting down of brick and wall stores in the face of adverse competition, as seen in the cases of some UK-based companies – Staples, Maplin, Poundland plus, etc. (BBC UK, 2018).

Technology is constantly changing, bringing with it a rapid increase in the demand for the personal data of consumers. Such demand brings with it possible social and economic consequences on different aspects of life. Some of these technological changes have been manageable and used by some businesses to create a competitive advantage in the business world, while for others, the results have been devastating. Following the incidences that have occurred on the internet such as cyberbullying, terrorism, identity theft, and abuse; the rise of negativity from the internet tends to question the use of it in the first place. Likewise, another focal point to note is how well the use of the internet and its methods have been adopted by businesses, both great and small. Many companies have been established just to aid the processing of big data which helps many companies make sense of consumer personal data. It is important to note that all technologies create a level of impact in our lives (Venkatesh, 1985). For instance, considering the television technology, we would note that it has had a major impact on the habit of its users which is seen in their attitude, behavior, and interactions among family and friends (Cole, 2000). Access to data about user interaction with television would make the originator invest more time and resources in getting user interaction. In a recent documentary sponsored by Netflix titled '*the social dilemma*', it was revealed that attention is the new currency. The documentary revealed unethical practices within companies that process large amounts of data and the length such companies will go to secure user attention and interaction on their platform (Orlowski, 2020). The findings from a study conducted by Kraut et. al. suggests that the internet has effects on social and psychological wellbeing (Chandio & Rajani, 2004). Furthermore, it suggested that increased use of the internet by users significantly

reduced community participation (Kraut, et al., 1998). Likewise, in a study conducted by N. Nie on the social consequences of the internet, the findings showed similar evidence with the Kraut group of negative social behaviour from the use of the internet (Nie, 2000). Another group of researchers, Katz and Aspden, surveyed 2,500 respondents from which they compared internet users to non-internet users, but they found no evidence of negative social behaviour which contradicts Kraut and Nie's research. Despite the issues that arise from the internet, it has become a major means of data collection and in some cases, storage for data in the new age. It is rapidly replacing traditional means of communication. For example, since the introduction of WhatsApp, the demand for airtime top-up has slightly reduced while demand for mobile data increased as many users turn to WhatsApp as a means for a mobile call, messaging, and data exchange communication. The company, Facebook, has recently introduced WhatsApp business to help businesses communicate faster with clients – giving a more convenient, personal, and professional look to businesses. Given the rapid diffusion of the internet in our world, businesses are forced into a state of competition in a bid to meet the demands of customers through the insight they gather from customer data. Suffice to say that customers control businesses. Hence, to survive, organizations use customers' data to help understand their needs and buying behaviour.

For this reason, certain concerns arise which includes:

- How far companies are willing to go to obtain data?
- What is the data used for?
- How long is a customer's data held for?
- How do companies analyse the data before deciding on a product or service to offer?

1.5 Data Access Benefits to travel agencies

1.5.1 Why Organisations Use Data

In a technological world characterized by regular rapid changes, customers are always eager to embrace change and participate in new trends. For example, Apple Inc. is a tech company that offers a variety of technological products such as phones, tablets, laptops, iPad, etc. Apple constantly provides customers with new trends which can be attributed to the fact that it has identified what customers want which is a crucial part of product or service creation. While access to data provides social and economic benefits, it also raises privacy concerns

(Rubinstein, 2013).

1.5.2 Consumer and company data access benefit

Rubinstein (2013) argues that data access provides joint benefits to consumers and companies alike. Some of the key benefits of data access are a means for consumer empowerment, improved shopping experiences, and an automated decision-making process. For instance, the decision-making process in getting a loan in the UK involves checking the customer's credit history. Good credit history is a representation of data sets that depicts a customer's worthiness to take a loan. Using data, the customer would save time contrary to providing the required information manually. Likewise, Amazon uses data to drive improved customer experiences through shopping suggestions like *'customers who bought this duvet also bought pillows*. Customers can benefit from automated decision-making process such as data protection cookies popups on certain websites which automatically gets the user consent. The user saves time by not reading through massive chunks of data protection texts. Some organizations do not allow full access to their websites without first collecting personal data from customers. Where there are significant benefits to gain from having such access, customers will have no choice but disclose their personal information (Wirtz, et al., 2017)

Similarly, data is needed for innovation as an important feature in establishing and increasing competitive advantage for businesses. Innovation would be fruitless if it is not accepted by those for which it was intended. For organizations to avoid waste in innovation, they need to improve innovation by knowledge management (Jaun, et al., 2016). To apply knowledge to innovation, organizations will need data for, from, and about customers and effectively manage this information for better performance, which Juan et.al describes as Customer Knowledge Management. Innovation comes from the Latin word *'Innovatio-onis'* which means (I) Action and effect to innovate and (II) Creating or modifying a product (Jaun, et al., 2016).

1.5.3 Data as a means for Customer Relationship Management in the travel industry (CRM)

A great deal of knowledge transfer occurs within the travel industry. The concepts of customer relationship management (CRM) and knowledge management (KM) have been recently gaining wide attention in business and academia. The approaches of CRM focus on allocating resources to support business activities to gain competitive advantages. CRM focuses on managing the relationship between a company and its current and prospective customer base

as a key to success. A good relationship with the customer will lead to higher customer satisfaction which directly affects the revenue stream (Gebert, et al., 2002). Customer Knowledge Management (CKM) creates a new platform for sharing and processing information between corporations and their customers (Garcia-Murillo & Annabi, 2000). Customer Knowledge Management serves as a continuous and strategic process through which businesses enable their customers to move from inactive information sources and receivers of products and services to empowered knowledge allies.

In contrast to an expansion of Customer Knowledge Management (CKM), Gibbert et. al, argues that CKM should be viewed in the aspect of extrinsic and intrinsic knowledge. They stated that extrinsic knowledge, being just basic knowledge about the customer (contact details and general preferences), is not enough for a successful innovation process. The intrinsic knowledge of a customer will better aid innovation and create value for the company and the customer. However, the question is will customers be willing to distribute knowledge that will enable a company to create value and then pay for the value they helped to create? Regardless of these challenges, some companies have identified the need for customer's intrinsic knowledge and created systems to gather such information. For instance, a big and internationally recognized insurance company called OLD Mutual acquired the knowledge of patients – regarding their health – through electronic means. Instead of relying on doctors for the patients' information, the company used electronic means to screen applicants for medical insurance and to create new insurance products. Old Mutual created electronic forms to replace patient's evaluation forms which were previously being filled by their doctors, though they still had to be evaluated by their doctors, but the electronic form saved time and led to greater accuracy because doctors were notorious for their unreadable handwriting (Gibbert, et al., 2002). The issue of security of patients' information was still a concern but it had to be managed carefully.

By effectively managing the intrinsic knowledge of customers, businesses will be able to spot emerging market opportunities ahead of their competitors, thereby creating economic value for themselves. Undeniably, most corporations today consider themselves customer-oriented or market-driven. Until now, only a few companies were effectively managing their, perhaps, most valuable resource: the knowledge *inherent in* their customers as opposed to knowledge *about* their customers. Customer Knowledge Management may be confused for Customer Relationship Management. However, they differ in the sense that Customer Knowledge Management requires managers to focus on the knowledge from customers rather than on the

knowledge about customers. Additionally, smart corporations have identified that customers are more knowledgeable than they presume. Hence, they use their customer representatives to obtain knowledge from customers. This is popular among telecom companies who would request feedback from customers to ascertain if their communication with the representative was satisfactory. They would always notify the customers in every call that such calls are recorded for monitoring and improvement purposes. Giving additional feedback to the company will enable them to match customer responses against their records. Likewise, conservative knowledge managers try to focus on obtaining intrinsic knowledge from customers, making them knowledge sharers rather than accumulators. This is mostly done by intranet-based knowledge-sharing platforms, Yellow Page initiatives, and 'Share Nets,'. Such platforms and tools often have sophisticated functions such as urgent requests, or incentive systems that reward both the giver and taker of knowledge.

Consider Amazon.com; the Internet retailer manages customer knowledge successfully – using book reviews, the customer's order histories, order history of other customers, and customized suggestions based on prior orders. Effectively, Amazon.com, a commercial enterprise, developed into a platform of book enthusiasts that are keen to exchange knowledge about their favorite topics (intrinsic motivation). In terms of motivating customers to share their knowledge, the Amazon way is a remarkable achievement particularly if contrasted with the, often vain, efforts to evangelize employees from egoistic knowledge hoarders to altruistic knowledge sharers by way of rewards systems that are mostly extrinsic. While some (tentative) approaches exist that tie employee promotion and demotion to their propensity to share knowledge (e.g., Davenport and Probst, 2002), human resources management is still struggling with the legal implications associated with the establishment of the employee's knowledge sharing record as a basis for instilling intrinsic motivation in employees to share their knowledge. What seems to prevail in Knowledge Management so far is extrinsic motivation systems allowing, for example, prolific knowledge sharers to spend weekends in attractive locations.

Similarly, a *North American company*, Holcim, recently analyzed how to deliver e-commerce solutions to their customers. Their idea was to create a knowledge-sharing platform where any member of the community of the cement industry – such as consumers, concrete producers, distributors, engineers, and architects – can transact business online, share and exchange knowledge. For example, sharing cement order forecasts, sharing good and bad experiences with specific applications, etc. To test and further develop this aspiration, Holcim's customer

knowledge managers conducted meetings with selected customers in the US. They selected, at random, different customer segments comprising of selected large multi-nationals, medium domestic, and small family-owned companies. The objective of the meeting was to discuss current and emerging trends in the cement industry and the potential impact of these developments on Holcim's customers, thereby jointly ascertaining how Holcim could create value for their customers. The discussion was open and free-flowing. Although Holcim had developed a set of value-added services that were thought appropriate, it did not implement these until after the customers had given their views, thereby adding value to the company's services. One of Holcim's customer knowledge managers said that their customers were impressed with the company's decision to include them in the decision-making process and no other supplier had chosen to do this. Holcim built and implemented the knowledge-sharing platform in North America and Western Europe and kept close contact with their customers. This was much appreciated by the customers. Such action fosters customer relationships: However, contrary to the knowledge management approach in fostering a relationship between product performance and customer, customer knowledge management proposes a counter-intuitive logic centered around the intrinsic knowledge of the customer. It suggests that getting employees and customers to share knowledge is challenging, considering that the information provided could help enhance quality and value creation for the company, which the customer may not be compensated for if they indulge in knowledge sharing.

In the face of these challenges, some retail e-commerce companies such as Primark, Boots, and New Look, offer raffle draw opportunities to their customers if they participate in giving feedback. If this action is considered, not many customers would participate because the offer is sometimes too far reached. For example, Primark receives up to 1000 customers daily across all its branches in the UK and offers buyers an opportunity to win a £500 shopping voucher if they participate in a survey or give feedback on the service they received. Considering the number of shoppers that enter their stores, the chance to win will be about 1 to 900. Customers will naturally be discouraged to spend time entering information online considering that the probability of them winning is relatively low. Preferably, if a more personalized approach is given, such that customers are offered a £1 off their shopping every time they give feedback on the service they received or product performance, etc., they would be able to record a high volume of responses. However, if this method is adopted, then a more constructive questionnaire could be created which will be targeted at improving value creation and increasing competitive advantage. The major critique of Customer Knowledge Management is

the uncertainty in the willingness of customers to share their knowledge; and secondly, the cost associated with implementing an effective Customer Knowledge Management (Gibbert, et al., 2002). Most organizations now use ‘SMAPLY’ – an online tool used to measure and document customer experiences, provide insight into the level of customer engagement and emotional relationship between the customer and product.

1.5.4 Data Access Issues: Implication for travel agencies

The integration of customer knowledge in innovation requires special types of customers and methods which entails specific risks. With the emergence of a crisis of trust in data security, there is a high risk involved in the innovation process. Therefore, customers now act on their privacy concerns.

Ridley (2015), in his study, showed that the number of people in the United Kingdom who are said to have shown concern about data privacy issues has dropped from 84% to 75% between 2012 and late 2017. The statistics of young adults between the ages of 18-24 who were concerned about their data privacy as of 2012 dropped from 75% to 58% in 2017 with about two-thirds of consumers now comfortable with the level of personal information they disclose to organizations. The study also found that there is a generational shift when it comes to data exchange as younger generations are more aware, accepting, and willing to exchange data. The study further discloses that consumers in the UK consider their data an asset; hence, they exhibit an entrepreneurial drive over the sharing of their data with companies as the ratio of consumers with such entrepreneurial spirit moved up from 40% to 56% between 2012 and 2017. A huge percentage of people hold the notion that organizations disproportionately gain from mining people's data, thereby making control the core aspirants of consumers. It's no more news that the establishment of the trust is paramount to the development of a sustainable data economy. Ridley's (2015) study further shows that the core of consumers' willingness to exchange data is rooted in transparency and a growing pattern of ranges of incentives that go beyond monetary value.

Afroz et. al., (2013), in a study on how the flaws of privacy impacts consumer perception using Sony, Apple, and Facebook data breach case studies — found that overall, consumers who have prior trust in a brand tend to keep patronizing the brand irrespective of the case of a breach. The study found that even after the case of privacy breach that Apple and Sony went through, consumers who already trusted the brands were more likely to patronize the corresponding company's products. The researchers suggested that they need to communicate their intentions

to consumers concerning privacy issues. According to them, if consumers perceive that there may be a breach of privacy, that feeling — to them — is equally as terrible as if a large-scale breach had happened. They, therefore, concluded that products that have suffered privacy breaches in the past impose a visible effect on the manner that consumers perceive the brand and its products. Their survey on consumer perception of the three brands: Facebook, Apple, and Sony, following their cases of privacy breach, concludes that consumers who are aware of privacy breaches trust the brand less.

1.5.5 Examples of Data Breaches and Exploitation of Customer Data

In 2010, the Financial Conduct Authority (FCA) released a report containing details of a fine of £2,275,000 issued by the Financial Services Authority to Zurich Insurance company as a result of the loss of the personal details of its 46,000 policy holders (Authority, 2010); and in 2008-2010 a similar case occurred between a former partner of insurance broker Godwin Best of Bury Lancashire and its clients which related to the misappropriation of client's premium for personal use up to £303,846. Financial Services Authority (FSA) fined the pair the sum of £472,000 for insurance fraud (Insurance News Daily, 2012). Similarly, the Information Commissioner Office (ICO) fined the bank of Scotland £75,000 for repeatedly sending customer information such as pay slips, bank statements, names, addresses, and contact details to the wrong fax address (Times, 2013). Similarly, in 2018, the worst level of account hacking occurred on Instagram. Instagram users complained bitterly about the inability to access their accounts due to hacking. Both businesses and personal accounts suffered the same fate. A popular Nigerian blogger, Linda Ikeji had her Instagram account with over 1million followers deleted by Instagram which has been a major battle to restore, but she gave up and started a new page all over again. The severity of data loss is beyond words (Adeneyo, 2019). In addition, in August 2019, USA authorities named 80 Nigerians in the biggest fraud crime in history amounting to \$46million. In 2017, Mr. Ade Adesomoju, a subscriber, to one of Africa's biggest telecommunications networks – MTN, won a lawsuit against them, for \$12,000 over sharing his contact number to third-party companies who sent unsolicited messages (Punch, 2017).

Prevalent cybercrime and breach of data protection policies involving the use of a massive amount of personal data makes the need to combat data protection implementation challenges more pressing. Travel agencies are involved in the issuance of tickets for travelers from all works of life. They hold sensitive information such as biometric details, bank information for

visa processing, ethnicity, age, sexuality, immigration history, criminal offense status, etc. This information if not securely stored or if carelessly handle would be devastating to the customer. Likewise, access to sensitive information about a traveler could aid effective fraud investigation in cases of cybercrime. Therefore, travel agencies must become data protection enthusiasts and not mere observers.

1.6 Data Policies in Selected Western countries, and Nigeria

A Close look at European, USA, and Nigerian Approach to Data Protection

1.6.1 USA Approach to Data Protection

The USA approach to Data protection differs remarkably from the European approach. While the EU believes that Data protection is a fundamental human right and enforces this belief, the USA on the other hand does not have included in its constitution “*protection of privacy*”. However, the USA 4th, 9th and 10th Amendment does recognize that the right to privacy constituted a part of fundamental human right (Ang, 2001). Nonetheless, this creates a sense of ambiguity when considering the regulation of privacy in the USA. There are privacy laws that exist in the USA, but they are disjointed. Some of these laws are Bank Secrecy Act, Cable TV Privacy Act 1984, Fair Credit Reporting Act, Electronic Funds Transfer Act, Social Security Confidentiality Act, Consumer Fraud Act, Telecommunications Act, Driver Privacy Protection Act, etc. (Ang, 2001). The privacy laws in operation in the USA have been aimed at public sectors and aimed at preventing specific abuse. For instance, the Driver Privacy Protection Act was implemented after an incident that led to the death of an actress occurred as a result of the disclosure of her driver's license details. Another example is the Fair Credit Reporting Act, which gives customers the right and ability to access their financial records and make changes to their details but does not restrict the transfer of customers’ information between companies (Steinke, 2002). The implications of sectoral and self-regulation on the concept of privacy are such that it restricts privacy laws to areas where privacy does not apply thereby creating a vacuum in the law (Ang, 2001). In 1998, the Federal Trade Commission (FTC) introduced four governing principles for websites that collect personal information from customers, which relates to cable TV and record stores. The FTC mandated that these sites do the following: give notice on their website to customers on the kind of data they collect, how it is collected, used, and whether it is transferred; offer customers the right to choose to opt in to allow their information used beyond the intended purpose; grant customers access to their information and allow them to delete or edit such information provided, and provide adequate security for the personal data they have collected.

Nonetheless, in a report issued by the FTC, it was discovered that only 14% out of 92% of websites collecting information, informed customers of their information collection practice

and only 10% made their policy easily accessible. Likewise, in another report in 2000, FTC found that out of 97% of websites that collect personal information from customers, only 20% complied with some part of the four fair information practices. As a result of the slow implementation of self-regulation, FTC suggested to congress to pass legislation in conjunction with the self-regulation practices (Steinke, 2002). While there has been a sluggish approach to the enactment of privacy legislation, some third-party organizations such as TRUSTe and BBB Online have provided a means for making companies comply with the four fair information practices. They provided a seal on the company's website which boost customers' confidence in the website but only 8% have displayed a privacy seal. Due to the inadequate privacy legislation in the USA, the EU threatened to put a stop to the transfer of data to the USA but an agreement was reached with the USA, called the 'The Safe Harbor Agreement' in conjunction with the industry self-regulation, which allows USA companies conducting business in the EU to comply with a code of practice based on the EU Privacy Directive (Steinke, 2002).

Furthermore, in the year 2000, the Platform for Privacy Preferences Project (P3P) was introduced to provide tools and services that give web users the ability to control their data and foster trust between users and website owners. As part of the plan to enhance web security, the World Wide Web Consortium (W3C) released, in April 2019, a highlight of its strategy to achieve a web for all. W3C hired a web payment security group aimed at providing a more secure and easy way for users of the web to process payments online and establish a common working environment for all payment service providers (W3C, 2019).

1.6.2 European Union Approach to Data Protection

The Rise of General Data Protection Regulation and Growing Trend of Consumer privacy

The EU believes that data protection is a part of fundamental human rights and as such developed a General Data Regulation and Protection policy which is pegged on four tenets: users and consumers must grant consent to organizations to process their personal information and they hold the right to withdraw such consents; at any given time, users can gain access to their personal information as stored away by the company and given proper orientation of the use of their data; on any account of a breach, consumers must be informed within 72 hours; and where a breach occurs, companies are expected to pay a 2% fine of annual worldwide turnover.

With the rise of GDPR stems the rise of the data privacy puzzle. Researchers are beginning to grapple with the following questions: who owns the data of consumers? Do consumers have trust in companies to keep their data safe? Will consumers adopt technological devices that demand their data? (Parks, 2017). The attitudes of consumers and the regulatory terrain show an ambivalence of the role data plays in today's economy. Recent studies reveal that though many consumers do not encourage nor support the collection of their personal information, they feel rather helpless to avoid it. At present, the flow of data is global, but its governance is regional, sectional, and inconsistent. For example, the recent European Union data regulation empowers consumer control over their use of data but the African, USA, Asian and other continents remain permissive (Parks, 2017). Further studies have shown that even as individuals and societies grapple with the challenge of the trade-off that happens between embracing innovation and keeping control, enterprises have piqued keen interest in businesses that have devised strategies to place a monetary value on the pool of data they have privy to as organizations continue to strive for competitive advantage to stay ahead. Current studies show that consumers generally consent to the collection of their personal information but are uncomfortable with the practice. (McDonald, 2018).

McDonald, (2018) report further found that consumers typically show a willingness to exchange their data in exchange for services. A study by Columbia University revealed that 75% of consumers would disclose sensitive data such as their mobile phone numbers, contact address, date of birth, or much more in exchange for a service or product they consider valuable from a trusted brand. More so, 80% of consumers – according to the study – would be willing to share private information with organizations to receive offers or benefits. Today, Companies exchange data from consumers by basically granting them discounts and other incentives. People also exchange their information to access free services such as social media, search engines, academic sites, GPS, maps, and other online tools. The use of devices that mine people's contacts has become pervasive among adults all over the world. Largely, companies explain this exchange paradox stating that consumers consider the gains and other benefits they reap worth the trade-off and giving up of their information (Marwick & Hargittai, 2018). An assessment of companies like Amazon, Wal-Mart, MasterCard, Facebook, Twitter, and American Express revealed that organizations' have moved from collecting data given willingly by consumers to a more passive form of information mining. Organizations are still warming up to new strategies of collecting data as the recent case of Facebook shows and the

recent enforcement of GDPR has forced organizations to rework their privacy settings and policies.

GDPR is presently one of the firmest regimes of data protection all over the world (Burton, 2018). The requirement GDPR has placed on firms all over the world who have dealings with EU citizens has caused a ripple of the impact trickling down other countries of the world. Particularly, the EU 1995 Data Protection Directive (DPP) prohibited the transfer of information internationally to countries that did not adhere to, or have a solid data protection policy in place such as the USA (Steinke, 2002). We see the effect of such restriction on companies – like Amazon, eBay, Yahoo – who have American branches, unable to operate the business in the same way across borders (Steinke, 2002). Remarkably, we find consistency in the implementation of the new 2016 GDPR policy, which not only adopts but modifies the law regarding the transfers of data internationally by providing a safe toolkit for transferring data –which are adequacy decisions, standard contractual clauses, binding corporate rules, etc. (Commission, 2016).

1.6.2.1 Principles that makeup GDPR

It is interesting to know that the GDPR is a progression from the former DIR95 (The European Commission 1995) (Brodin, 2019). However, the GDPR introduces some new regulations for data protection.

1.6.2.2 Principles of GDPR

Under Article 4-11, it highlights some principles relating to the processing of personal data Transparency, data minimization, and consent of children (minors); *Pseudonymization* which is the processing of personal data in a method that the data does not directly relate to any subject or person without the use of any additional information. Data minimization on the other hand means the restriction of data collection to only what is needed, which means organizations should only collect what they need and no unrelated data from data subjects (Regulation, 2020).

1.6.2.3 Rights of the Data Subject Under GDPR

Some of the rights of the data subject (data owner) include the right to object, right to forgotten, right of access, right to rectify, right to restriction of the processing. In addition, the data subject also possesses the right to be told the source of data, lawful reason for requesting data, the time for processing the data, where the data will be stored, his or her rights as a data subject, and the

right to data portability, *‘which is the right to request access to their data to reuse it and this can be granted under strong legal grounds.*

1.6.2.4 Responsibility of Controller and Processor of Data Under GDPR

The first foundation of gaining the right to access and control data is having the basic principle of data protection, which demands the implementation of safe security measures in handling or transferring data. Furthermore, a controller must ensure that when he or she processes data, only personal data required for specified purposes are collected and processed. In addition, when a breach occurs, the data controller must within 72 hours, report the breach to the designated supervisor and inform the data subject. It is also required for small to medium-sized enterprises to appoint a Data Protection Officer (DPO), if their business is involved in the processing of a huge amount of data, either personal or criminal data.

1.6.2.5 Transferring of Personal Data to outside the EU/ International Organizations

The GDPR rule under this section has shaken most countries and hence made them tidy up their data protection laws. In this section, GDPR provides certain conditions under which data can only be transferred to internationally domiciled countries. These are appropriate safeguarding of data, which ensures that organizations involved have an acceptable level of protection in place for handling data, appropriate safeguards, and adequacy decisions. In the absence of these, data can still be transferred based on the authority of a competent court or tribunal in a country outside the EU.

1.6.2.6 Criticisms of GDPR

Robert Madge, the Chief Executive Officer and founder of Xifrat Daten AG, Switzerland, and a renowned data-centric supplier and general IT solutions services whose works in data has gained global recognition, points out five key criticisms of GDPR in the aspect of inferred data, invisible data chain, data controllers outside the European Union and information losing the protection of GDPR (Robert, 2017).

1.6.2.6.1 Criticism one: controllers outside the European Union

The recital of GDPR states severally that personal data should be protected where the natural person’s data collection takes place irrespective of the nationality of the person or the residence. Looking at the previous directive of data protection, it applies to any organization involved in the processing of personal data in the European Union but fails to assure the protection of every individual in the EU when their personal information was processed by a company outside the

EU. This is a major loophole that can be taken advantage of by organizations when dealing with data subjects. For example, educational agencies, as well as educators, use the data of students to inform and plan their instructional practice as well to have a better understanding of their students and the students they work with. These data are valuable and when mismanaged or in the wrong hands, possibly a third party, can be a threat to students. Still examining the issue of control, some organizations seek to exploit the details of the phrasing of the law that covers GDPR. The geographical scope entails the processing of personal information of someone in the European Union by business organizations outside the EU, in situations where the processing activities relate to the offering of services and goods to the individual involved. Studies are beginning to explore the phrase: “the offering of goods or services” as it can be subject to diverse understanding and interpretations.

Recital 23 of GDPR states verbatim *“To determine whether such a controller or processor is offering goods or services to data subjects who are in the Union, it should be ascertained whether it is apparent that the controller or processor envisages offering services to data subjects in one or more Member States in the Union. Whereas the mere accessibility of the controller’s, processor’s or an intermediary’s website in the Union, of an email address or other contact details, or the use of a language generally used in the third country where the controller is established, is insufficient to ascertain such intention, factors such as the use of a language or a currency generally used in one or more Member States with the possibility of ordering goods and services in that other language, or the mentioning of customers or users who are in the Union, may make it apparent that the controller envisages offering goods or services to data subjects in the Union.*

Robert (2017) points out the loophole in the recital to mean that the statement is hinged on whether the organization “anticipates” offering of services and goods or not and if an actual transaction takes place or data was simply obtained. A good analogy will be to imagine a scenario where an online education agency that offers a broad range of educational services to international students is sourced from third parties. The said company, for instance, creates a website with an array of services. The website is made accessible worldwide and may even include European languages and maybe tools to convert currency from naira to euro or vice versa to attract more prospects. Potential students who seek such educational services such as scholarship abroad or the like may click on the service on the website of the company and get redirected to a website or portal of an independent third-party organization which is outside the European Union countries whose website may not even have any EU regulation binding them.

At this point, the personal data exchange occurs with a third-party organization (Robert, 2017). It is important to note here that once personal information or data are outside the confines of the law of GDPR, they remain outside the border if it does not get transferred back to the European Union. This invariably implies that a non-European Union organization in possession of personal data and not subject to regulations or restriction of data use or GDPR can decide to sell or compromise the data to any other non-EU member company and get away with it undetected.

1.6.2.6.2 Criticism two: Information losing GDPR protection

Personal information processed in the EU is covered by the GDPR, however, there is a challenge here. Let us use the case of an online education agency as a reference. An education agency based in the United Kingdom, for example, dealing with international students who wish to study in colleges or universities within the UK or any EU country is bound by GDPR and has no option but to comply. However, a loophole occurs in the statement ‘‘offering services to an individual in the EU’’. If such services were to be performed by a third party outside the EU for the same individual, that third party company is not bounded by the EU GDPR and can decide to process such information for other purposes. Likewise, if a Nigerian educational agency collects the personal information of study applicants in the EU, the company will follow the due process and request the consent of the individual who then gives his consent or permission to use his data. But if the organization transfers such data to a third-party company also in Nigeria or Africa, at this point, the transfer of information would still be considered as being processed under GDPR; but since the activity of processing has no relationship with the offering of services or goods to the individual who granted the access, such data is now outside the parameters of the GDPR.

Furthermore, this is a potential threat as the information of the individual would have leaked out of the boundaries of GDPR. The thin hope with this scenario is that the leaked data would be retrieved or regained if used to transfer an offering to another person in the European Union. At this point, it would be very difficult to say that this is occurring through targeted advertising, and much difficult to find and identify the controller who is responsible. A possibility of closing up this limitation could occur with the rephrasing of the words ‘‘related to’’ which is contained in the phrase within the charter that says: ‘‘processing activities related to the offering of goods or services’’ and then replacing it with the phrase ‘‘arising from’’ as suggested by Robert (2017). With the rephrasing, it would therefore mean that any personal information collected during

initial processing would have to continue to enjoy the protection of GDPR when used for a different purpose. With such provision, the data of students would have some level of protection even when it is being transferred by a third party. This is an obvious fact because the process of an international student gaining admission into colleges and universities abroad requires transfer of the student information and with the risk or possibility of losing personal data.

1.6.2.6.3 Criticism three: Invisible Chain of Data

One of the goals of the GDPR is for individuals to always be aware of the state of their data and be able to exercise rights and control over it. For instance, the owner of a data reserves the right to have access to his or her data in the custody of a controller. The data subject can correct errors in the data already supplied, he or she can object to the processing of the data and request a complete erasure as stated in Article 15 of the law. The big question and limitation to this article are how the data subject is supposed to know the controller to direct such request to. Transparency is supposed to begin at the point of collection of the data. The data controller is meant to provide a set of information to the subject and is typically found in the privacy setting on websites in line with Article 13 of the law. One of the important information that the controller is expected to provide is “the data categories or recipients if any”. The word “recipient” implies a third party that the controller shares, transfers or discloses the data to.

The controller is not under any obligation to provide the names of recipients that the data is shared with since it can decide to provide only the “recipient's categories”. If the data subject still decides to request access further, the data controller can still restrict the response to only the categories of the recipient. Article 14 of the GDPR law states that each data recipient controller is mandated to inform the data subject within one month of receiving the data. The issue is what if the recipient does not do this or is not able to do so? This is a huge possibility because there might be cogent reasons why a data controller or recipient may not supply this data. Reasons could be that the data controller may not be able to identify the owner of the data and because of the confidence assured not to disclose the information to the wrong person, he or she may decide to withhold it. Even on an occasion where the individual can be identified, the data recipient controller may lack the details of their correct contact. For example, in the UK, a customer who owed money to a trader’s union was contacted severally but could not be reached. Unknowingly to the company, the debtor had moved three addresses. But luckily for the company, they filed a County Court Judgement against the debtor which appeared in his

credit file and he had to contact the company to make payment. In the scenario mentioned above, the debt collection company had already sent letters with the debtor's details three times to the same address they had a record of. Anyone in the household could have gotten a hold of that letter and decide to use the information contained for illicit purposes.

Likewise, where a student finds out that an organization sold his personal information and thus receiving unsolicited direct marketing communication from a business organization that is not familiar, such individual can make access request as stated under Article 15. It may, however, be impossible to verify the source, where the data was gotten since the obligation of GDPR allows a company to make available only general information for such data subject request as stated by Recital 61. This makes it difficult to hold a particular company liable where there is a breach. At present, there is a very long data chain with individual personal information held in numerous steps away from the original data owner. Today, personal data are bought and sold like a commodity. Multi-million dollars companies are built around data and its analysis. Despite the regulation of GDPR, invisible data chains are very likely to exist for quite some time. A few organizations or online education agencies may decide – and as well have the means – to be compliant and by making notifications of Article 14, but largely, the legal basis for treating this data is non-existent unless if there is a significant breach of data. However, complaints from data subjects are unlikely to arise. This, therefore, leaves businesses to or not carry out data protection practices. While it is hoped that this loophole will be covered up, there is a high likelihood of the continuity of the personal data black market.

1.6.2.6.4 Criticism four: Inferred Data

Furthering his argument, Madge (2017), explained that “inferred data” implies information that is not in the original format in which it was collected but can be referred to as personal data because it identifies a person. Data derived from the Internet of Things (IoT) falls well within this category. Data of this sort falls under the definition of the profiling that GDPR covers in the context of direct marketing or in situations where profiling could have a significant effect on the individual. Recent studies show that this is a hitch in GDPR because, for example, in a scenario where data gained from an individual is used to promote other services to him or her; though the person can object to direct marketing and have the advert stopped, there is no obligation on the part of the data controller to inform the original data owner that his information had been sold to a third party. The question of whose interest it serves comes to mind when dealing with the issue of inferred data. Under the GDPR law, except in special cases

where an individual is at risk or threatened by the volume of sensitive data being processed, the independent data controller can access and make a decision based on the interest of the organization without seeking to consult the data subject. Article 13 of the law permits the controller to describe his (organization's) interest or the interest of the third party (where it applies) without clearly stating or considering the interest of the subject of the data.

Still looking at the issue of the inferred data, the case of C-141/12, *YS v Minister Voor Immigratie* points a limitation to data subjects. In this case, the data subject was denied access to her data analysis stating that the analysis was not personal data even though it contained personal information. The limitation is that a company is liable as far as the raw data is concerned but at the point that it becomes inferred and a breach occurs, a business organization is not obligated to the data subject at this point. Taking it further using the example of an online educational agency that wants to keep the personal information of an individual without being subject to any form of obligation, this agency would simply exploit the loophole in GDPR by transforming the data by tweaking one algorithm or the other to enhance its level of legal backing. This manipulation could be taken to another level where the agency may decide to recreate the original information if they decide to, but in the meantime, they could delete the raw original data by invoking the data principle of minimization. If someone cannot gain access to a copy of his data, they will not be aware of the exact data that is in the custody of the controller. Hence, will lack the ability to correct any inaccuracies nor will they be able to contest for the issue of 'inferences' drawn from their data by the controller. This becomes complicated because although an individual grants consent to make use of original data, he or she may not be able to obtain the portability of the same data once inferred (Hert, et al., 2018) Additionally, this loophole can be abused by EU companies when dealing with customers in the EU especially those from non-European countries of the world.

1.6.3 The Nigerian Data Protection Approach: Past and Present Policies

In Africa, a recent study shows that 19 African countries (Angola, Benin, Burkina Faso, Chad, Equatorial Guinea, Mali, Gabon, Ghana, Ivory Coast, Lesotho, Madagascar, Malawi, Morocco, Niger, Senegal, South Africa, Tunisia, and Zambia) have established and enforced data protection and privacy laws. Nigeria is experiencing an exponential rise in technological trends. Recent studies are beginning to probe the potential capacity of emerging economies like Nigeria, Ghana, and South Africa and the impact perceived privacy concern plays on the engagement of consumers in these regions of the world. One of the key interactions, Nigeria has with online consumption is through social media interactions, e-commerce, modern technology devices, and little of the Internet of Things (IoT). Burton (2018) in his study on developing countries' scope of things with GDPR found that countries such as Kenya, Nigeria, Togo, Tanzania, Uganda, and Zimbabwe have drafted laws that are at different stages of implementation and the rest of the countries are yet to formulate any law that protects consumers' privacy.

The study reveals that Nigeria has been tagged by many investors as a viable hub for e-commerce to thrive. Findings show that Africa, to which Nigeria stands out, has more concerns about security and online commerce as against other parts of the world as indicated by (Miao & Jayakar, 2016) report. According to the study, shoppers in Africa are most likely to see data security as a hurdle to shopping online in their own country. Meanwhile, Eastern European customers show minimal concerns about payment security.

Examining the prospects of e-commerce implementation in Nigeria, (Ayo, 2006) observed that factors such as the number of people who owns a PC, mobile phone, access to the internet, and payment cards make Nigeria's prospect high, yet sales are still largely done the traditional way due to slow acceptance of technology advancement. Data from his study shows that due to low payments made through card systems (36.2% which is relative to the over 180 million of population), the cash-based economy, and the fear of fraud, the thrive of e-commerce in the country is a near impossibility.

These reviews point in a direction: Nigeria has great prospects in e-commerce going by its demographic strength which is heavily skewed towards the youths; the growing middle class; the wide use of technology, mobile to be precise; the present broadband penetration, and a few other factors. This points out that Nigeria looks good with e-commerce and there could be a viable case to build a sustainable industry in the niche; however, challenges such as fraud,

cybercrime, lack of trust, and inadequate infrastructure and regulatory policies seem to be a threat to this emerging market, hence impacting on the consumer engagement. Just recently, within 2018, major e-commerce companies such as Konga and Olx have closed their operations in Nigeria alleging it to several factors, but user behavior is one of these factors that affected their profitability, hence leading to outright closure.

Jumia, one of Nigeria's leading online retail stores and e-commerce sites stated that Nigeria has a much higher penetration rate than across Africa of 18% and that the country continues to experience a path, through the increasingly wide highway, that is positioning it as the continent's highest internet penetration rate of about 55% which corresponds to 97.2 million internet users, (Afolabi, 2017). The demographic demand of Nigeria which leans heavily towards youths and middle-aged between the ages of 15 and 54 years of age, gaining 50.13% of Nigeria's population estimated to be 186,053,386 (Ibabor & Obarisiagbon, 2016), puts the country's prospect to thrive in e-governance a worthy argument. A PwC report in 2013 reveals that Nigeria, with a projected GDP of nearly US\$4 trillion by 2050 and an annual average real GDP growth rate of around 6% as well as a youthful and growing working population, is projected to rank 13th among the world's largest economies by 2050 if it can realize its full potential (Economics, 2013).

The Nigerian Communications Commission (NCC), Nigeria's telecoms regulatory commission, reports that the number of internet users on the country's telecom networks increased to more than 93 million (Chidozie & Olutosin, 2015). PayPal buttressing these facts in a survey carried out in 2015 shows that 65% of internet users in Nigeria already shop online and a further 24% are expected to do so in the future. Little wonder the high flow of online retail stores and e-commerce sites and dealers competing for the virtual retail space in Nigeria. Among those leading the Nigerian e-commerce space includes Jumia, Konga, Kaymu, DealDey, Yudala, PayPorte, Jiji, just to mention a few. As e-commerce advance to becoming a formidable business globally and Nigeria looking promising for it to thrive, recent reports seem to be pointing in the direction that adoption and usability of e-commerce remain low and discouraging. Yudala, one of the front-line e-commerce firms in Nigeria, in a report in April 2017 said that a good number of Nigerians are still skeptical about adopting e-commerce and most especially when it comes to using their debit card to complete any form of transaction online.

As attractive and promising as eCommerce is in Nigeria reports point to one direction – ‘the growth of e-commerce in Nigeria is being stunted’; data from Nigerian Inter-Bank Settlement System (NIBSS) shows this. NIBSS raised concern about the challenges of commerce in Nigeria pointing out that in 2014, there were 1,461 reported cases of e-fraud leading to losses grossing about \$14,500,000. Likewise, about 946 attempted e-fraud cases were also documented by banks in 2015, Other Financial Institutions (OFIs), and Mobile Payment Operators (MPOs), resulting in an estimated loss of \$12,000,000. Nigeria’s present Minister of Communications, Hon. Barr. Adebayo Shittu said that about \$187,200,200 is lost yearly in Nigeria to all forms of cybercriminal activities. Oxford Business Group in May 2016, reported that the Nigeria e-commerce platforms need to overcome some structural hurdles if it must breakthrough, pointing out that while successful global e-commerce businesses like Amazon in the US are on an upward doing, Nigeria (and the African space as a whole) presents a unique set of challenges and one of such hurdles is the payment process for online purchases. Unlike e-commerce users in developed countries of the world who prefer online payments and going cashless, many Nigerian customers are on the contrary and rather prefer to pay cash on delivery than make payment online. Buttressing this, PayPal survey, according to Oxford Business Group revealed that 31% of Nigerians who are familiar with eCommerce and have the requisite infrastructure to carry out transactions do not shop online. (Okoro & Kigho 2013) points out that Nigerian consumers’ source for information online, then make purchases the traditional way.

Likewise, in a study conducted in Urban Ghana, a remarkable gap was noted in the way security matters are handled by online service providers when compared with global best practices. There is a fact that online security threats are global, but threat perception is localized generally. The study found the major security measure taken by online users in Ghana is the reliance on the defense of passwords and their memorization. Quite unfortunately, the study found that the respondents rarely change their passwords and often keep them in manners that are unsafe and reused often. To the best of their knowledge, Ghanaian customers believe that online security means password protection and once that is compromised, they do not see any law that protects them. This exposes the fact that most Ghanaian online consumers are oblivious of how valuable their data is and the potential loss or harm they may suffer should a case of data breach occur.

They noted that some online users go through great lengths in protecting their privacy and security like clearing their browser history, deleting messages, etc., which are although imperfect, still show security measures. The respondents are quite adept with social

engineering like phishing and outright internet scams by imposters, but they are outrightly unfamiliar with other types of data theft that fall outside the existing scope of what they are used to. The study also shows that a potential threat exists of consumer's data being exploited by businesses, within and outside the EU due to the ignorance of the people as well as their obvious lack of data privacy law that protects them. Obviously, by not being covered by GDPR, a potential threat exists of online consumers' data being compromised, even by businesses in EU countries.

1.6.3.1 Nigeria's Past Data Protection Laws

Before this research, Nigeria did not have a solid Data Protection Policy in place. Though there were bills created to regulate information technology, none had legislative backing. Among these bills were the Electronic Fraud Prohibition Bill 2008, the Computer Security and Critical Information Infrastructure Protection Bill 2005, The Cyber Security and Data Protection Agency Bill 2008, The Computer Misuse Bill, The Economic and Financial Crimes Commission Act Bill 2010, and the Nigeria Computer Security Protection Agency. Out of all the bills only 2 are related to the issue of Data protection, which is the Information Secret Act and the Freedom of Information Act, but they were never passed into law.

1.6.3.2 The Official Secrets Act

The purpose of this Act was to secure public safety and the Act contains nine sections of which only two are relevant to Data Protection. Section one of the Act relates to the 'Protection of Official Information' which states that: a person is guilty of a data breach if he or she transmits any classified matter to another person without the authorization of the government, or without authorization from the government to obtain, reproduce or retain any classified information. Secondly, an officer of public office who does not adhere to any instructions given to him by the government regarding the safeguarding of any classified information, which through the authority of his office, he obtains or controls, is also guilty of an offense.

Thirdly, according to subsection one of this section – in respect to a breach of classified information, a person can defend himself by using one of these: When a person is guilty of transmitting or reproducing classified information, he or she can in defense claim that he did not know the information was classified; If he knew or came to know the information as classified, he should immediately place his knowledge of the information at the disposal of the Nigeria police force. The fourth section of the Official Secrets Act relates to the control of mail forwarding agencies, which states that the minister may make regulations for the following: for

controlling how an organization deals with letters, telegrams, packages, or any other matter concerning delivery or forwarding of another person's personal information; provide for the furnishing of information and keeping of records by persons having or ceasing to have conduct of such organization.

In addition, based on the consideration of the Minister, additional provisions can be made to supplement this regulation when expedient. This includes the introduction of penalties but not exceeding 3 months or a \$240 fine or both. However, the regulations under this section shall not come into force until they are approved by the resolution of each House of the National Assembly. As such, the above regulations only dealt with classified information belonging to the government alone and not to private individuals, and the Act deals with government officials mishandling classified information. Section nine of the Act further describes classified information as any information under any system of security classification in use by any arm of government, which is not to be disclosed to the public and if in the case of a disclosure would be detrimental to the security of the country. Hence, the only type of information under the protection of this Act are those which would cause a breach in the security of the country. Lastly, the law considers such information as an asset of the government for which disclosure is punishable but no compensation for the owner of such information is addressed.

Likewise, concerning mail forwarding agencies, section four of the Act provides a futuristic preparation for Internet Service Providers that handle electronic data and mail. In the exact words, the law says, '*for controlling the way any individual or organization receives letters, packages, telegram, or other items for delivery or forwarding to another person*'. This seems to cater to all kinds of information transfer through electronic means; however, the current situation with data protection is more delicate. Hence the law has been criticized to be inefficient (Jemilohun & Akomolede, 2015). The Act intended to make private the transfer of information about government to the public and over the years it is believed to have been used to prevent citizens from knowing the activities of government and all efforts to inquire were thwarted by the Official Secrets Act.

1.6.3.3 The Freedom of Information Act (FOIA)

In 2011, this Act was enacted. It was intended to give the public access to public information which unlike the Official Secrecy Act was impossible. It is also intended to protect officers serving in public office from facing adverse consequences if they disclose public information. Just like the Official Secret Act, it deals with classified matters in the custody of public

organizations. On the other hand, there is a conflict of interest between the right to privacy and the right to know, being that data protection and privacy laws seek to provide restrictions on information disclosure while the Freedom of Information Act permits access to information. However, the access the Act provides is only for public information; hence, it cannot be referred to as a protection for private information as in the case of the European data protection laws which caters for the protection of private information from abuse by organizations at large (Jemilohun & Akomolede, 2015). Nevertheless, the Act has been criticized in three ways. Firstly, it does not match the standard for which data protection is formed. Secondly, it does not differentiate between private information and public information, or reference to the information in the hand of private individuals. Thirdly, the act contains no penalty for the abuse, loss, or misuse of information (Jemilohun & Akomolede, 2015).

1.6.3.4 The Computer Security and Critical Information Infrastructure Bill

In 2005, this bill was made public, and the objective of the bill was to secure computer systems and networks and safeguard critical information infrastructure in Nigeria, by barring certain unwanted computer-based activities. Crimes such as hacking, internet fraud, cyber-squatting, cyberterrorism, computer forgery, identity theft, impersonation on the internet, misuse of the computer for sexual gains, and spamming in breach of this bill would attract a fine of \$2,400 and in some cases a jail term starting from 6 months. Nonetheless, we see that in the now modern world, internet crimes are prevalent, and measures set up to prevent or track down these offenders are ineffective (Jemilohun & Akomolede, 2015).

The Bill further mandates all service providers to keep a record of all traffic and subscribers' information on their computer networks and hold any information at the request of the Law Enforcement Agency, until such a time deemed by the president. In addition, the Bill allowed the Law Enforcement Agency to request for the release of information using a warrant issued by a court of competent jurisdiction. Notably, the Bill ensures that the privacy and liberties of individuals are protected by requiring that there is a legitimate and legal use of every information released by service providers and authorized by a court of competent jurisdiction or by the affected individual. In continuation of this, the Bill demands that in carrying out their duties, law enforcement agencies must ensure that they comply with the constitutional right to freedom of privacy which is guaranteed under the Nigerian Constitution of 1999, and undertake the right measures to protect the confidentiality of the information obtained, retained and processed to enforce the law. To ensure that service providers and corporate organizations

comply with the bill, it recommends that any breach by the above bodies after conviction shall be fined up to and not more than \$12,000. Likewise, any person in a managerial or directorate position in such an organization will be fined \$1,200USD or imprisoned for a minimum of three years or be served both a fine and a prison term. However, the Bill makes the proposed law more of a punishment than of protection (Jemilohun & Akomolede, 2015).

The criticism of the Bill is based on the following premise: firstly, there is zero involvement of an independent body to monitor the compliance with the provisions made in the bill other than the law enforcement agents; secondly, the bill does not provide an award of compensation to individuals whose information has been lost or compromised – rather imposes high penalties which may, in turn, enrich the pockets of the officers in charge of collecting such penalties. Although the provisions of the Bill try to secure data, it is not a direct source of data protection. A comparison with the European data protection law would show some of the weaknesses of the Bill in that it does not define what personal data is, it does not identify the right to privacy, it does not define what data subjects right is, it does not appoint a body to regulate the compliance or breaches of the provisions thereof and fails to provide exceptions where data can be used without the consent of the data owner. Though the Bill was written, it was never passed into law (Jemilohun & Akomolede, 2015).

In 2015, Nigeria witnessed an increase in the demand for personal data. With an event such as in the year 2009, when the Nigeria Communications Commission instructed subscribers to GSM phones services to register their sim cards with operators like MTN, GLO, etc. This same directive has become even more firm in 2019, being that an individual cannot have a functional sim card without having to register it, and in the event of a loss or request to retrieve the sim card, the individual will have to go to a court of competent jurisdiction to swear an affidavit that the sim was lost or stolen. With such restrictions placed on obtaining a sim card in Nigeria, there has been evidence of much compliance from the members of the public. However, there have been cases where some friends, family members, or even employees of companies have registered a sim card on behalf of someone. Such an act is deemed dangerous if peradventure, the sim in question is used by someone else to engage in unlawful activities, the law enforcement agency can demand the identity and personal details of the person who registered the sim card. A loophole exists in this directive because at the time the directive was implemented, there was no objection to the lack of legislative framework for such an exercise being carried out, many Nigerians gave away their personal information to these telecommunication companies, not considering that their data could have been sold to the third

party or misused. In these times people received messages from services they did not subscribe to, which begs the question ‘could their data have been sold’?

Nigeria as a growing economy has since passed the era of using computers connected through wired telephone lines. Since the introduction of internet-enabled mobile phones, the use of these computers has become obsolete. A statistical report in 2012 of global internet users showed that Africa was 7% out of 16,335,676 global internet users. With the emergence of online e-commerce companies such as Konga, Jumia, Buyright, Mystore, etc., individuals are required to give out their personal information to such companies. The presence of such companies increases the need for a legislative approach towards the use of personal data (Jemilohun & Akomolede, 2015).

1.6.3.5 The 2013 NITDA Regulations for Data Protection

After many failed attempts on data protection, Information gathered from research shows that in 2007, former President of the Federal Republic of Nigeria introduced the National Information Technology Development Agency (NITDA), responsible for implementing national information technology policy through a framework for planning, research, development, standardization, application, coordination, monitoring, evaluation and regulations of information technology practices in Nigeria. However, in September 2013, the NITDA draft guidelines were released to serve as a compulsory guideline for local, state, and federal government private and public sectors, institutions, and agencies. A breach of the guidelines would be a breach in the Section 6,17 and 18 of NITDA Act. The guideline permits a periodic review by NITDA while developing better and advance ways of tackling data protection issues.

1.6.3.5.1 NITDA Act Provisions on Data Protection

As an alternative to the use of paper-based methods of communication in the government, educational sector, commerce, labor, public and private sector, NIDTA provided a guideline to oversee and monitor the use of electronic data exchange and all other forms of communication transactions. This is the only part of the guideline that points towards data protection. Other sections like 17 and 18 of the NITDA Act addresses offenses such as failure to comply with the provisions of the Act (but no specific penalty is stated), the liability of officers, failure to pay when appropriate, and the need for the agency to work under the Standard Organisation of Nigeria in enforcing the guidelines of the Act.

1.6.3.5.2 NITDA Draft Guidelines

The 2013 NITDA guidelines bear a similarity with that of NITDA 2007, which stipulates that the agency will formulate guidelines to aid the development of information technology in Nigeria. It also went further to say that every Nigerian citizen's data

which it refers to as '*identifiable information*' will be protected. The draft was divided into three main parts. Part one deals with authority which the guidelines are based on, the scope it covers the purpose and definition of the terms of the guideline, and the applications thereof. Part two deals with aspects concerning data protection, guidelines for processing data, accessing data, and guidelines for data security officers. Part three states the principles for data protection which mirrors the principles initiated by the European Data Protection Directive. The NITDA guidelines suggest that it aims to recommend procedures for organizations responsible for controlling, collecting, storing, and processing personal data of residents inside and outside Nigeria in the private and public sectors. However, it failed to guarantee a cover for the processing of data relating to defense, public security, national security, and other activities in Nigeria in the area of criminal law (Jemilohun & Akomolede, 2015).

1.6.3.5.3 NITDA Guidelines for Collecting Data

Section two of the NITDA guidelines separate data collection from its processing, which is difficult as data cannot be collected without undergoing processing. It is also identical to section two of the United Kingdom's 1998 Data Protection Act. Furthermore, the controllers of data, who could be persons with legal authority or just ordinary citizens, are deemed responsible for the protection of privacy of the citizens by determining the aim or means for processing data. Secondly, the guidelines strictly forbid the collection of data that will reveal race, ethnicity, political opinions, philosophical or religious beliefs, sex, health, and trade union membership with exception to certain circumstances.

Thirdly, in a case where data is not obtained directly from the owner of the data, the controller of the data must provide the data owner information on what the data will be used for, who the data will be shared with, and give the data owner access to rectify such that about the owner at will. The fourth aspect of the guidelines covers the transfer of personal information which is undergoing processing or unprocessed until it reaches the intended destination, which can be another country. The transfer is only permitted on the condition that the recipient country will ensure a satisfactory level of protection. This guideline is like the EU 1995 Data Protection

Directive (DPP) which prohibited the transfer of information internationally to countries that did not adhere to or have a solid data protection policy in place.

The fifth guideline gives the controllers of data 12 months from the date of adoption of the guideline to provide administrative directives to enable them to comply with the provisions of the guideline. However, this does not mount pressure on data controllers. Lastly, the guidelines for collecting data mandates organizations to develop and implement comprehensive and effective privacy policies and procedures, which will be visible online and offline to ensure that Nigerians will understand and have confidence in the use of their personal information. It is, however, a challenge as this is only a guideline, but an average Nigerian does not know what data protection is and businesses seek to avoid legal compliance with the law. Nigeria telecommunication companies do not respect the privacy of its citizens going by the increased number of unwanted texts and calls made to people's phones daily. If data protection law is unlegislated, then the tendency for abuse of data will increase (Jemilohun & Akomolede, 2015).

1.6.3.5.4 Guidelines Principle for Data Protection 2013

The final section of the NITDA 2013 draft seeks to outline the set of principles that support Data Protection Guidelines. Eight principles serve as a bedrock for data protection policies that are universally accepted. They are as follows: *personal data* must be processed lawfully and fairly; *personal data* shall only be used for the purpose for which it was intended; *personal data* must be suitable and relevant, avoiding the addition of unnecessary information; *personal data* must not be kept longer than required; *personal data* must be accurate and updated regularly; *personal data* must be processed in consideration with the right of the data owners. To protect personal data, the right technical and organizational measures must be incorporated and unless adequate protection is adopted, personal data must not be transferred outside Nigeria.

1.6.3.5.5 Criticism of NITDA 2013 Guidelines

NITDA made a commendable effort towards tackling the issue of data protection in Nigeria however, the drafted guidelines have been found inadequate in handling the problems of data protection. Professor Akomolede and Dr. Jemilohun's article highlighted some shortcomings of the guidelines. Firstly, the guidelines lack legislative backing. it suggests that data subjects can opt-out of data sharing if the controller thinks their data will be used for marketing but says the data subject does not have a right to do so. Secondly, the guideline does not state or create

a legal right of the data owners, rather it creates liabilities for data controllers. Thirdly, it also does not specify a method of obtaining compensation nor the amount of compensation to be given to data owners over the loss of their data and in the event of non-payment, the data subject becomes helpless (Jemilohun & Akomolede, 2015). Fourthly, the method of enforcing the guidelines is not stated; therefore, there is a tendency for data abuse. Lastly, the most glaring shortcoming is the 12-months elasticity given to data controllers to formulate administrative policies to carry data protection practices in the organization, in which the 12-months period does not begin until they adopt the guideline. This is an open window for many organizations to ignore data protection requirements, as they can use the timeframe as an excuse to postpone implementation. Yet if there are no measures for enforceability, how can these organizations be tracked to see if they have data protection policies in place. In conclusion, the guideline poses more as an advisory tool for organizations to formulate their policies rather than legislative enforcement with legal sanctions in the case of noncompliance (Jemilohun & Akomolede, 2015).

1.6.3.6 African Union Convention on Cyber Security and Personal Data Protection 2014

In 2014, the African union – an association of Africa states – came up with a treaty aimed at tackling the issues of data protection and cyber security. The African Union is made up of 55 members – Nigeria inclusive. The treaty is like that of the European Union regulation for data protection but with an expansion into cyber security. The treaty was formulated with consideration of the fact that the development of electronic commerce in Africa is highly linked to the issues of cyber security (Africa Union, 2014).

The African Union also mandated that all member state sign a document as proof of their acceptance of the treaty. Furthermore, it appointed a chairperson charged with – but not limited to – some of the following responsibilities; Gathering information that is helpful for the successful implementation of cybersecurity policy in each member state; Submit reports to the executive council of the African Union about the progress made by each member state with regards to the implementation of the treaty; Advise member state on the best way to promote cyber security and combat the surge of cybercrimes (Africa Union, 2014).

At the time of this research, only 14 out of 55 members of the African Union had signed the treaty and sadly, Nigeria has not signed. Such response towards a treaty aimed at combating cybercrime which has surged in Africa, especially Nigerian, is a clear reflection of the government's attitude towards tackling data protection and cyber security issues (Union, 2014).

1.6.3.7 The Economic and Financial Crimes Commission (EFCC)

The Economic and financial crimes commission (EFCC) was founded in 2003 and charged with the responsibility of combating financial crimes. It is meant to prevent, investigate, prosecute, and penalize those guilty of involving in perpetuating financial crimes. Additionally, the EFCC is also responsible for enforcing the provision of other laws which includes The Money Laundering Act 1995; The Advance Fee Fraud and Other Fraud Related Offences Act 1995; The Failed Banks (Recovery of Debts), and Financial Malpractices in Bank Act 1994 and The Money Laundering (Prohibition) Act 2004 (Commission, 2021).

Since its inception, the EFCC has combated a significant number of financial crimes. However, the organization has been accused of carrying out unfair arrests of youths, unfair prosecution, and corruption within its system. On July 6th, 2020, the acting chairman of the EFCC – Ibrahim Magu, was arrested by the Department of State Services (DSS) on allegations of transferring funds abroad through a third party belonging to corruption perpetrators (Gistreel, 2020). Further inquiry into the allegation revealed that Magu had distributed 222 properties that were seized by corrupt officials without the authorization of the president (Vanguard, 2021).

Given these challenges, it is obvious that the federal government needs to put more effort into combating fraud, data theft, and cybercrime in Nigeria and within its system.

1.6.3.8 Nigeria's Current Data Protection Regulation

Where we are now

Since the introduction of the NITDA 2013 Guideline, there has not been any recorded evidence of sanctions on data misuse in Nigeria. However, in the sudden wake of the EU GDPR, there has been a high emergence for countries far and near to wake up to their responsibility towards safeguarding the personal data of their citizens. In response to this urgency, the National Information Technology and Development Agency (NITDA), in a bid to fulfill its responsibility as stated in the 2013 guidelines which permit it to conduct a periodic review, issued a new NDPR (Nigeria Data Protection Regulation) policy on January 25th, 2019. The NDPR is alarmingly identical to the EU General Data Protection Regulation. Though we do not fault NITDA's attempt to provide a standard Data Protection Regulation by using the policy from a more advanced continent like Europe, the issues lie firstly in the applicability of such regulations in a different terrain as Nigeria, a developing nation. Secondly, are there measures for enforceability and monitoring? Thirdly, are there sanctions for non-compliance? Has there

been an improvement from the 2013 Guideline and the 2019 regulation? Lastly, are the citizens aware or familiar with the term data protection? A close examination of the provisions of the 2019 regulations will ascertain the answer to the foregoing questions.

1.6.3.9 The Nigeria Data Protection Regulation (NDPR) 2019

A Step Forward

The NDPR 2019 is a step up from the 2013 NDPR 2013 guideline because while the 2013 guideline deals with which recommendation of procedures for data protection, the 2019 guideline provides an actual policy to follow. The new NDPR contains mainly four parts, the first section covered the objectives, scope, and relevant definitions of the policy just as the initial 2013 guideline, which is aimed at safeguarding citizens of Nigeria living in and outside Nigeria. The scope of the regulations controls the activities of data controllers who are involved in the collection, controlling, processing, and storage of personal data. Also included in the document was a definition of what personal data constitutes as. It says any information that can be used to identify a person. This includes name, address, bank details, location, contact number, age, date of birth, photograph, email, identification number, medical record, sim, posts on the website, etc. However, included in the definitions is the Data Protection Compliance Organisation (DPCO), an entity licensed by NITDA to enable the implementation and compliance of the regulation which was not previously included in the NDPR 2013 Guideline.

1.6.3.9.1 Rights of the Data Subject

The regulation also stipulated that citizens had rights and stated the rights as follows: Data subjects are entitled to know their rights; this also requires that data collectors must make data subjects aware of their rights before collecting their data by providing a comprehensive policy easily accessible for them to read. Secondly, data subjects are required to provide consent without duress to data controllers before their data can be obtained or processed. It is the responsibility of the data controllers to ensure that the data subject has the legal capacity to provide consent. Thirdly, data subjects can, without restrictions, demand for their data to be deleted or request correction to data held about them and demand to know what information the data controller holds about them. However, the regulation included that the data controller could demand a fee if the request made by the data subject is excessive and will incur some expense. The data controller can also refuse but send a refusal letter to the data subject and the

agency, stating the grounds for refusal. Lastly, the data subject can decide at will to transfer their data from one controller to another.

1.6.3.9.2 Transferring information outside Nigeria

If the data controller wishes to transfer personal data to a foreign country, they must seek the permission of the Attorney General of the Federation and comply with the decisions and supervision of NIDTA.

1.6.3.9.3 Dealing with breaches and non-compliance

In the case of a breach or an allegation of data misuse, there is an Administrative Redress Panel (ARP) set up by NITDA whose responsibility is to investigate any allegation of breach of the regulation and fix an appropriate redress within 28 working days. However, the data subject still has the right to seek redress in a court of competent jurisdiction.

1.6.3.9.4 Penalties for non-compliance

In the case of a breach of the right of any data subject, the offender is liable to pay a fine under one of these circumstances: If a Data controller who deals with more than 10,000 data subjects is guilty of a breach, he or she is liable to pay 2% of the preceding year annual gross revenue or \$24,000. Secondly, if a data controller who deals with less than 10,000 data subjects is guilty of a breach, he or she is liable to pay 1% of the preceding year's annual gross revenue or \$5,000.

1.6.3.9.5 Instant Compliance demand for Data Controllers

One of the criticisms of the 2013 NITDA guideline was the 12months period laxity which encouraged non-compliance. However, the NITDA 2019 required that all Data controllers comply immediately following the issuance of the regulation on January 19, 2019. The following dates were set to force compliance: No later than the 25th of April 2019, all data controllers should make their data policy available to the public which must be under the regulation. Secondly, before the 25th of July 2019, all data controllers must carry out a detailed audit of their data privacy and data protection policies, for which they may need the services of a NITDA licensed Data Protection Compliance Organisation (DPCO). Thirdly, any data controller dealing with over 1000 Data Subjects must before the 25th of July 2019 submit an audit report to NITDA. But if the data Controller deals with more than 2000 data subjects, they must submit their audit report by March 15th, 2019. Lastly, all data Controllers must appoint a Data Protection Officer either within the organization or externally who will ensure the organization's compliance with the regulation and their data policies.

The tide of GDPR and NDPR sweeps across every sector, and educational agencies are not left out in the wave. Colleges and universities are also subject to some level of rules and regulations regarding how they collect, disseminate, share, store and use personal data of their students through the chain from application to placements. In line with the larger data reforms and transparency across the globe, data and information is increasingly a pivotal requirement to many aspects of the international education sector. For example, the use of agents as a bridge to recruit students from international communities to universities and institutions of higher learning has come to stay. A study carried out by Lawton (2014), a think tank and educationist pointed out that the use of agents has become a routine as more countries like America included, are now lifting the long-standing ban on agents who are paid a commission for educational services rendered.

A survey by Observatory in 2013 on 181 universities and colleges in seven countries reported the following figures as a proportion of international students who have been recruited by agents into universities and colleges: Australia - 53%, Netherlands - 20%, Canada - 41%, United States - 28%, United Kingdom - 38%, Malaysia - 56% and New Zealand - 47%. A publication by New Zealand Immigration observed that education agents which include exempt advisers or agents and licensed immigration advisers (LIAs) make up critical aspects of the international education system of New Zealand. A report of education agent performance data compiled by New Zealand immigration in the first half of 2018, — from January to June 30th — found that the Vietnam market recorded an 82% visa approval rate with a total of 546 student visas granted. Philippine's market witnessed an 83% approval rate with 638 students' visas granted; while in India, 81% approval occurred with 4805 students' visas issued. Many universities, especially in the United Kingdom, now engage in educational fairs in target countries where they plan to recruit students. The purpose of the fairs is to sensitize potential students on the benefits of studying in the UK and boost their trust and confidence in the agents representing them. Because applicants' data can serve a wide variety of purposes, investigations are now being made against the backdrop of how successfully information is collected, shared as well as its completeness, timeliness, consistency, accessibility, privacy sensitivity, equity and the extent of future-proof of data.

1.6.3.10 Nigerian Data Protection Regulation 2020 Compliance Framework

The data protection regulator published a compliance framework on how it intends to implement the new data protection law in Nigeria. The framework indicated that the regulator

will now allow private firms who meet certain criteria to act as compliance agents to data controllers. These private firms will be called ‘Data Protection Compliance Organisations (DPCOs). The framework allows any legally registered company to apply to act as DPCOs provided they meet the following criteria: A DPCO must be either a professional consultancy or service firm; audit firm; information technology service provider; or a law firm. Furthermore, the DPCO must have an experience of data protection evidenced by a certification in data science, data protection, and privacy, information audit, information security, information privacy, information technology due diligence, EU implementation of and compliance with GDPR, cyber security law, data analytics and data governance (National Information Technology Development Agency, 2020).

In addition, the regulatory authority will give license to the approved DPCO to provide the following services to data controllers: advisory services, training and awareness, contract drafting, breach remedies, and support, privacy breach impact assessment, outsourced data protection officer (DPO), and information privacy audit. DPCOs are asked to pay a licensing fee of \$121 annually (National Information Technology Development Agency, 2020).

A data controller is required under this regulation to appoint a data protection officer (DPO) under the following criteria: The data controller is a government entity or agency; its core activities involve the processing of large sets of data subjects per annum; it regularly processes sensitive personal data as part of its core business; it processes personal data that are part of the national databases (National Information Technology Development Agency, 2020). Three loopholes exist with this compliance framework; Firstly, the criteria to appoint a (DPO) allows for some organizations to be exempted. Secondly, the regulation does not set out a pricing guideline for DPCOs in providing the listed services to data controllers. Such omission will consequently give room for overpricing which may discourage many businesses from compliance. Thirdly, the regulatory gives DPCOs the responsibility for creating awareness to and training of data controllers. As data protection issues affect all, the compliance framework leaves out an organization that does not meet the criteria for appointing a DPO and leaves out awareness creation for the public.

1.6.3.10.1 NDPR compliance checklist for data controllers

The major responsibility for ensuring compliance lies with the data controllers. The Nigerian data protection regulatory authority introduces a checklist to guide data controllers on enhancing compliance. The checklist contains the following:

- a. Information audit.
- b. Processing data on a lawful basis.
- c. Provide clear information on data processing activities to the data subject in plain writing, orally, electronic means, or as requested by the data subject.
- d. Fulfill publicity of privacy through the website, digital media, posted at conspicuous part of the business, reading it to the data subject over the phone or otherwise, and publication in any public media.
- e. Build data processors based on NDPR data protection regulatory requirements.
- f. Provide training to all persons involved in processing data within the organization.
- g. Develop and circulate data protection strategy to all staff within the organization.
- h. Conduct data protection impact assessment when embarking on a project that might involve significant risks to the rights and freedom of data subjects.
- i. Appoint a Data Protection Officer.
- j. Design systems that make data request easy for data subjects for corrections, and transfer of data requests from data subjects.
- k. Make the process for objection easy for data subjects.
- l. Create a procedure for informing data subjects when an automated decision has been made on their behalf (National Information Technology Development Agency, 2020).

In summary, the regulatory framework aims to provide support to the data controller to enable them to meet the compliance requirement and minimize the risk of breaches and legal action. The framework is a step forward from when the regulation was first introduced in January 2019. Nonetheless, there is room for improvement.

1.7 Data policies awareness in Western and Nigerian context

The concept of data protection has gained momentum in western countries due to EU GDPR however, awareness in Africa particularly Nigeria is significantly low (Abdulrauf, 2015).

Abdulrauf (2015), highlights some causes of low data protection awareness level in Nigeria such as the political will of the government, the quality of the legal framework, little importance placed on data protection, underdevelopment of technology, poverty, and corruption. From the standpoint of the issue of poverty, it is understandable that a hungry man may not consider data protection as an issue. Some may even be willing to disclose their information and the information of others for a token. In a recent kidnapping reported by AIT news Warri Nigeria,

it was discovered that the leader of the group was a former driver to one of the bank managers of Zenith bank Nigeria – the victim. The driver had given full information to the gang that the boss had millions in his possession before the kidnap. Such an act could not have been possible without detailed information about the victim. Data protection issues when compared in western and African contexts vary because in Africa the consequence of data breach can birth damaging insecurity issues (Onoye, 2020). Hence, awareness is a serious responsibility that should not only be on the shoulders of the government but the public needs to be trained on how to protect their data.

In contrast, Olivero, and Lunt (2004) argue that data protection awareness poses a risk that would cause tension in the relationship between the data subject and data controllers. They added that awareness will make the commercial relationship between data subjects and data controllers no longer rely on trust alone because data subjects will increase their demand to control their information.

Culhan (1995), and Collier (1995) hold a different opinions about awareness issues. They argue that organizations should strive to meet data protection standards which include making the data subjects aware of what they use their information for. They believe that if data subjects are aware of what their data is used for, it will drive a positive attitude towards data protection.

1.8 Data protection theories: Consumer centered

1.8.1 Gossip Theory

The concept of privacy has been viewed differently by several researchers and among the public. The term privacy has been related to physical privacy while other information privacy. When the concept of privacy is discussed, varying responses emerge which are largely affected by how an individual's culture draws a boundary on what should be kept private and what should be made public. The concept of privacy is broad hence, to maintain focus on the aim of this study, few selected privacy theories will be discussed to allow a better understanding of the term 'data protection' as it relates to this study. However, many of the theories have been focused on data protection from the consumer's perspective and the impact of privacy laws on consumer behavior.

The psychology of consumer attitudes to a feeling of vulnerability is said to be informed by Gossip Theory putting into consideration the idea of unauthorized transmission of personal

data of a third party (Martin, et al., 2017). While researchers of Gossip report that an estimate of two-third of public social settings is dedicated to evaluative communication about a third party that is absent, (Feinberg, et al., 2012) affirmed that to be true, hence a lot of people have become proficient at recognizing gossip and guards against the vulnerability of becoming a gossip target (Beersma & Van Kleef, 2011). People react with an array of negative cognitive and emotional responses (Leary, 2015) when they learn that they are gossip targets. Some of such feelings include a high feeling of violation and betrayal and a reduced trust level. Bringing gossip theory to the context of business organization connotes that customer data vulnerability has a likelihood of leading to reduced cognitive and emotional evaluation of trust (Martin, et al., 2017) with control and transparency identified as two factors that repress the undesirable effects of unauthorized transmissions of information.

Martin, Borah & Palmatier, (2017) also notes that transparency in this context infers the awareness of the gossip target that his or her details are being shared, aware of the potential danger it could pose, and has can come with plans on how to counter such negative .

Control refers to the level a customer believes he can manage the information flow of his details thus, the perception of the inability to control one's data on learning that it is being shared leads to undesirable effects that surround a gossip event irrespective of whether the information in question is either positive or negative (Feinberg, et al., 2012). It can therefore be deduced that empowering customers with the ability to control their information and improved transparency will reduce the negative feeling of vulnerability (Baker, et al., 2005).

1.8.2 Privacy Regulation Theory – Irwin Altman 1975

The theory of privacy regulation was posited by Irwin Altman in 1975. The theory suggests that people may sometimes prefer to stay alone as opposed to having social interactions. Altman regarded privacy as a non-static process that allows *dialectic* and *dynamic* processes where access to privacy is selective control over oneself or one's group. According to Altman, dialectic is the ability for one to be open and close to others in seeking and avoiding social interactions while dynamic refers to one's desired level of privacy which is subject to change at any given time.

Furthermore, he claims that the goal of his theory is to achieve the ideal or optimal privacy level. At the optimal level, an individual can have the desired level of privacy if he or she chooses to either be alone or be with people. In addition, he claims that a person who has

control over the openness or closeness to others will have a better societal experience than those who do not. However, if the actualized privacy level is greater than the desired level, then the individual will end up feeling left alone, isolated which, may result in depression (Altman, 1975). The opposite of it will leave the individual feeling violated, annoyed, or crowded. To create a balance, he suggested the use of behavioral mechanisms such as, para verbal, verbal, and non-verbal behavior, environmental mechanisms of personal space through which an individual can effectively communicate his or her desired level of privacy at the given time. One of the implications of Altman's theory is that it challenged researchers to think about privacy in a social context, bringing dynamism in how people should regulate social interactions (Altman, 1975).

1.8.3 Theory of Privacy and Freedom (General Privacy) - Westin 1968

Westin considers general privacy as a person's voluntary or temporary withdrawal from society which can be through psychological or physical methods. Withdrawal in this sense can happen in a small group, large crowd, or a state of solitude (Dinev, et al., 2013). He recommends that there are four states of general privacy: intimacy, solitude, anonymity, and reserve. Pedersen (1997) gives a broader insight into the concepts of privacy as posited by (Westin 1968). He refers to Westin's state of privacy as types of privacy which are: Solitude, Isolation, Anonymity, Reserve, Intimacy with Friends, and Intimacy with Family.

Solitude privacy – refers to placing oneself in a place where no one will have access to see what you are doing. *Reserve Privacy* – refers to one's control over what is disclosed to others regarding his or her personal information. *Isolation Privacy* – is keeping physical distance from others to obtain privacy. *Intimacy with Family* – is being alone with one's family away from others. *Anonymity* – is seeking privacy by being deliberately unnoticed in a crowd. Lastly, *Intimacy with friends* – is the same as a family but rather with friends (Pedersen, 1997).

Contrary to the views of Westin (1968) and Altman (1975), psychologist's view of general privacy is different being that it is an emotional feeling rather than a sense of one right. They argue there is no logical reason why an individual should feel a violation of his or her privacy. By contrast, economists define privacy as a value in economic terms because of the role access to data plays in the economic market (Dinev, 2013).

Past scholars have looked at what general privacy is in varying concepts such as behavior, function, state, feeling, etc. These concepts cannot be interchanged. Additionally, they argue that general privacy has no links with solitude, secrecy, and autonomy (Dinev, et al., 2013)

Altman's theory (1975, p.24) of general privacy resonates with this study because his theory focuses on the concept of selective control of one's personal information. Furthermore, it resonates with the current push of the European Union Data Protection Regulation for which is targeted towards data subjects having control over what information organizations have about them (Governance, 2020).

Both Altman (1975) and Westin (1968), talk about privacy in terms of the state of control and limiting access. However, contrasting views in the literature suggest that the privacy concept can be applied to diverse contexts.

1.8.4 Nissenbaum Privacy Theory Contemporary works

The privacy theory agrees that the ability to control the information about oneself is an important element of information privacy however, the level of access external forces have to the information irrespective of who has control over the information is also important. A right to privacy is not necessarily a right to secrecy but a right to control the appropriate flow of a person's information (Nissenbaum, 2010).

Nissenbaum proposes 'context -relative information norms that govern the activities data subject and data controller in different contexts. She provides four parameters in analyzing privacy scenarios: context, actors, attributes, transmission principles.

Figure 1:Parameters for analyzing privacy scenarios (Nissenbaum, 2010)

Based on the theory, information flow in the context of the travel industry and educational travel industry will differ. Though both industries are very similar, however, the information they will require from clients will slightly differ. For example, the information required from a student to get them into university and through university will differ in the context of the travel industry where a client just wants to book a vacation to a chosen destination. The central theme of the theory is that the information required from data subjects will differ in a different context and that will affect the flow of information (Nissenbaum, 2010).

1.8.5 Information privacy awareness (IPA)

Although information privacy awareness has become important more than ever in recent times, a generally accepted definition of the concept. However, some scholars have attempted to define IPA from different perspectives. Thus, this section shall be considering some of the definitions of IPA as defined by different scholars.

As defined by Deuker (2010), “privacy awareness is individual user’s ability to identify and assess risks associated with the disclosure of personal information.” This definition sees IPA as knowing the likely consequences and possible consequences of disclosing personal information. Similarly, Konings et al. (2013) defined IPA as “someone’s ability to accurately

perceive potential privacy threats. Especially threats emanating from virtual entities, which are not physically present, and cannot be perceived without support.” These definitions imply that there could be resultant effects that can arise from the disclosure of personal information of people on the internet with organizations, as organizations could share the information with third parties that may put them at risk or lead to privacy invasion. This has made Enck et al. (2010) go further to state that IPA “includes not only the users’ knowledge of what information a service provider collects but also what are the possibilities of sharing this information with third parties.

Another perspective that has IPA has been considered is seeing it as a users’ awareness of privacy policies content and laws that defend or protect the privacy rights of individuals., Li et al. (2011) have defined IPA as “individual awareness of the content in the privacy statement of a website.

It has been argued that the information privacy awareness of people determines their privacy behavior on the internet. Although it is expected that high IPA will lead to careful online behavior, the behavior of some persons with perceived high IPA is conflicting with their actions. According to the study of Talib et al. (2014), it was discovered that participants that had high IPA had more careful online behavior, as it was discovered that 90% of Instagram users pay attention to the disclosure of personal information, and over 50% of them do not accept strangers and prefer to have few followers. Similarly, Consolvo et al. (2010) stated that “increased IPA leads users to adopt more protective practices with regards to online privacy.

As it is with high IPA, so also it is expected that low IPA will result in less careful privacy behavior online. According to the study of Nyoni and Velepini (2018), it was discovered that there is a relationship between low users; privacy behavior, and low IPA level as it was revealed that 33% of participants disclosed their full personal information, and 75% of the users either sometimes or often share their geo-location with the Facebook friends. In a similar study by Braghin and Vecchio (2017), it was reported that users are not aware of major privacy concerns, and they partially read privacy policies and most former users reported that they have not erased their account.

All definitions of IPA are relevant in that; they point to one important term “awareness”. Though different individuals will exhibit varying levels of IPA, the focal point is that their awareness level will affect the actions they will take towards data protection.

Soumelidou and Tsohou (2021) suggest the attributes in the figure below as the main criteria a data subject should have which is a direct reflection of their IPA level (Soumelidou & Tsohou, 2021).

Figure 2: Profile of Information Privacy User (Soumelidou & Tsohou, 2021)

The figure above depicts the attributes a data subject should possess.

Some of the key attributes for IPA user would be useful in combination with the NDPR’s compliance framework to ascertain if the travel agencies are aware and compliant.

1.8.5.1 IPA User Attribute 1

Through the investigation of selected works done on information privacy awareness, the authors concluded that an IPA user should not only be aware of the threats or consequences of information disclosure but should be able to protect their privacy online effectively.

1.8.5.2 IPA User Attribute 2

Data subjects often claim to have low Information privacy awareness level but they have some idea about data protection but lack the knowledge needed to protect their privacy (Braghin & Del, 2017) as such the authors suggest that a data subject should have a high IPA which is

expressed in their hesitation in to provide data to suspicious websites (Soumelidou & Tsohou, 2021).

1.8.5.3 IPA User Attribute 3

In addition, past literature reveals that data subjects with lower IPA are more susceptible to the risk of data misuse or breach (Braghin & Del, 2017). As a result, a data subject should have low-risk behavior expressed in extreme care in reading privacy laws or policies available on websites where their information is required (Soumelidou & Tsohou, 2021).

1.8.5.4 IPA User Attribute 4

Some researchers have indicated that there is a disparity between the perceived IPA level and the actual behavior of data subjects. This contradiction has led to many researchers suggesting ways to enhance data subject IPA level. Based on this evidence, the authors propose that a data subject should be familiar with the mechanisms for enhancing privacy awareness and be constantly updated with the progress made towards enhancing the protection of their data (Soumelidou & Tsohou, 2021).

1.8.5.5 IPA User Attribute 5

Finally, the authors argue that IPA should be applicable in all contexts. Thus, indicating that data subjects should be conscious of the protection of their privacy especially when it relates to disclosing their information to an external authority (Soumelidou & Tsohou, 2021).

1.8.5.6 The usefulness of IPA to the Study

Some of the key attributes for IPA users would be useful in combination with the NDPR's compliance framework to ascertain if the travel agencies are aware and compliant. Specifically, the data controller is a major actor in the subject of data protection.

Figure 3:Principal actors in data protection (Authored)

The figure above illustrates the principal actors in data protection.

If the data controllers do not collect data, there would be no need for regulation, and data subjects would not be saddled with any responsibility towards the security of their personal

information. On this basis, Information Privacy Awareness User Attributes (IPA) can be applied in the context of the travel industry. IPA attributes one focused on data subject awareness of potential threats to their data. In the same way, the data controller also needs to be aware of not just the penalty of a potential breach but, the negative impact that breach could potentially cause to the data subject. Likewise, regarding IPA attribute 2, not many travel agencies are aware of the Nigerian data protection laws and a consequence of this ignorance is that they would not press to get the needed knowledge required for protecting the data they hold of customers. For example, getting a data protection officer would not be a pressing need if they are unaware that such is required of them by the data protection regulatory authority. IPA attribute 3 for travel agencies is a case carelessness that could potentially arise from the transfer of data to third-party companies that may not have a data protection policy in place. Having such verification is very paramount which is why the EU GDPR prohibits trading with countries with little action towards data protection. IPA attribute 4 is a case of travel agencies taking up the responsibility in ensuring that they use data privacy security technologies to ensure proper encryption of data they collect, using secure servers, etc. Finally, IPA attributes 5 relates to travel agencies being at alert regarding the flow of data not only outside their organization but also amongst departments within their organization.

1.8.5.7 Limitations of IPA User Attribute

The IPA frameworks provide insights to both data controllers and regulatory bodies in developing policies and using technologies that can inform and protect the data subject. However, the framework has not yet been empirically validated and the attributes of the “data subject” were based on theoretical assumptions not considering the technical know-how of the data subject. For example, knowledge of how to browse the internet. Notwithstanding, the framework still serves as a skeletal guide towards providing solutions to factual data protection issues.

1.9 Data protection models and concepts

Chang, Wong, and Lee (2015), in a study that attempts to understand perceived privacy using a privacy boundary management model, stated that an unimaginable volume of data flows through the Internet on daily basis. This information contains pieces of data that range from basic and simple daily interactions to more complex and very delicate personal data which may include monetary information. This data often leaves behind digital trails of the activities of the users when effectively mined, stored, and even processed. These data eventually allow

organizations to have a good understanding of individual consumer preferences and their online behaviors. Valuable information of this kind helps organizations customize and personalize their products and services to properly meet the needs of consumers and the organizations' competitive advantage. Consumer data has become the bedrock that supports the present trend of big data, the Internet of Things (IoT), and analytics (Chang, 2015). The world today is intertwined, and a piece of data can no more be viewed in isolation. With the growing rate of data – in a highly exponential manner – within a few years, the world around us would have changed so rapidly in ways that we can scarcely imagine (Wachter, 2017).

Consumers now place a demand on acts and dividends on their privacy due to the increase in breach of trust, data compromise, and another cyber crisis. (LaSalle, 2015) recommended *five* principles to organizations' that can help them place value on personal information supplied to them. They recommended proper *digital stewardship* to ensure synchronization of consumer expectation with the management of data provided; *transparency* by the organization in how they make use of the data collected; *empowering users* to have control of their data, *equity* which explains the potential benefits consumers enjoy for exchanging their data; and *finally inclusion*, which explains how businesses make use of data to boost positive outcomes in the lives of people. The concerns raised by consumers on the status of their private data are closely connected to how the data is mined, kept, exchanged, and accessed by a third party (Nir, 2017). In the light of cases of breach of consumer's data, studies are beginning to probe the impact of privacy concerns on the perception of consumers.

1.9.1 Privacy Boundary Management Model

To understand perceived privacy concerns among consumers, (Chang, 2015) tested ma, an adaptation of the Communication Privacy Management (CPM) model by (Petronio, 2017) and the application of CPM in an information privacy context to have a comprehensive view of the management process of consumers' privacy boundary. The model puts together previous Fair Information Practices (FIPs) to study how consumers connect the aspects of FIPs to examine privacy policy's effectiveness. The model also studies, as its dependent variable, perceived privacy; hence, separating the concept from privacy concern and trust. Under the broad Privacy Boundary Management Model, the following models were examined: Perceived Privacy, Risk-Control Assessment, Privacy Policies, and Its Perceived Effectiveness.

1.9.1.1 Communication Privacy Management

The all-encompassing theory for this model is Communication Privacy Management (CPM). CPM is the framework upon which the privacy management process pegs where customers make decisions on whether to conceal or reveal their personal information (Petronio, 2017). The model makes use of boundary metaphor which suggests that people follow a set of system-based rules to always maintain, adjust and coordinate the boundaries of their privacy based on the benefits that are perceived and costs of the disclosed information. There are three rules with which communication privacy model management elements are identified: boundary coordination, boundary rule formation, and boundary turbulence. Boundary rule formation suggests that a person's privacy boundary entails data and pieces of information that are known only to the individual. This kind of boundary is established on the premise that individuals hold the notion that their personal information is owned by them; therefore, they hold the exclusive right to control and maintain what is shared, with whom it is shared, and when and how it should be shared. This private boundary is built on the fact that when information is maintained by the owner, such boundary is thick; when it is disclosed and shared with a third party, such boundary becomes permeable and thin. The second element of CPM, which is boundary coordination, happens when people share their private or personal information. At this point, the information moves to the collective boundary level which ensures that both parties work to ensure that the information shared is kept private. This level of information sharing marks the beginning of control of collective data and coordination of mutual boundaries by both parties involved. The third management element of CPM, which is boundary turbulence, happens when people seek recourse such as industry standards, government regulations, organizational policies, etc. to ensure assurances from third parties (Jarvenpaa, 2017) (Heng Xu, 2011). Furthermore, the research model analyzed Perceived Privacy, Risk-Control Assessment, and Privacy Policies and Its Perceived Effectiveness.

1.9.1.2 Perceived Privacy

Perceived Privacy refers to a state of privacy, which implies the self-assessed condition of an individual, in which external agents have limited access to information about the individual (Dinev, 2013). Several studies consider privacy as a substitute irrespective of whether it is explicitly or implicitly stated. (Westin, 1968), for instance, talks about the state of privacy; whereas Westin (1968) and Altman (1975; 1976) refer to 'State of limited access and state of control'. When the issue of privacy is treated as a state, it implies that a person in the given

context at a moment in time – is in a situation where decisions that concern his privacy issue are made. Trust and privacy concerns are two known substitutes of perceived privacy (Dinev 2013; (Flavián, 2006) and they both refer to the mental state of individuals with regards to the safety of their information.

1.9.1.3 Risk-Control Assessment

Dinev (2013), found that the most effective framework that is used to analyze present-day privacy concerns of consumers is the *Risk-Control Assessment model* (Bies, et al., 2003). The framework postulates a positive relationship between optimistic bias and control perceptions. The model emphasized that the higher a consumer perceives control over the outcome of his data, he shows the more positive attitude is. Therefore, individuals are more willing to take a risk when they assess that the associated risk has a less serious impact (Laura Brandimarte, 2013). Likewise, when individuals do not perceive control, there will be a reduction of trust towards the business organization (Johnson et al., 2010) and their perceived privacy (Dinev. 2006; Dinev 2013).

1.9.1.4 Privacy Policies and Its Perceived Effectiveness

(Westin, 1968; Wu et al. 2012) noted that Privacy laws and policies set up by organizations or government regulatory services can go long way in helping to enhance customer trust and alleviate concerns (Westin, 1968; Wu et al., 2012). Such policies inform the decisions of consumers and guide them on how their private information is being used. This helps to directly or indirectly inform consumers about the security and systems of an organization's websites that they make use of (Heng Xu, 2011) (Westin, 1968) further disclosed that many companies online put out their privacy policies on visible places on the websites to build the trust of consumers and reduce the concerns that their private information will be exposed (Westin, 1968). With the present General Data Protection Regulation that has been set in motion across Europe and chipping on other countries of the world, consumers are being sensitized to the importance of their data.

1.9.2 Customers attitude towards data protection

Considering data protection issues, customers are beginning to develop cold feet towards disclosing their data regardless of the benefits.

Martone, (2018) identified four important attitudes of consumers to share data and how to connect and engage with the different categories: the unaware, the accepting, the cautious, and the incognito.

1.9.2.1 Unaware Consumers

Consumers who fall into the "the unawares' category are typically enthused to explore and access a service or product that they desire and go on to click "accept" to cookies on websites without really understanding the implication or consequence of their data exchange. Most of the consumers in this category may even have applications in their devices that are mining data like a tracker of their GPS location without being aware. To help consumers in this category, organizations should set up a data management policy that makes consumers easily understand their Terms and Conditions in a clear and precise way; interpret the data being mined from users and for what reason (Martone, 2018). The study also advises that consumers should be nudged to always review organizations' settings to be informed of changes that may have been made to their Terms and Conditions to allow consumers make informed decisions on the value exchange.

1.9.2.2 Accepting Consumers

For consumers within the 'accepting' category, they consider data sharing a trade-off that is inevitable and so accept to exchange data but are not excited about the level of data they share with organizations. These types of consumers are aware of the changing world and so go with the tide to get what they need from the service provider. To help these consumers, organizations should enable customers to get a better grasp of the need for the exchange of their data and point out why the value exchange is important.

1.9.2.3 Cautious Consumers

These categories of consumers are naturally cautious and so approach data sharing with utmost caution. They scrutinize and ask critical questions to organizations before venturing on sharing their information. They dig deep before clicking 'I accept' on any website they visit or fill forms. To reach these consumers, Nicholas Moore – a staff of one of the biggest credit reference agencies – Experian, suggests that organizations should make it quite easy for them to locate the information they need (Moore, 2018). The organization should reinforce credibility by showing its data protection policy. Transparency, reassurance, and trust are critical if this consumer must accept to exchange his or her data.

1.9.2.4 Incognito Consumers

These kinds of consumers have developed mechanisms to defend themselves from unwanted surveillance by creating an environment that lets them navigate through sites without disclosing their identity or sharing data. They often browse the internet using Google's "Incognito" setting. To be of help to these consumers, the study suggested that organizations gradually request additional information from them but most importantly, build confidence on trust to enable disclosure. The issue of data privacy concerns consumers within all age brackets. Studies have shown that consumers are not very particular about their benign data, such as basics like age, sex, but are particularly concerned about who gains access to their activities online and their buying behaviors. A great number of consumers believe that neither government nor companies should have access to their activities online via social media tools or cookies (Martone, 2018).

Wirtz, et al., (2007) in their study about consumers' privacy concerns, found out from responses that consumers expect both governmental regulations and organizational policies to protect their online privacy. Firms can therefore improve consumer's perception of their data

safety by teaming up within and outside their business organizations to ensure a responsibility balance with consumers. They called on firms to have a proactive posture in their collection and usage of user data and implement a comprehensive privacy policy to protect consumers. They also urge firms to work together with regulators and other industry bodies to create a mutually beneficial plan to communicate a comprehensive data privacy policy and make it visible on websites for users to see. Their findings also suggested that policy formulators need to make efforts in managing consumer perception of policy regulation as there is a likelihood that end users will have less concern if they perceive an effort of regulators in setting up a framework that protects their online privacy (Reidenberg, 2003). As perceived regulations by government bodies influence the responses of consumers, a holistic system that addresses information protection might be more preferred to individual statutes that separately focus on areas of likely misuse of information (e.g., HIPAA 1996 and The Right to Financial Privacy Act of 1978;). An all-encompassing regulatory approach, which touches on all types and sectors of data collection, has a higher likelihood of enhancing user perception of the regulation (Wirtz, et al., 2007).

To glean a more recent insight on the perspective and attitudes of consumers towards privacy security issues, Gigya, an identity management company, in 2017, published a report on the state of consumers with regards to the issue of privacy and trust. They took a poll of 4,002 respondents – 50% from the U.S. and the other 50% respondents from the U.K. The result of the study is quite revealing. The study revealed that 69% of consumers showed concern about the security of the device and a lack of confidence in brands to keep their personal information such as email address, contact address, and name private. Sixty-three percent (63%) of the respondents expressed acknowledgment of being responsible for protecting their personal information while 62% said they have changed their passwords for concern of compromise. Also, 32% said they have added a second level of password authentication on their devices to ensure security, 18% admitted having out rightly closed an account, 61% of respondents who have an account with Facebook said that they have taken advantage of Facebook's privacy settings to update their status and preferences (GIGYA, 2017). Despite all the measures taken to protect themselves, 70% make use of seven or fewer passwords details across several online platform accounts which points to an ineffective password habit. Despite government involvement in data privacy regulation and security, 53% of the respondents believe the recent governmental involvement will have little effect. More recent studies on consumer views on data privacy reveal much more and defer slightly from older studies carried out in the field.

The awareness created by the recently enforced General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) in the European Union has rippled down on not only Europeans, but other nations of the world about privacy issues and how consumers engage with organizations regarding their data (GIGYA, 2017).

1.10 Data protection theories and framework – organizations centered

1.10.1 Tavani and Moor Privacy Theory

The authors proposed a hybrid privacy theory that attempts to go beyond early privacy theories. They developed a tripartite model that suggests that privacy theory should include three core aspects: the concept of privacy; justification of privacy; and management of privacy. The concept and justification are concerned with policies within an organization that justifies the need for data collection while the management of privacy relates to the measures put in place by the organization to keep information secure (Tavani & Moor, 2001).

Both contemporary theories focus on privacy being viewed in a different context. Given the diversity associated with the business in our world today, one privacy rule may not work in another context. Hence why the EU GDPR places the burden of securing data collected on the shoulders of the data controllers.

Many Data controllers within the European Union have faced several challenges in attempting to meet GDPR requirements. Regardless of the lengthy research, discussion, revisions, and negotiations conducted, there is still more work to be done to enable compliance (Eugenia, et al., 2018).

1.10.2 Brodin framework for implementing GDPR in SMEs

Brodin (2019) attempted to establish the fact that SMEs indeed struggle with implementing GDPR. In his research, he developed a framework using design science to help SMEs adapt to GDPR. He tested his framework in three different organizations to ascertain its potency. The selected Organizations were chosen to represent the private and public sectors, small and medium-sized, with and without the mandate to employ a Data Protection Officer (DPO).

Figure 4 : Framework to help SMEs adapt to GDPR (Brodin, 2019)

1.10.2.1 Elements of Brodin’s framework explained

1.10.2.1.1 A. Analysis

In this stage, the framework helps organizations to assess their current state regarding controlling and securing information. It starts with *information analysis*, classifying information following GDPR principles using a Post-it. All personal data processed by the organization is considered, how is it processed, the medium for processing it (e.g., writing on paper or using a computer), and external processors are also considered. The analysis is taken further using an information flow analysis only if the data processing method is complex, involving many systems or departments. This stage has five steps: *Information analysis, Information flow analysis, classification, security of data, and Legality of processing data.*

1.10.2.1.2 B. Design

The design stage focuses on the organization’s policies, routines as well as templates involved in processing data. There are two aspects of routines: internal routines, which are derived by organizations in dealing with personal data daily. While the second routines are GDPR derived, which focuses on the responsibilities of the data controller following GDPR principles. See (3.2.4). Furthermore, the design stage comprises of five levels that help organizations create and implement effective routines for data processing; *updating routines, generating routines*

in managing data subject requests, updating processes for data breaches, updating policy for personal data, create policies that ensure oneness in data handling throughout the organization.

1.10.2.1.3 C. Implementation

The implementation is the most important stage as it will determine the success or failure of the routines, templates, and policies. This process involves creating working conditions that will ensure the organization's compatibility with GDPR, appointing staff to roles for GDPR compliance, and getting rid of unnecessary personal data not compatible with GDPR law. Some important elements are key to making implementation successful. These are ***education, communication, training, and adjustments.***

- i. Education:* All Staff members of the organization should be informed about GDPR. Everyone needs to have the right competency to handle data, thereby complying with GDPR terms.
- ii. Communication:* Information needs to be disseminated through the appropriate channels, so that staff members are thinking and working in the right manner.
- iii. Training:* Staff members need to be aware of the GDPR working procedures, routines, security, and policies
- iv. Adjustments:* Feed backs are an important way of ensuring that the organization is fully compliant with GDPR and that necessary changes are made to help the organization comply effectively.

1.10.2.2 Summary of Brodin's Findings

The first organization involved in Brodin's case study was a Swedish company that processes personal data through its IT department and external bodies. The second organization was a mid-sized private firm which has about 5-100 employees, hence they were not obligated to have a Data Protection Officer. However, their CIO, CEO, and other experts within the organization handled the personal data of their clients. The third company was into event planning, with a workforce of 10-20 staff, nonetheless, the company processes a lot of personal data due to the nature of their business.

The three case studies helped to analyze Brodin's framework in the real workplace. One of the challenges common to all three companies was that they felt overwhelmed by GDPR and did not quite know where to begin. The framework helped to point them in the right direction, but

the limitation was the inability to resolve all the company’s challenges. Nonetheless, while in the *information analysis stage*, the organizations were able to identify unnecessary personal data they had stored.

At the end of the workshop, all three companies had similar challenges, but the framework was able to answer their questions. Below are some of the questions and how the framework resolved them.

Table 3: The application of Brodin’s framework on real companies (Brodin, 2019)

Company’s Similar Challenges	Solutions from Brodin’s Framework
What should we do to be compliant?	Brodin’s complete framework
What are our current personal data processing methods?	Analysis stage – Information analyzing
Do we require any data processing agreements?	Analysis stage – Information analyzing
What are the legal requirements for processing personal data	Analysis stage – Legal requirements
Do we require consent for all data processing and data subject access requests right?	Analysis stage – Legal requirements
What level of security is good enough for data protection?	Analysis Stage – Security of information
Are we currently involved in managing data?	Design stage – Routines and policies
How do we handle breaches?	Design stage – Routines and policies
How do we process data information requests?	Design stage – Routines and policies
How do we know more sensitive data?	Analysis stage – Classification of information

(Brodin, 2019)

The table above shows the application of Brodin’s framework to real companies.

1.10.2.3 Limitations Brodin's Framework

Brodin's framework was built on three independent and one dependent variable (s). The independent variables are the analysis, design, and implementation stage, while the companies are the dependent variable. Using the framework, he engaged the three firms in a workshop, where he used each stage to identify the GDPR compliance challenges and offered solutions. The implementation of the policies formed needed time and as a result, the researcher was not able to tell if the framework worked in totality. Furthermore, the researcher was unable to determine if the firms carried out training, communicated across departments effectively, or made the necessary adjustments where the framework failed. In addition, the framework was only tested in three organizations which were small and medium-sized firms, hence results may be different if tested in other organizations.

1.10.3 GDPR Readiness assessment tool

In similar research on GDPR effectiveness carried out by Chatzipoulidis et al. (2019), they were of the school of thought that for GDPR to be effective organizations need to ascertain their readiness. The authors proposed a 'Readiness Assessment Tool' to check both internally and externally, the state of data protection at a business and compliance level. Four factors were considered using in shaping GDPR compliance within an organization these are – business context, authority support, processing control, and improvement.

Figure 5: Factors that influence GDPR compliance (Aristeidis, et al., 2019)

The figure above illustrates the factors that influence GDPR compliance.

These four factors as shown in figure 1 above, directly determine the extent to which a business can be GDPR compliant. The Business context factor suggests that management is responsible for its business strategy, data protection reasoning, process justification, and provision of resources that support GDPR compliance (Aristeidis, et al., 2019).

Authority support within the organization is dependent on which responsible person will oversee ensuring that the business is compliant with GDPR. The GDPR recommends that such responsibility should be handled by a Data Protection Officer (DPO).

Processing control deals with how an organization handles the data life cycle – from receipt to removal. Lastly, improvement is in line with industry standards, customer satisfaction, and awareness (Aristeidis, et al., 2019).

The authors further proposed that an auditor should be able to assess whether an organization can conform with GDPR requirements using a scoring scale. They propose the following elements to aid GDPR readiness scoring – Compliant (C) – where evidence matches GDPR expectation the score is 1, Major Nonconformity (Major NC) – where there is no evidence to support GDPR expectation the score will be 0, Minor Nonconformity (Minor NC) – partial fulfillment of GDPR expectation the score will be 0.5, Correction – where partial nonconformity can be resolved e.g. an outdated policy that needs updating, and Not applicable (NA) – where evidence is not a requirement to ascertain GDPR conformity (Aristeidis, et al., 2019). The authors claim that their GDPR Readiness Assessment Tool will help ascertain in real-time, the GDPR compliance level of a business.

Having the right support in place to effectively implement GDPR requirements is very vital in mitigating the issues that surround breach of data security or theft. Over the past years, many data privacy skeptics and enthusiasts see GDPR as a response to the reaction of victims of data breaches. For example, a portion of the research community advocates for a more relaxed privacy regulation while another school of thought believes that the existence of big data presents the need for stricter privacy regulation. Hence, the challenges surrounding data protection are unavoidable. It is in account of these challenges that GDPR modified the regulation by introducing the right of that data subject to ask to be forgotten or request for the erasure of their personal information. Whitley (2009) suggests that in practice it is difficult to erase a person's data on request because where the data in question is being held due to constitutional purpose, it may prove nearly impossible. He added that differentiating between revoking the 'right to use' personal data for specific purposes and revoking the 'right to hold' person data may go a long way in resolving the issues (Whitley, 2009).

In our digital world, access to personal data represents both money and power – which may affect our society negatively. Thus, to create a balanced world, consumers and businesses need to understand the need to protect data and the need to have access to personal data for economic reasons. Otherwise, we might end up in a world where innovation becomes hampered (Eugenia, et al., 2018).

1.10.3.1 The usefulness of Aristeidis et al readiness tool to this study

One of the focuses of this study is to assess the compatibility of the Nigerian data protection regulation within varying organization sizes within the travel industry. Hence, the readiness assessment tool suggested ways that this could be done using "GDPR Scoring". Though the

research may not directly make use of scoring to assess compatibility nonetheless, the readiness assessment tool helps to point the researcher in the right direction.

1.10.3.2 Limitation of Aristeidis et al readiness tool to this study

Though the authors did not highlight any limitation with their research, the only limitation the research points out is that the readiness assessment tool has not been tested in real case studies which if done will result in varying GDPR scores among varying business contexts. Nonetheless, the authors did point out that there is room for future improvement in their research.

1.11 Data protection implementation challenges in Western and Nigerian Context

Tankard (2016) points out that one major challenge of GDPR for organizations is the expansion of data subjects' rights towards the retraction of their shared data (right to be forgotten). Thus, mandating that companies know where each data is stored. However, putting such provisions in place to support data recall will be costly for many organizations. GDPR does not just demand compliance but, demands compliance with the use of the appropriate technology – the cost being, therefore, a burden for organizations to bear which not many organizations are willing to take on (Tankard, 2016). Another school of thought suggests that GDPR raises the bar for data protection law in the EU and beyond which caused a wide awakening to the formulation of data protection in emerging economies which had led to a genuine opportunity for global partnerships. Nonetheless, they do argue that GDPR is not completely faultless (Buttarelli, 2016).

Likewise, Buttarelli (2016), suggests two rather – strategic consequences for GDPR on organizations; Firstly, he points out that organizations should not view GDPR as a burden rather, as a means for strategic global partnerships to emerge. Nonetheless, the safeguarding of protection should be view more as a corporate social responsibility than a burden (Buttarelli, 2016).

Similarly, in recent research conducted by Tikkenen, Rohunen, and Markkula (2017), they identified 12 practical implications of GDPR for organizations.

Table 4: 12 practical implications of GDPR for organizations (Brodin, 2019)

<i>What organization needs to do</i>	<i>What it means</i>
To specify the need for data and its usage	A data controller /processor is prohibited from collecting more data than required.
Provide the right conditions for processing data internationally.	When transferring data abroad, the organization should ensure that it meets the EU GDPR standards of safeguarding.
Have adequate data design by default.	Every data controller/processor must institute organizational and technical methods and procedures for safeguarding data.
Display compliance with GDPR Principles and Requirements.	Controllers of data show that they have a plan for ensuing compliance with GDPR
Procedure for handling data breaches.	When a breach occurs, it must be reported to the supervisory authority and the data subject must be informed as well.
Accepting sanctions for non-compliance.	Every organization must be aware and prepared to answer sanctions relating to non-compliance or breach, which is up to 4% of the annual global turnover.

Appointment of a Data Protection Officer (DPO)	Not all organizations may require a DPO; however, it is the responsibility of the organization to find out if they require a DPO.
Keeping the Data subject informed	The organization must ensure data subjects are well informed about information related to their data, such as where data is stored, what it is used for, who it is transferred to, etc.
Obtain consent for using personal data	Under GDPR, if it is legally required to obtain consent before processing data, the data processor must follow due process.
Guarantee data subject right to be forgotten	If a data subject demands his or her information to be erased, the controller must ensure they fulfill their request.
Ensure data subject right to portability	An organization needs to ensure that when data transfer is required, it is portable for swift and easy transfer.
Maintaining compliance and documentation	Organizations must ensure that they are up to date with GDPR compliance requirements.

(Tikkenen, Rohunen, and Markkula ,2017)

The information above shows 12 practical implications of GDPR for organizations.

Many organizations agree that GDPR is a useful regulation, however, the process for GDPR implementation is seen as ambiguous because it is not simple to read (Bihari, 2018). One of the ways for companies to cope with the severity of GDPR compliance – For example marketing companies – is to give their customers controlling power over their data (Kolah, et al., 2015).

In Nigeria, the case is slightly different. Abdulrauf (2015) argues that the major challenge of data protection implementation in Nigeria is the lack of legislation backing the data protection regulation. If people are aware that a breach of data protection would not be valid in court, they are more likely to show less concern towards protecting people’s data. For instance, since the introduction of the Nigerian Economic and Financial Crimes Commission (EFCC) many individuals including businesses have taken serious caution towards monetary deals because,

if entangled in a case of fraud, even if innocent, they will go to prison. If the same approach is used for data protection, the number of breaches would greatly decline. In addition, due to poor technological advancement, Nigeria lacks the facilities required to implement data protection policies (Abdulrauf, 2015).

Despite the popularity of GDPR in western countries, organizations still struggle to understand what is required of them in terms of implementing GDPR policy within their organization (Brodin, 2019). One of the practical implications of GDPR as highlighted by (Tikkinen-Piri , et al., 2018) is that organizations can decide whether or not they need a DPO. If this is the case then, it begs the question: who should be compliant? Should only big organizations comply? What factors should SMEs consider when deciding whether they need to employ a Data Protection Officer? Do these exempted companies process data? If they do, who then within the organization should handle data in absence of a DPO? All these and more are existing in regulation and theoretical gaps. According to Irish SMEs Association, only 30% of businesses have discovered the steps involved in becoming GDPR compliant. Research shows that there are **99 articles** written about GDPR and most problems stem from, especially SMEs, who are struggling with GDPR implementation. Also, when matched with reality it seems impossible for all organizations to come to a point of total compliance with its terms without reasonable adjustments (Brodin, 2019).

One of the major drawbacks of GDPR is that it does not provide any technical support to an organization that may need that assistance in facilitating compliance. Another profound difficulty was highlighted in the aspect of adjusting current procedures to suit the right to be forgotten requirement which involves assessing backup that could lead to mistakes. Another challenge worthy of being mentioned is in the aspect of GDPR's request for simplicity in the data collection process (Eugenia, et al., 2018). This poses as a threat for business that requires many more information from users to enable them to have a personalized service experience and may hamper the delivery of quality service if this personal information is not provided. Furthermore, scholars have argued that there is a conflict of interest between those who have a perfectly good reason for wanting to collect data and those who have a perfectly good reason for wanting privacy.

Data protection is a serious topic that should not be taken lightly. Beyond the consequences of getting fined for defaulting, there are other negatives impacts a business can suffer if found to be non-compliant. Such negative outcomes span from the damage of reputation, disruption of

businesses activities, and legal liability nonetheless it can be managed by advanced risk management and monitoring mechanisms (Ouwerkerk, 2018). Similarly, research carried out on the risk-based approach – recommended by GDPR – concluded that since companies vary by size, the privacy protection measures a company will put in place should be proportionate to the amount of data it processes (Coraggio, & Zappaterra, 2018). The world we knew previously was moving slowly towards digitization, but the current global pandemic has caused a rapid shift towards faster adoption of digitization. Though this is a welcome development, however, it has given rise to a new host of serious cyber security issues (Krystlik, 2017). Being able to protect customers' data is a good thing but, many businesses will make a significant amount of restructuring to conform to GDPR mandatory requirements (Krystlik, 2017).

2.12 Proposed Conceptual Framework

After considering relevant theories, models, frameworks, and concepts of data protection, it is evident that data protection is broad and evolving in a different context. The literature was presented comprehensively to reflect a broad view of different perceptions on data protection. The review has shown that data protection means different things to different people however, the key theme central of most journal articles reviewed were based on ‘privacy awareness’. Questions such as: Are customers aware of their rights? Are data controllers aware of what is expected of them? were asked. All these questions were raised in previous research. Data privacy is gaining momentum through the efforts of researchers such as Berlinger and Crossler (2011), Booth and Ho, (2017), and many more. Past researches focused on areas such as changes in GDPR in comparison to DIR95 (Ataei, et al., 2018); Challenges of insurance organizations in personal data access (Grundstrom , et al., 2019); (Brodin, 2019) focused on compliance challenges for small and medium-sized enterprises, while (Tikkinen-Piri , et al., 2018) looks at the challenges of GDPR for all organizations; (Eugenia , et al., 2018) focused on challenges associated with revoking consent and (Abdulrauf, 2015) focused on how data can be protected in Nigeria. These studies are great contributions to the body of knowledge in which the majority have been focused on developed economies, but little research has been done in the aspect of implementation challenges within organizations in Nigeria. Brodin (2019), revealed that many SMEs’ struggles with understanding what is required of them. In addition, Aristeidis et al. (2019) suggested from their study that not many organizations are ready for GDPR and proposed a GDPR readiness assessment tool that can be used to check if organizations are compliant and identify the aspects that they need to work on. These signs of

progress in past research focused on the western context but are lacking in developing economies such as Nigeria. The introduction of the Nigeria Data Protection Regulation (NDPR), stimulated comments, thesis, and speculations from top solicitors, in Nigeria. All these authorities questioned the reliability of the regulation, but no evidence of research has been made on data protection implementation issues within organizations in Nigeria. Nonetheless, as mentioned earlier, some researchers like (Chandio & Rajani, 2004), (Cole, 2000) have looked at the use of the internet and its impact on society. (Tikkinen-Piri , et al., 2018) looked at the practical implications of GDPR for companies in the western context, (Robert, 2017), and (Ataei, et al., 2018) criticized the GDPR and practical use in the real-world situation, (Brodin, 2019) focused on the challenges of SMEs in complying with GDPR and (Aristeidis , et al., 2019) proposed a readiness tool for ascertaining the GDPR compliance level within businesses. All these studies based on a western context are important during this study. However, considering the focus of the study to recommend a solution for the effective implementation of NDPR, Brodin's framework has been considered in developing a conceptual framework for this study. This is because Brodin's framework has been found suitable. After all, it incorporates elements of GDPR requirements for organizations.

2.12.1 Extension of Brodin's framework to the context of Nigeria

Brodin's framework had three stages which are: analysis, design, and implementation. All three stages portray the application of GDPR which depended on the organization's profile. At the analysis stage, the companies needed to understand what GDPR required from them, leading to the designing of routines, policies, and templates for the implementation of data protection regulation.

Though GDPR and NDPR are similar, they differ in practice. The organizations' processes explored by Brodin in his study differs from how travel agencies work in Nigeria due to factors such as work culture, work ethics, organizational awareness of GDPR. Brodin used companies who already knew about GDPR but had not fully integrated GDPR in their system. Contrary to his approach, this thesis uses companies that may not be aware of NDPR. Thus, applying Brodin's framework in Nigeria's context will yield a different result. Therefore, the framework will be extended to suit the Nigerian context by taking into consideration the already laid out NDPR requirements for data controllers.

The Nigerian data protection regulation (NDPR) sets out a compliance framework that all data controllers must follow however, it contains different requirements that the data controllers

may struggle to integrate. To ascertain travel agencies' compliance level, the framework is classified into three levels which is an extension of Brodin's framework to suit the Nigerian context. See the figure below:

Data protection compliance levels based on NDPR framework

Figure 6: Conceptual Framework for assessing the adoption of NDPR for effective data protection practices in Nigeria (Authored)

2.12.2 Explanation for framework terms

(I) Compliance level I

a. Policy

The Nigerian data protection regulation is structured in such a way that the responsibility of ensuring the success of data protection solely rests on the data controllers through a term called ‘*privacy by design*’. Despite the level of autonomy, the data controllers have, they are required by NDPR to design their policies under the regulation. Some of the key considerations are data retention periods, capacity building, awareness creation, and data impact assessment (DPIA) (NITDA, 2020).

b. Visibility

The concept of data protection will not be complete without the data controller and the data subjects. Every data protection regulation such as the EU GDPR and the NDPR has been developed in a way that it is focused on the data subject as the central team. Therefore, the NDPR requires that all data protection policies generated by data controllers should be put together under its regulation. Visibility is centered on transparency of data policy, conciseness, and accessibility. According to NDPR visibility can be achieved through either one or more of the following mediums: website, digital media as well as other possible means (NITDA, 2020).

c. Accountability

The NDPR requires that all data controllers have a responsible person who will oversee ensuring that their organization is compliant with the regulation. Though the newly introduced Data Protection Compliance Organisations can fulfill this requirement on behalf of the organizations, the setback is that it is not a free service. The DPCOs have the liberty to decide what fee to charge but with no cap on fees, exploitation is prone to occur. Nonetheless, while some organizations may not yet have access to DPCOs, they can assign a responsible person internally within their organization to meet up the requirement of the NDPR regulation (NITDA, 2020).

d. Sensitization

One of the important requirements as set out by the NDPR for both data controllers and DPCOs is the creation of awareness for data subjects. Having a data protection policy would not fully satisfy the NDPR requirement if public sensitization is not done. The organizations are to ensure that their clients are duly informed about how their data is used and what rights they

have as a customer. Some of these rights are withdrawal of consent, request for erasure, right to be notified of breaches affecting them, etc. (NITDA, 2020).

(ii) Compliance level II

a. Advanced data security systems

To achieve this level of compliance, data controllers would need to use a high level of security through encryption services. Data controllers in Nigeria may fall in the category of small to medium-sized enterprises with a size of 5-500 employees. The companies involved in this study have a size of between 6-500+ being among the popular travel agencies in Nigeria. Based on this data, not many of these agencies will be able to afford the cost involved with advanced data security systems. The cost of integrating advanced security systems may be high for travel agencies because of the multiple parties involved in data sharing such as, third-party business partners who are in their processing pipeline. Therefore, the use of advanced security systems would not be for just the data subject but data processors as well. Some of the key considerations for setting up advanced security systems as stipulated by NDPR are that the systems should provide easy access for data subjects to request for correction, updates, transfer of information (porting) to another data controller. Such systems might be costly to implement (NITDA, 2020).

(iii) Compliance level III

a. External support for auditing and filing compliance reports

Level I – II are responsibilities that organizations can fulfill independently without the use of Data protection compliance organizations (DPCOs). However, level three must be done through the DPCOs. The NDPR states that data controllers may file their compliance report by themselves, but it must be supported by a verification statement from a licensed DPCO. There are now 103 licensed DPCOs in Nigeria (NITDA, 2021). This requirement may pose as a stumbling block for organizations that may not be able to afford the fees charged by DPCOs. Though NITDA states that the DPCOs are subject to the NDPR regulation, but there is no limit on how much fees the DPCOs can charge data controllers for filing their compliance reports. As a result, data controllers can decide not to file their compliance reports and whether they file or not, the impact is not yet known because the regulation is still being improved (NITDA, 2020).

2.12.3 Summary

The literature review has been comprehensively presented in this chapter. Drawing from works of literature on past theories and models reflects different perceptions on data protection and provide insights into how data protection breach causes distrust in the relationship between the data subject and data controllers. However, the researcher found that the most suitable framework in explaining the phenomenon was Brodin's framework for helping Small to medium-sized enterprises implement GDPR because it incorporates elements of GDPR requirements for organizations. The three stages of Brodin's framework portray the application of GDPR which is relevant to the organization's used in his study. However, Brodin's framework needed to be extended to suit the Nigerian context. The agencies' behavior towards data protection issues is a product of their awareness level which is a key concept that information privacy users explained. Thus, using these two key concepts, the researcher expects to contribute to the more effective practice of the Nigerian data protection laws within travel agencies in Nigeria.

Chapter Three: Research Methodology

1.12 Introduction

The general purpose of this research is to investigate Nigerian's approach to data protection and examine the effectiveness of the new Nigeria Data Protection Regulation within the travel industry and recommend a framework for rolling out the new regulation effectively in Nigeria.

In Chapter one, there were specific research questions formulated to facilitate this research. These are:

1. To what extent does legislative backing, direct towards governing data protection exist in Nigeria for online and independent travel agencies?
2. What are the challenges associated with effective legal framework implementation of the Nigeria Data Protection regulation for online and independent travel agencies?
3. Has the government sensitized travel agencies enough to ensure awareness and compliance with NDPR in Nigeria?

The purpose of this chapter is to discuss the research methodology used in this thesis and to provide a justification for choosing a multiple case study approach based on the research objectives and research questions above. Using the ‘onion’ research process, the research design, research philosophy, and data collection methods will be discussed (Saunders, 2003)

1.13 Research Onion

To justify the research methods used in this study, the research process ‘onion’ gives a clear illustration of the steps to follow in developing a thesis (Saunders, 2003). The layers of the onion process are represented in the following aspects: Research philosophy, approach, methodology, time horizons, and data collection methods. The specific approach adopted for this study is highlighted in red in Figure 3.1 below

Figure 7: Research onion (Saunders, 2003)

The figure above gives a clear illustration of the steps to follow in developing a thesis.

1.13.1 Research Philosophy

There are three research philosophies as identified by Saunders et al (2003) namely: interpretivism, positivism, and realism.

1.13.1.1 Interpretivism

- Interpretivism is a systematic and detailed way of observing people’s actions to create an understanding and interpretation of how people’s social world is created and maintained. It particularly relies on qualitative methods of conducting research (Neuman, 2000). Furthermore, contrary to other philosophical approaches such as positivism, interpretivism holds a subjective view of the world. They argue that the

complexity of an environment is difficult to general rather, it should be understood (Saunders, 2003).

1.13.1.2 Positivism

- Positivism is characterized by the belief that the world is external, and the observer is objective. It suggests that humans' actions and institutions can be studied objectively as the natural world. It is seen as having accurate and value-free knowledge about what is possible (Fisher, 2003). It believes that the researcher is independent of the research and does not affect or is affected by the subject of the research (Remenyi, 1998). It particularly relies on quantitative methods to carry out research.

1.13.1.3 Realism

- Realism assumes that reality exists independent of human thoughts and beliefs (Saunders, 2003). Furthermore, it claims that scientific inquiry is based on the collection of facts than opinion, belief, divine revelation, or tradition. It is like positivism but with a focus on social context (Saunders, 2003)

The main research philosophy used for this study is interpretivism which is aimed at investigating and exploring the effectiveness of the New Nigerian Data Protection regulation (NDPR) in Nigeria, using selected travel agencies. During this research complex phenomena are observed, changes and implications are interpreted.

1.13.2 Research Approach

In conducting business research, there are two main approaches: the deductive and inductive approach (Saunders, 2003).

1.13.2.1 Deductive approach

Deductive starts with a theory about an area of interest working from a general to a more specific approach. It comprises of the use of hypotheses that can be tested leading to confirmation or not of the original assumptions or theories (Trochim, 2006).

Figure 8: Deductive approach (Saunders, 2003)

The figure above shows the deductive approach from theory to confirmation.

1.13.2.2 Inductive approach

Inductive works are the opposite of the deductive approach. It moves from specific observations to broader theories and generalizations by measuring and detecting patterns and regularities, formulating tentative hypotheses that can be explored, then generalized (Trochim, 2006).

Figure 9: Inductive approach (Saunders, 2003)

The figure above shows the inductive approach (moves from specific observations to broader theories)

In addition, the inductive approach emphasizes a close understanding of the research context, meaning of human-led events, collection of qualitative data, less need to generalize, flexibility in allowing the researcher to make changes as the research progress, and an understanding that the researcher is a part of the research process (Saunders, 2003).

Based on the nature of this study, the inductive approach will be more appropriate because of the degree of uncertainty and exploratory nature of the inductive approach. The process of this study is, to begin with studying four individual travel agencies, and then explore general observation and patterns regarding travel agencies which will give more insight into the general travel industry.

1.13.3 Research methodology

There are several research methods such as surveys, experiments, case studies, grounded theory, action research, and ethnography. The case study method will be used in this research however, other research methods will be discussed and justification for choosing a case study will be provided.

- ❖ Experiments involve hypothesis and sample selection. It ensures a high standard is used in sample testing procedures which keeps the dependent variable in constant condition except for the independent variable (Morrison, et al., 2010).
- ❖ A survey refers to a method of using an instrument made up of closed structured or open-ended questions, to gather data needed for research from respondents who mostly specific parts of a population are (Garson, 2001). Surveys have three characteristics: first, it is used in gathering information from people by asking them structured or predefined questions. Secondly, it is useful in quantitative research that requires standardized information about the subject being studied. Thirdly, it is used to collect information from a fraction of a population which might lead to generalization however, a larger sample is usually required for extensive statistical analysis (Kraemer & Pinsonneault, 1993).
- ❖ Grounded theory is inductive, and it allows the researcher to develop theory from qualitative analysis of data (Martin, 1986).

- ❖ Action Research aims to solve a problem in a system by collaborating with the people in the system to bring about a desirable change. Hence, a researcher has to work with the respondent to accomplish such a desirable outcome that satisfies both parties involved (Gilmore, 1986).
- ❖ Ethnography or ethnographic research is a social and cultural discipline where the ethnographer is required to spend considerably more time in the fields with the intent of learning about people cultures, customs, mutual differences, or habits (Myers, 1999)

1.13.3.1 Case study methodology as the chosen method in this study

A case refers to an entity, individual or event, or unit of analysis (Yin, 1984). A case study, therefore, is an empirical investigation of a phenomenon in its real-life state (Baxter & Jack, 2008), using several sources of evidence. Case studies can also emphasize how and why things happen, which allows an insight into the difference between what was intended and what occurred (Anderson, 1993). The purpose of a case study is not to study an entire organization but to focus on a specific issue and provide insight and understanding. Hence, a case study method was chosen for the research. Phenomenology, as described by Patton (2002), focuses on two specific aspects: first, explaining the subjective viewpoint of how people perceive the world (the descriptive part); and second, examining what this experience means to them (the analytical part). The aim is for the studied group of people to discover the essence of common experiences. The phenomenon investigated can be an emotion or a relationship, but it can also be an entity, culture, or a community (Patton, 2002); (Sayre, 2001).

1.13.3.1.1 Limitations of case study method

Some researchers have argued that the case study method does not address the issue of generalizability; lacks reliability and rigor (Johnson, 1994), and may contain a researcher's bias in verification (Flyvbjerg, 2006). However, one of the strengths is that since many pieces of evidence are used, it helps the researcher to gain a holistic perspective of the phenomenon (Gummesson, 1991)(Flyvbjerg, 2006).

Using Multiple Case Studies

Yin (1993) suggests that using multiple case studies will allow the researcher to predict the replication of results and boost the confidence of the researcher in the results. Hence, a multiple case study was used in this research. Documentary evidence aided the cross-validation of information gathered from the interviews. Evidence on how an organization collects data and

the availability and accessibility of the organization's data policies aid the validity and reliability of findings. The commencement of this research involved an extensive review of literature which led to the formulation of a theoretical framework and then formed a structure for the study. A set of semi-structured questions were formed to guide the interview process.

1.13.4 Time horizons

According to Saunders et al. (2003), time horizons are necessary for research design irrespective of the choice of the methodology used in the research. There are two main types of time horizons: longitudinal and cross-sectional. Longitudinal is suitable for the repetition of a study over a long period while cross-sectional is used to study one or more variables within a limited time frame. This study is limited to a time frame of 3 years and the data is collected from four different travel agencies.

1.13.5 Data Collection method

There are different methods of collecting data namely, questionnaires, surveys, checklists, interviews, observation, and focus groups. The main technique used in this study to collect primary data is qualitative interviews. In addition, a semi-structured interview with open-ended questions was chosen because it allows for more flexibility for the respondents to give insight regarding the research questions and provides a way to gather richer empirical data (Eisenhardt, 1989). It also allows cross-case analysis comparability (Bryman, 2004). This research used both secondary and primary sources (interviews) of data in the study.

Primary source - Interview

An interview is a communicative process in which a person or investigator or interviewer extracts information from the participant. The knowledge gathered will be highly affected by the respondent, who behaves and interprets his environment based on his past experiences (Nigel, et al., 2000). Based on these criteria, it is apparent that the object of qualitative interviewing is to provide an interpretation of factors that cannot be observed, such as interviewees' emotions, perceptions, beliefs, behaviors, or attitudes. Because qualitative interviews are focused on the premise that someone else's perspective is important and knowable, understanding their perspective becomes a researcher's goal (Patton, 2002); (Sayre, 2006).

Forms of interviews

Qualitative researchers suggested various classification schemes for the forms of interviews. For example, Sayre (2001) differentiates the unstructured field interview from the more formal structured interview that operates with a predetermined collection of open-ended questions. Patton (2002) offers a more comprehensive description of open interviews, differentiating between three fundamental approaches: the interview guide approach; the informational conversational interview; and the standardized open-ended interview. The benefits of these interview types are shown in the table below.

Table 5: Benefits of open-ended Interviews (Patton, 2002)

The informational conversational interview	The interview guide	The standardized open-ended interview
<u>Unstructured</u>	<u>Semi-structured</u>	<u>Semi-structured</u>
<p>Questions stream from the immediate context, with no predetermination of wording or questions.</p> <p>Uses conversational flow as a major tool of fieldwork.</p> <p>Data gathered will be different for each person interviewed.</p>	<p>The interview guide offers predetermined topics or subject areas, in an outline.</p> <p>The interviewer is free to explore, probe, and ask questions within the framework but focuses on a predetermined subject.</p> <p>Data collected systematically</p>	<p>Predetermines the exact wording of questions and their sequence.</p> <p>Respondent gets to answer the same questions in a similar, order, including standard probes.</p> <p>Comparability of data is enhanced.</p>

The table above illustrates the benefits of open-ended interviews

These three forms include open-ended questions, which ensure that the phrases or categories of responses used by respondents are not predetermined, as is the case for closed, fixed-response interviews in quantitative research. What varies is to what degree the wordings and order of the questions to be asked during the interview are predetermined. The model uses in this the interview guide style, with predetermined question wording, but the order used during the interview is the conversational flow. This method has the benefit of making data collection more systematic and ensuring that all subjects and issues of concern are covered (Patton, 2002).

(i) *Explorative expert interview*

Interviews performed by the researcher may be listed as explorative expert Interviews. Explorative interviews are unstructured or semi-structured discussions that concentrate mainly on collecting extensive and informative information on specific topics or issues of interest. Its key objective is to obtain relevant information and opinions about research (Patton, 2002). This attribute is the key criterion used to differentiate between explorative and in-depth interviews, aimed at exposing hidden motivations and behaviors which are hard to figure out. So, the psychological dimension is predominant in in-depth interviews, while explorative interviews are more based on the information dimension (Patton, 2002).

(ii) *Interview Guide*

An interview guide outlines essential issues and subjects relevant to the study questions posed that need to be discussed during the interview. Questions in qualitative research need to be available, impartial, specific, and transparent. There are various types of questions, from experience to background or demographic questions (Patton, 2002). The interview guide developed for this study consists mainly of questions of experience and conduct as well as questions about participant's perspectives on the research topic. Part of the expert interview also focuses on so-called critical incidents in data breaches.

The questions asked during the interview for this were group into three key areas.

- ❖ General questions about the travel agency business (7 Questions)
- ❖ General discussion into the travel agency's awareness of the Nigeria Data Protection Regulation (16 Question)
- ❖ Core questions on agency's experience with data breaches (7 Questions)

The full list of questions can be found in appendix 1

As discussed earlier, this research is focused on the issues of data protection effectiveness in Nigeria. Using a case study will enable the researcher to investigate how data protection has been perceived, received, and the occurrences of data breaches as well as the impact of this on data controllers and data subjects. Gaining this amount of valuable insight through a case into the subject will lead to recommending a framework for effectively rolling out data protection in Nigeria.

1.13.6 Research design

1.13.6.1 The rationale for the choice of agencies in the sample

(I) Sample size

While quantitative research operates with random probability sampling, qualitative research does not have any clear guidelines for determining sample sizes. The sample size rather depends on the researcher's considerations concerning the intent of the research, the relevance and reliability of the cases chosen, and the time and resources available (Sayre, 2001) (Patton, 2002). Patton (2020) describes the different aspects of quantitative and qualitative research concerning sample size as an interchange between scope and depth.

(ii) Scope versus Depth

Quantitative instruments restrict answers by standardizing questions to predetermined categories. As a result, quantitative researchers can quantify other respondents' reactions and can improve data and scope in this way. On the contrary, qualitative studies typically require only a few chosen cases to be examined, but to be examined in great depth and with attention to detail and context, thereby increasing the depth of the research. In addition, purposeful sampling helps to limit the trade-off (Patton, 2002).

(iii) Purposeful Sampling

Purposeful sampling is a term that describes the "strategic and purposeful collection of knowledge-rich cases" to ensure that the sample selected offers the requisite depth but at the same time fulfills the objective of an ideally high degree of breadth (Patton, 2002). Still, the exact number of the cases selected depends on the intent of the study and other factors listed above (i.e., resources). The cases selected will be judged according to the intent of the study and their importance in providing answers to the research questions about the phenomenon under investigation (Patton, 2002). The sampling procedure used in this research on data protection will be explained in detail.

(iv) Sampling Procedure

Resources: Five variables can be recognized as the significant limitations in sampling: (a) inadequate time frame, (b) financial limitations, (c) geographic boundaries, (d) a limited number of interviewers, and (e) limited access to private company information. The time frame

for conducting in-depth interviews was approximately one year, with no budget available. The research was geographically limited to the states of Lagos, Delta, and Abuja in Nigeria. Only one interviewer was required to conduct all expert interviews, challenged by the restraint of limited access to confidential company data.

(v) *Sampling Strategy*

An approach to homogeneous sampling was initially adopted. The principle of homogeneous sampling is the emphasis on a specific set of similar incidents, minimizing variance, and simplifying analysis. The intention was to conduct interviews on data protection with a few selected travel agencies that operated in Nigeria. The idea of choosing the travel agencies rather than any other company was because they collect a significant amount of data from several travelers, amounting to over thousands. The travel industry is involved in moving people from one destination to another and this cannot be achieved without information sharing. This approach was also determined by the assumption that problems related to data protection may have greater complexity with the growing size of the travel industry. Hence, considering the aim of the study and limitations mentioned above, it was decided to focus on travel agencies in Lagos (business hub) and Abuja, being the capital state of Nigeria. These major states in the country have international airports from which people travel to and from daily to any part of the world.

To give a broader overview of the state of NDPR effectiveness within the travel industry, the number of agencies registered with the Nigerian Civil Aviation Authority, the National Association of Nigerian Travel Agencies, and the Corporate Affairs Commission were considered.

The Nigerian Civil Aviation Authority (NCAA) is a regulatory body set up to function autonomously since 2006. The responsibility of the body is to regulate and govern the activities of airlines, airports, airspace and meteorological services, and economic regulations of the industry. According to NCAA, 145 registered travel Agencies in Nigeria are also registered with the National Association of Nigerian Travel Agencies NANTA (NCAA, 2020). NANTA is a body that offers a full fee-based membership status to all International Air Transport Association (IATA) and Non-IATA accredited travel agencies and allows customers to report fraud online. One of the benefits of being IATA accredited is that the travel agencies will have access to sell international and domestic tickets on behalf of the airlines, but non-accredited members can only sell as third party or sub-agents to customers. The figure provided by the

Nigerian Civil Aviation Authority is lower than what was published by the National Association of Nigerian Travel Agencies (NANTA). NANTA claims that there are 5000+ travel agencies and over 25,000 independent travel consultants (NANTA, 2020).

The travel industry in Nigeria is diverse because it is made up of agencies that specialize in offering varying services which do not require them to be registered with either NANTA or NCAA. Such agencies are the education agents who like the travel agencies have significant access to sensitive data. The major difference between travel agencies and education agencies is that the former represents airlines while the latter represent universities. Nonetheless, both deal with sensitive information which is required to make a trip outside the country. Based on this similarity, the sample for the case study had to include agencies from both backgrounds.

The first major requirement to operate as an authorized travel agency or education agency in Nigeria is to be registered with the Corporate Affairs Commission. Therefore, to ensure that the travel agencies were well represented in this study, two travel agencies with registration from either NANTA OR NCAA were chosen to represent the travel leisure agencies. While education agencies with CAC registration were chosen to represent education agencies. Furthermore, to enable the researcher to access the NDPR compliance level, the sample size was further reduced to include only agencies with an online presence. To get a two-way insight into the phenomenon, four travel agencies were included in the study. These were particularly key players in the industry.

1.13.6.2 Sample selection criteria

- Travel agencies who are registered with Corporate Affairs Commission
- Travel agencies who are registered with the National Association of Travel agents
- Travel agencies who are registered with the Nigerian Civil Aviation Authority
- Travel agencies with an online presence

Table 6: Participating agencies in study

Agency Name	CAC Registered	NANTA Registered	NCAA Registered
Education Agency A	Yes	No	No
Education Agency B	Yes	No	No
Travel Agency C	Yes	Yes	No
Travel Agency D	Yes	Yes	Yes

After concluding the telephone interviews with the selected agencies, it became necessary to examine the trends under review — which, in particular, were the organization’s aspect of handling data and the difficulties related to cooperation with the new government regulation for data protection. Patton (2002) refers to the practice of pursuing new leads during fieldwork and using the unexpected as emergent sampling.

1.13.6.3 The rationale of choice of respondents

Based on the conceptual framework, it is evident that the most suitable candidates for interview are those who meet one of the following criteria below:

- i. Collect data from customers and transfer it to the processing department
- ii. Receive data from a department and use the data to process customers’ request

The respondents from the travel agencies had job titles such as operations team lead, business manager, CEO, and sales officer, etc. These individuals are at the focal point of building and maintaining a relationship with clients and conducting or overseeing the day-to-day activities of the business and deal with sensitive data. Furthermore, interviewees from these departments

can give insight into key issues from different angles which will help build a better understanding of the research objectives and validate the research data. In addition, further observation was carried out on 155 travel agencies and information gathered was used to support the case study of the five travel agencies. Interview and data collection was done in two years.

Table 7: Background of Interviewees

Agency	Position in Company	Age Group	Years in Company	Level of Access to Sensitive Information
A	Business Manager	35 - 50	3	High Level
B	Founder & CEO	40 - 45	15	High Level
C	Customer Service (Sales)	27 - 35	4	Moderate
D	Head of operations	29 - 35	8	High Level

The table above contains details about the interviewees representing the agencies who participated in the case study.

❖ *Strengths and weaknesses of the sampling procedure*

The beginning of the study provided insight into how travel agencies use data and why it is important for them. But the in-depth interviews were expected to disclose key information on data protection awareness and the challenges with compliance based on the following: Firstly, travel agencies tend to be big and are likely to come across challenges with implementation and compliance. Secondly, the design of the study allowed the researchers to obtain the viewpoints of both the customers (travelers) and the travel agencies. Lastly, it could be examined how the regulatory body and the travel agencies work together to make data protection laws effective in managing or minimizing breaches, thefts, and frauds. Nonetheless, because of the nature of the sampling method, this study does not offer a wide variety of viewpoints as far as the side of the data controllers is concerned, because it focuses on one industry. Furthermore, because of restricted resources, the study is limited to investigate travel agencies in Lagos, Abuja, and Delta State, Nigeria. Thus, it does not claim validity in other industries or emerging markets. Nonetheless, some significant insights could be gained that are common also to other industries or markets.

1.13.6.4 Impact of sample on findings

The result from the interview reflected the selected agencies' views on data protection. The travel agencies' perspective is limited as only key players in the travel industry with large operations and reputations were interviewed, excluding local, small, and independent travel agencies. There are not many limitations from the travel agencies' perspective as sizes of agencies vary since the selected travel agencies have an important range of clients, from small local businesses to big and multinational companies. However, only a few of these agencies were willing to participate in the interview. As a result, to add more diversity and quality to the finding, further desk research was conducted to review how other travel agencies collect data, the kind of data collected, and if they were compliant with the new data protection regulation. A total of 50 qualifying agencies were observed based on the sample selection criteria used for the four travel agencies. Therefore, telephone interviews and desk-based case studies were used in this research to obtain secondary and primary data.

1.13.7 Data collection process

The level of cooperation received from the travel agencies who participated in the case studies affected the scope of the research. Due to the sensitive nature of the research topic, it was challenging to secure interviews with people working in travel agencies. In addition, during the data collection period, the current global pandemic hit the world making it impossible to travel to get a face-to-face interview. Furthermore, many agencies were not available to participate in the research because the travel industry was particularly hit the hardest because passengers canceled their flights, vacations were rescheduled, students who were traveling to study abroad had to defer, staff were retrenched, which put many companies in survival mode.

The researcher realized that it would be very difficult to secure a face-to-face interview with the senior consultants in these travel agencies because of the sensitivity of the issues raised by the research questions. The thesis aims to propose a framework for effectively rolling out Nigerian Data Protection Regulation (NDPR) in Nigeria and to achieve this the study will have to ascertain the level of awareness and compliance within these travel agencies. Therefore, some of the questions contained in the interview guide were deemed too sensitive to answer. The reluctance of the travel agencies is understandable because being aware and not compliant with the data protection law would mean getting a fine from the Nigerian Data Protection Regulatory Body.

The researcher worked in one of the major educational agencies and in view of the above challenges, the researcher had to start contacting interviewees through a personal contact within the travel industry where she worked, and all interviewees who participated agreed to do so on the basis that their personal information and name of their agencies will be kept private. Some of the interviewees were her friends who worked in other travel agencies offering the same services as the agency where she works. In total 4 travel agencies were interviewed.

The interviews were conducted online due to Covid19 travel restrictions between 2020 and 2021. During the semi-structured interviews, an interview guide was used as a framework to ensure that the topic of interest was covered and consistent across all the travel agencies cases. The interview guide contained questions concerning the travel agency's data protection policy, awareness of the law, the impact of the regulation on business activities, and experience of breaches. In all cases, at request, the interviewees were provided with the guide and a general overview of what the researchers hope to add to the body of knowledge as well as recommendation for effective data protection laws. After reviewing the guide, they were comfortable participating in the interview. The in-depth interview gave the researcher insight into deep and broad information from the agencies.

At the beginning of the interview, the researcher notified the interviewees that it will be recorded to allow for verification from the doctoral college and the supervisor to increase the validity of the research. Each interview started with the researcher introducing herself, the researcher, and informing the interviewee that their responses will be recorded but kept confidential – their details and that of their agency will be anonymously included in the thesis. In qualitative interviewing, an interviewer must establish a rapport with the interviewee (Patton, 2002). The interviews lasted for 15mins. Written abstracts and transcripts of the interviews were made. After the initial interview, the researcher made subsequent contact with other travel agencies and customers via telephone which was focused on getting additional insight into the broad problems relating to the effectiveness of the Nigerian Data Protection Regulation.

1.13.7.1 Multiple sources of data

One of the major strengths of case study data collection method is that it allows using different sources of evidence which exceeds that of other research methods such as surveys, histories or experiment (Yin, 2009). Therefore, in this study primary and secondary sources of data were used. Secondary data is essential in recompensing for limitations of primary data collected from

interviews, can be used as a method of validating information gathered from interviews, serves as a guide during interviews. Some of the advantages of using case studies are: it is cost-effective more than primary data; a wider breadth of data is available; the permanence of data; it provides contextual and comparative data (Saunders, 2003). Sources of secondary data include tertiary literature such as catalogs and indexes; articles; documentaries and informal discussions (Saunders, 2003).

For this study, the secondary data used includes official websites of interviewed travel agencies; official websites of interviewed education agencies; internal material of interviewed agencies, and journal articles and reports. The use of multiple data collection methods in this study will enhance its validity and reliability.

1.13.8 Data analysis process

The data analysis process of this research is divided into three stages: individual case analysis and cross-case analysis. Data analysis has been defined by Marshall and Rossman (1995) as a process of bringing order, structure, and meaning to the bulk of data collected. Due to the nature of the data, the data analysis process adopted involves data reduction, data display, and verification/conclusion as recommended by Miles and Huberman (1994).

Data reduction: This process involves tie selection, focusing, simplification, and abstraction and transformation of data. The reduction and transformation of qualitative data can be done through paraphrasing or summarisation among other methods.

Data display: This process involves the organization and compression of information that allows for different conclusions or actions (Miles & Huberman, 1994). The most common way for displaying qualitative data is text form, however, it has been argued that other better methods of displaying qualitative data include charts, networks, graphs, etc.

Conclusion/Verification: The process of drawing of conclusion starts from the collection of data, identification of patterns, regularities, explanations, proposition among other things. Until data collection is completed or over, a conclusion may not be made. The analysts verify the conclusions reached as the analysis process is going on. The verification can be done briefly in the researcher's mind or through elaborate and clear explanations of arguments and a review of the literature.

Miles, Huberman, and Saldana (2014) state that the data collected should not only be useful to the investigator but for everyone. The data was organized by coding the main transcribed interview to identify the most common themes. The analysis of the data started after the interview records have been transcribed combined with all the notes created for all the cases. This enables the research to create a robust description of the available data. To prevent errors and ensure consistency, the researcher reviewed the interview transcript and the interview audio recordings and notes. This was done repeatedly by the researcher to identify the main themes of the data to enable her to understand the meaning or story that the data reflects.

Individual case analysis leading to cross-case analysis of the travel agencies were employed in this study. The data analysis was focused on the three (3) main research questions for the individual travel agencies and cross-agency analysis. At the final stage, the results were presented using texts, charts, and graphs.

1.13.8.1 Thematic coding

As stated earlier, thematic coding was used for this study. Transcripts from the interviews and notes were used to generate the codes based on themes. Thematic coding has been defined by Braun and Clarke (2006) as “a method for identifying, analyzing, and reporting patterns (themes) within data.” Emergent themes in individual cases and cross-cases were recognized or identify from different levels of coding using Nvivo software. Thematic analysis was employed because it allows for flexibility as it offers details and richness on the complex data (Miles, Huberman & Jonny, 2014).

1.13.8.2 Individual case analysis

The understanding of how travel agencies ensure compliance to information privacy and make recommendations depends on the patterns in individual cases. In this study, the researcher did individual case analyses to reveal the themes that emerged from the data. Individual case analysis is important because it helps to reveal any special interest themes that may emerge from the data.

1.13.8.3 Cross-case analysis

After individual case analysis was done, cross-case analysis was done to help in the understanding of the patterns across the cases. Cross-case patterns identified when a cross-case analysis is employed are most useful in gaining great insights and better understanding in studies.

1.13.8.4 Ethical considerations

It is important to clarify that this research complied with ethical standards to resolve all ethical concerns or issues. Ethics describes how research is conducted in a morally and accepted manner (Bloomberg et al., 2005). Ethical concerns address how research questions are formulated and research topics clarified, on research design, data collection, data analysis, and how findings are presented in a morally and responsible way. Thus, this study followed the ethical guidelines of the University of West Scotland to ensure the integrity of the research and robust data collection, while minimizing researcher bias. The following ethical considerations were followed in this study:

- **Informed consent of participant:** According to Nardin (2014), informed consent is the process by which a subject voluntarily confirms his or her willingness to participate in a particular study after been informed of all of the aspects of the study that are relevant to the subject's decision to participate." Consent forms were presented to the participants by the researcher before they decided to take part in the study.
- **Explanation of the benefits of the study to the participants:** An information sheet was presented to the researcher to the sampled participant to explain the purpose of the study. Contained in the information sheet are the aims and objectives and other basic information about the researcher such as the university of the researcher which is the University of the West of Scotland. This helped the researcher to gain the trust and confidence of the participants. Also, it helped the researcher to begin meaningful discussions with the study participants, thereby increasing the quality of collected data.
- **Explanation of the rights and protection of the participants in the study:** The researcher explained the participants' rights and protection in the information sheet as well as verbally explanation. They were informed of the right to withdraw from the study at any time of the interview. The explanation was done for them to understand their rights and the study process to make them comfortable.
- **Confidentiality and anonymity and of the participant's information:** The researcher ensured that the anonymity and privacy of the participants at every stage of the study. Also, the particulars of the participants as well as the identity of the businesses were kept anonymous to maintain privacy and confidentiality.

1.13.9 Strength and weaknesses of research method

❖ Strengths

The research design choice provided the researcher much insight into the research topic. The case study method and unstructured interview allowed the participant to freely express their opinion about the research topic. The chosen methodology allowed trust to be set as a foundation for the relationship between the participant and the researcher. Another key aspect that strengthened the study is the researcher's working experience in the travel industry. The research collected data from 04 varying cases which strengthen the validity, precision, trustworthiness, and stability of the research findings (Miles, et al., 2014).

❖ Weaknesses

One major weakness of the research is that the portion of data collected cannot fully represent data protection issues in Nigeria. In addition, the data was plenty and unorganized hence the researcher had to take out time to make sense of the data collected. Nonetheless, access to a large volume of data brought more quality to the research work.

1.13.10 Challenges in data collection due to corona virus restrictions

The corona virus outbreak limited the number of cases that were included in the study. This is basically because the travel industry was hit the most during the global pandemic. The UK office for national statistics reported that travel and tourism businesses had a sharp decline to 26% between February and May 2020. According to the report, overseas travel and tourism also declined by 96% in the second quarter of 2020. One of the agencies who participated in the interview revealed that they had laid off 50% of their staff at the time of the outbreak. The whole travel industry was under such immense pressure that participating in a research interview was not a priority. The travel agencies were scrambling to save what was left of their business. In addition, given the timeline for the entire research, the researcher could not take up an extension on the program as travel agencies' recovery from the losses created by the pandemic was taking longer than the researcher anticipated. As a result of these unforeseen challenges, the researcher had to make do with the 04 cases that were already interviewed. Nonetheless, the agencies represented in the study are top agencies in Nigerian with the highest market shares in the travel industry. With this, in view, the research data collected was still of great quality and was sufficient to answer the research questions.

1.13.11 Research validity, reliability, and reflexivity concerns

The concerns of the validity and reliability of the research data were addressed through the adoption of a case study method. A mix of secondary and primary data was used in the findings. The primary data was the interviews conducted with the four travel agencies while the secondary data was the desk research which gave more support to the primary data. The combination of both strengthened the research validity and reliability.

The researcher works in a travel agency and as such the concerns of positionality and politics needed to be addressed. To address this, the researcher ensured that the participants understood what the purpose of the research was and the benefits it would bring to the travel industry's data protection practices. In addition, the participants were made aware of their rights to refuse participation, withdraw, and request for the removal of any information they had provided. The researcher's position and influence did not in any way influence the participation of the interviewees rather, the participants understood the benefits of the research hence, they participated.

Furthermore, after the data was collected and analyzed, the research sent the transcription to the participants to get a confirmation if the transcription reflected what they had said. After confirmation was received, the researcher proceeded to include the data in the research (Barry et al., 1999).

1.13.12 Summary

This chapter has covered the philosophy of the study which is interpretivism with appropriate justification for the choice. In addition, an inductive approach was adopted to explain the phenomenon. A multiple case study method was selected because it was more suitable for the research. The chosen data collection method was purposeful sampling and unstructured interviews. The data was analyzed individually before proceeding to do a cross-case analysis. The strength and weaknesses of the research were also mentioned.

Chapter Four: Findings

1.14 Introduction

This thesis is adopting the case study method as mentioned in chapter 3.0, which includes individual case study analysis and cross-case analysis. Firstly, this chapter starts with an overview of each selected agency, followed by a summary of the participant's response to interview questions, then themes generated from the responses, and finally, a cross-case analysis of the responses will be presented.

1.15 Individual travel agencies background and insights

1.15.1 Case 1: Agency (A): Education travel agency

1.15.1.1 Background and insight

Agency A was established in 2018 with a workforce of 6 - 10 employees. The company offers travel services to international students who intend to study in countries like UK, Europe, Dubai, the USA, Canada, Russia, and Australia. The agency represents universities to international students by selling study plans, courses, and pathway programs. In addition to these services, they offer ticketing services, accommodation services, airport transfers, for its clients through third-party travel agencies.

The agency has its headquarters in Nigeria from where it runs operations online. The company has a website and from the findings, the agency has a data protection policy that is visible to customers through a popup notification when they visit the website. The company also has a strong social media presence on Instagram, Facebook, and Twitter.

1.15.1.2 Information flow analysis

How does the agency collect data

Customer data is primarily collected through Instagram direct message, WhatsApp, email, website forms, and phone calls.

To process a request a customer will have to provide their full names, contact number, and email address, and inquiry type. If a student wants to process a study plan, he or she is first transferred to the admissions team who accesses his documents before he is transferred to other

relevant departments. Information flow starts from the customer services and ends at third-party partners.

Figure 10: Summary of agency (A) information flow (Authored)

The GDPR data categories are useful in understanding the kind of data travel agencies collect. According to GDPR sensitive data is a special category that reveals sensitive information about a data subject. The following information is considered ‘special category data’: biometric data for identification, data concerning health, sexual orientation, religious or philosophical beliefs, political opinions, racial or ethnic origin, and trade union membership (Information Commissioner Office, 2021). Any other information apart from criminal data is not classified as sensitive but rather personal data. The table below reveals the class of data agency (A) collects from clients.

Table 8: Classification of information collected by agency A at each level

Agency A departments	Type of Information Collected	GDPR Data Classification
Customer Service Team	Full name, email, phone number.	Personal data, non-sensitive data
Admission Team	Same as above plus travel documents, education qualification documents, financial information, family status, sexual orientation, ethnic origin, religious beliefs.	Sensitive data
Visa Team	Same as above plus bank statements, immigration history, criminal offense records	Sensitive data
Client Management Team (After Sales Service)	Full name, email, phone number, travel date, home address.	Personal data, non- sensitive data

The information above shows that Agency A collects both sensitive and personal data which makes them appropriate to be a part of the selected case study.

1.15.1.3 Agency (A): Interview Responses

To make the interview questions concise, the questions were section into to five places to tackle the important issues related to the research question which is ‘‘Are travel agencies aware and compliant with NDPR in Nigeria?’’

Interviewee Profile: Business Manager

General question about travel agency business activities

“Our services are geared towards ensuring that students are settled comfortably into the university where they chose to study. Based on this we handle the entire process from admission to arrivals and this service requires third parties to deliver. Our third-party partners are the universities, estate agencies, airlines, other travel agencies, and transport companies”.

General discussion into awareness of Nigeria’s Data Protection Regulation

“We are aware of Nigerian data protection regulation of 2022. However, before we knew about it, the concept of data protection was introduced to us by our partner universities in the UK. They would not agree to process applications within a proper GDPR form being completed and signed by the student, as a result, we had to choose to get the knowledge about data protection within Nigeria as well. We were not contacted by the NDPR to inform us about the regulation, we had to find out for ourselves what is available online”.

In Agency A, all staff are trained on the importance of data protection and are mandated to sign a Non-disclosure agreement (NDA) upon employment which is renewed at data protection training held every quarter. The Agency has not had any cases of breach.

“Sometimes mishaps occur, there was an incident when an email was sent to the wrong customer though, it was non-sensitive information. To avoid such from reoccurring, we have a centralized system for receiving documents from clients so that documents are not sent to just anybody”.

“We have a data protection policy online, but we know that most clients will not stop to read it and the term “ cookies or data protection” has been commonly used and interpreted the same way. So, we ensure that the form sends out to clients requesting their information, has a brief write-up about how we use their data, and we ask for their consent to proceed”.

Agency (A) analysis: Insights from case and findings from data

Figure 11: An analysis of agency (A) Interview (Authored)

1.15.1.4 Conclusion

Information gathered from the interview is in synchronization with what was found while surfing Agency A’s website. The agency is aware of the data protection law in Nigeria and has taken measures to ensure that they comply with the regulation and protect their customers. However, agency A is not reliant on the government to provide training for data protection awareness. The agency accepts the protection of its customers’ data has its responsibility.

1.15.2 Case 2: Agency (B): Education travel agency

1.15.2.1 Background and insight

Agency B guides international students on educational planning, application processes, and visa requirements. They enable a student to make the most of their academic and extracurricular opportunities throughout their secondary or university career which will help distinguish any strengths and talents in the admission consideration stages. From its headquarters in Lagos, the company works with various partner institutions worldwide. The agency offers similar services like Agency A but with the exclusion of ticketing, accommodation, airport pickup. The processes of Agency B limit the flow of information to third-party organizations. Agency B does not have a data protection policy on its website. Customers are not informed about how their data is used via the online portal. The agency has an online application portal through which clients can fill their requests including uploading sensitive documents. Some of the data requested will give insight into the customer's marital status, financial information, and gender, academic record, sponsors information and contact, ethnicity, and biometric information.

1.15.2.2 Information flow analysis

How does the agency collect data

Customer data is primarily collected through visits to the office where they fill a biodata form, Instagram direct message, WhatsApp, email, website application form, and phone calls.

To process a request a customer will have to provide their full names, contact number, and email address, and inquiry type. This information can be provided when the student visits their physical office. Agency B does not require their client to provide full detailed information online, but the client is directed from online to their office address. The diagram below shows that information flows starts from the customer services department and ends back at the agency.

Figure 12: Summary of agency (B) information flow (Authored)

To ascertain whether travel agency (B) collects sensitive personal information, the information collected is classed in the table below according to GDPR classification.

Table 9: Classification of information collected by Agency (B) at each level

Agency B departments	Type of Information Collection	GDPR Data Classification
Customer Service Team	Full name, email, phone number.	Personal data, non-sensitive data
Admission Team	Same as above plus travel documents, education qualification documents, financial information, family status, sexual orientation, ethnic origin, religious beliefs.	Sensitive data
Visa Team	Same as above plus bank statements, immigration history, criminal offense records	Sensitive data

The information above shows that Agency B collects both sensitive and personal data which makes them appropriate to be a part of the selected case study.

1.15.2.3 Agency (B) Interview Responses

To make the interview questions concise, the questions were section into five places to tackle the important issues related to the research question which is ‘‘Are travel agencies aware and compliant with NDPR in Nigeria?’’

Interviewee Profile: CEO & Founder

General question about travel agency business activities

Agency B helps students who are willing to study abroad to process their admission and vision. The agency owns a website and is present on social media. Agency B serves 150 students online yearly. They collect information from students that aid the process of their requests such as admission and visa processing to the UK, USA, Canada, Poland, Australia, Ireland, Germany, and others. About 80% of their customers patronage their services online which means they do not need to visit the physical office to access the full service.

‘‘To process applications abroad, we ask clients about their financial status to ascertain affordability, copies of their bank statements to verify if funding is available, family information, academic documents to ascertain if they meet the entry requirements of the university, and travel documents with immigration history’’.

General discussion into awareness of Nigeria’s Data Protection Regulation

B1 recognizes that there are data protection laws in Nigeria but say that there are not enough resources or facilities to implement such laws.

‘‘I am aware that as an agency we are expected to keep our client’s information safe, we are not supposed to disclose to third parties, the information given to us must be used for the purposed it was intended for and not for marketing or advertising purposes’’.

B1 acknowledges that there is no data protection policy on her agency’s website and agrees that is it a delay in compliance with the NITDA data protection regulation. However, B1 argues that there is no certainty if the agency is in breach of the data protection law because, to the best of their knowledge, there is no law mandating agencies such as theirs to put up a data protection notice on their website.

“Our clients ask us if their information is safe with us and we tell them it is. We have signed an agreement with the universities in UK, Canada, and others to protect the data of students. We know that the information ought to be kept private. We are not unaware of data protection rules especially since we interact with international organizations, we are aware of EU GDPR, but we do not know if any such law is available in Nigeria”.

To safeguard our client’s information, B1 says that employees are trained to handle data. There is no Data protection officer because all student counselors handle data. B1 has not had any issues of a breach within the agency. However, B1 is not aware of any penalty for breach of data protection in Nigeria.

“I think the major issue is ignorance, people are not aware of the data protection laws in Nigeria. People need to know the penalty for misuse of data”.

Agency (B) analysis: Insights from case and findings from data

Figure 13: An analysis of agency (B) Interview (Authored)

1.15.2.4 Conclusion

Information gathered from the interview is in synchronization with what was found while surfing Agency B’s website. The agency has general awareness about data protection laws but zero awareness of the Nigerian data protection regulation. Based on international influence, the agency implements data protection practices. However, agency B is not reliant on the government to provide training for data protection awareness. The agency is accountable for the protection of its client’s data.

1.15.3 Case 3: Agency (C): Travel and leisure

1.15.3.1 Background and insight

Agency C is one of the leading online travel agencies headquartered in Nigeria. It has a travel booking portal where customers such as individuals or corporate organizations can access the services it offers such as flight tickets, visa services, holiday packages, airport transfers, protocol services, and other travel-related services. The agency was established in 2008, with over 500 employees in its workforce. With over eight years in operation, the agency has grown to become one of Africa's leading travel agencies.

1.15.3.2 Information flow analysis

How the agency collects data

Customer data is primarily collected through the agency's online portal, email, website forms, and phone calls.

To process a request a customer will have to provide their full names, contact number, email address, passport number, travel destination, date of travel, accompanying passenger's information. In the case of a visa request, customers are asked for all personal details in addition to marital status, employment status, card details, and gender.

The company has a data protection policy on its website however, customers would have to deliberately search for it else they would not be notified. When filling the booking form for a ticket, a customer is required to submit personal information that gives insight into the customer's marital status, age, biometric information, and ethnicity. Such data according to EU GDPR and Nigerian Data Protection Regulation (NDPR) is classified as sensitive information. In contrast, when filling a visa application particularly to Dubai, a static notification is visible which says "*your personal data is protected*" however, for other services such as ticket booking and hotel accommodation, no data protection notice is provided. The diagram below shows that information flows from the agency's booking portal and ends back at the agency.

Figure 14: Summary of agency (C) information flow (Authored)

To understand the kind of information travel agency (C) collects, the information collected is classed in the table below according to GDPR classification.

Table 10: Classification of information collected by agency C at each level

Agency C departments	Type of Information Collection	GDPR Data Classification
Customer Service Team	Full name, email, phone number, inquiry	Personal data, non-sensitive data
Sales Department	Same as above plus travel document, financial information, family status, sexual orientation, ethnic origin.	Sensitive data
Visa Team	Same as above plus bank statements, immigration history, criminal offense records	Sensitive data

The information above shows that Agency C collects both sensitive and personal data which makes them appropriate to be a part of the selected case study.

1.15.3.3 Agency (C) Interview Responses

To make the interview questions concise, the questions were section into five places to tackle the important issues related to the research question which is ‘Are travel agencies aware and compliant with NDPR in Nigeria?’

Interviewee Profile: Customer Service Officer

General question about travel agency business activities

Interviewee C1

C1 confirms that the agency offers services such as flight ticketing, hotel accommodation, tour, visa assistance, and more. The interviewee confirms that these services can be assessed online without visiting their physical offices. C1 handles customers’ data with which she processes tickets and other services. *‘Over 70% of our customers patronage our services online’.*

Clients are contacted through phone calls, emails for follow-ups. Regarding data collected from customers. Sensitive documents such as passport data page, immigration history, and travel documents requested by the airline (third party).

General discussion into awareness of Nigeria’s Data Protection Regulation

C1 suggests that she is aware of what data protection is and defined it as follows:

’’ Data protection means safeguarding important information from corrupt files and compromise’’. I know that information such as full name, nationality, sexual orientation can identity a person accurately and such information if compromised will be against our company policy.

‘I know what data protection means but I have not heard about such law in Nigeria. But I stumbled on some data law some time ago’.

When asked if they have a date protection policy in place for customers to access, C1 says that at the branch level they do not have such information available. However, C1 says to secure customers’ data, they make sure they are careful and do not share information with unauthorized parties. In addition, C1 is unaware of any breaches that have occurred at the branch level. C1 says she is unaware of any penalty for data breaches in Nigeria.

Agency (C) analysis: Insights from case and findings from data

Figure 15: An analysis of agency (C) Interview (Authored)

1.15.3.4 Conclusion

Information gathered from the interview is in synchronization with what was found while surfing Agency B’s website. The agency has general awareness about data protection based on self-education but no awareness of the Nigerian data protection regulation. Agency C compliant level is low. The agency Based on self-education; the agency implements data protection practices. However, agency B is not reliant on the government to provide training for data protection awareness. The agency is accountable for the protection of its client’s data.

1.15.4 Case 4: Agency (D): Travel and Leisure

1.15.4.1 Background and insight

Agency D is a travel and lifestyle company that provides services that span from flights booking, hotel booking, vacation packages, and airport pickup services. From the company services, it is evidence that there is a flow of information from the agency to third-party organizations. The agency was founded in 2015 is headquartered in Nigeria with a workforce of 11 - 50 employees.

1.15.4.2 Information flow analysis

How the agency collects data

Customer data is primarily collected through the agency's online portal, email, website forms, and phone calls.

To process a request a customer will have to provide their full names, contact number, email address, passport number, travel destination, date of travel, accompanying passenger's information. The agency also provides visa assistance services. A request for a visa must be filled online with details about intended travel dates and destination country. Using the information provided by the customer through the online portal, the agency will make contact to finalize the sales offline.

The company does not data protection policy on its website however, the information the agency request from customers will give insight into the customer's marital status, age, biometric information, and ethnicity. Such data according to EU GDPR and Nigerian Data Protection Regulation (NDPR) is classified as sensitive. The diagram below shows that agency D's Information flow starts from the booking portal and ends back at the agency.

Figure 16: Summary of agency (D) information flow (Authored)

To ascertain whether travel agency (D) collects sensitive personal information, the information collected is classed in the table below according to GDPR classification

Table 11: Classification of information collected by Agency (D) at each level

Agency D departments	Type of Information Collection	GDPR Data Classification
Customer Service Team	Full name, email, phone number, inquiry	Personal data, non-sensitive data
Sales Department	Same as above plus travel document, financial information, family status, sexual orientation, ethnic origin.	Sensitive data
Visa Team	Same as above plus bank statements, immigration history, criminal records	Sensitive data

The information above shows that Agency B collects both sensitive and personal data which makes them appropriate to be a part of the selected case study.

1.15.4.3 Agency D Interview Responses

To make the interview questions concise, the questions were section into five places to tackle the important issues related to the research question which is ‘Are travel agencies aware and compliant with NDPR in Nigeria?’

Interviewee D1 Profile: Operations Team Lead

General questions about travel agency business activities

D1 confirms that the agency offers a variety of services such as ticketing, protocols, sale of travel insurance products, vacations, hotel accommodation. These services can be accessed online by customers without any visitation to their physical office. The agency issues a minimum of 1000 air tickets per month per branch office. They request information contained in the traveler’s passport data page, email address, phone number which is the major information required to process a standard ticket.

General discussion into awareness of Nigeria’s Data Protection Regulation

C1 defines data protection as a way of protecting people’s data. D1 suggests that a breach in data protection would be offensive and harmful. She believes that most Nigerians are not comfortable in revealing their personal information online due to security reasons. D1 says she is no aware of any data protection law neither is she aware of what is required of her agency by NITDA regarding data protection. When asked if her agency has any data protection policy in place, she says she isn’t aware. However, they do not share customers’ information with the third party. In addition, the company has a corporate communications unit in charge of managing customers. To the best of her knowledge, there has not been any breach of data protection within the organization.

Agency (D) analysis: Insights from case and findings from data

Figure 17: An analysis of agency (D) Interview (Authored)

1.15.4.4 Conclusion

Information gathered from the interview is in synchronization with what was found while surfing Agency D's website. The agency has general awareness about data protection based on self-education but no knowledge awareness of the Nigerian data protection regulation. Agency D compliant level is low. The agency Based on self-education; the agency implements data protection practices however staff is not trained for effective data protection practices. Agency D is not reliant on the government to provide training for data protection awareness. The agency is accountable for the protection of its client's data.

1.16 Additional findings from desk research 50 agencies

In addition to the findings from the individual case studies, to give a broader view of the awareness and compliance level of data protection in Nigeria, the researcher also looked at over 50 agencies that were registered with NCAA or NANTA. The result of this finding was used to feed into the case study of four selected travel agencies.

About the figures presented by the National Association of Travel Agents (NANTA), there are over 5000 travel agencies and 25,000 independent travel consultants. However, 5000 agents could not be included in the desk analysis because their information was not accessible on the NANTA database. Hence, the sample was reduced by the following criteria.

The first criteria used in selecting the travel agencies included in the sample size was based on NDPR's requirement which states that all data processors and controllers must have a data protection policy accessible on their website for customers. Therefore, the researcher only included travel agencies that had a website. The second criteria hinged on the legal registration of the travel agencies operating in Nigeria.

The selection criteria revealed that 145 agencies who were registered with Nigeria Civil Aviation Authority as provided on their database were also registered with the National Association of Nigerian Travel Agents (NANTA). However, 9 travel agencies out of the 155 selected sample, were found to be registered with Corporate Affairs Commission, but not registered with NANTA or NCAA. Nonetheless, they were added to the sample due to their popularity among customers.

Furthermore, it was necessary to ascertain whether these selected travel agencies were compliant with the Nigeria Data Protection Regulation (NDPR). Hence, we measured NDPR compliance using the following variables: availability of privacy policy on website and accessibility of privacy policy to customers. The variables revealed that only 50 out of 155 agencies were partly NDPR compliant; the reason being that, they met the first criteria of having a website. Therefore, the remaining 105 could not be assessed for NDPR compliance, It was difficult to measure compliance due absence of a website.

Figure 18: Overview of NDPR awareness and compliance among 150 travel agencies in Nigeria

1.17 Cross case analysis

In this section, the researcher presents the cross-case analysis informed by the individual case analysis. The theme developed from the individual case analysis will be discussed in this section. From the individual cases, the researcher identified two main themes which are data protection awareness level and data protection implementation challenges – with sub-themes such as high information, privacy awareness, compliance, data minimization, purpose limitation, lawful processing, accountability, confidentiality, lack of technical support, need for NDPR training, no data protection training for staffs, self-education, zero awareness of NDPR.

1.17.1 Part A: NDPR Compliance checker

Table 12: NDPR compliance checklist for travel agencies (National Information Technology Development Agency, 2020)

NDPR Compliance Checker	AGENCY A	AGENCY B	AGENCY C	AGENCY D
	Education recruitment	Student recruitment	Travel for leisure & work	Travel or leisure & work
Conducting information audit.	No	No	No	No
Data processing on an NDPR basis	No	No	No	No
Clear and accessible data privacy policy	Yes	No	No	Yes
Data protection systems under NDPR	No	No	No	No
Creating awareness through staff training	Yes	Yes	No	No
Conducting Data impact assessment	No	No	No	No
Data Notification	No	No	No	No
Appoint a responsible data protection personnel	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Systems for data are subject to easily request correction or erasure	No	No	No	No

The information above illustrates the NDPR compliance checklist for travel agencies

1.17.2 Cross case analysis of emerged themes using key NDPR terms

There are some key terms contained in the Nigerian data protection regulation which guide the formulation of privacy by design. Some of the terms are lawful processing, data minimization, accountability, confidentiality, and purpose limitation. The emerged themes from the case studies will be explained using these key NDPR terms.

Theme I: data protection awareness level

Evidence from the interview reveals that the travel agencies have varying levels of data protection awareness. Although the travel agencies claim that they have not heard about the Nigerian data protection regulation, they practice general data protection within their agencies. In the interview, when questions regarding general data protection were asked, travel agency C claims to be aware of general data protection.

Agency C'' Yes, I do. I feel data protection is just a way of protecting people's data''

However, she did express a lack of awareness on the introduction of the Nigerian data protection regulation in 2019. She mentioned that she stumbled upon the regulation online however, she was not certain it was the Nigerian data protection regulation

Similarly, Agency A and B stated that they had not heard about the regulation. Other responses the agencies provided gave insight into the attitude towards data breach. In particular, the agencies were asked if they know what personal data consists of and all four agencies stated that information containing names, date of birth, sexual orientation, nationality, home address, family information, and financial status. All four agencies gave different definitions that showed a reasonable understanding of data protection.

Agency A'' If my data is made public without my consent, I would feel horrible and uncomfortable''.

Agency B ''Yes, my data such as my name, date of birth, home address, office address, family information and qualifications''

Nevertheless, they did not know the Nigeria data protection regulation existed. In agency D's exact words:

“Data protection is a way of protecting people’s data against compromise”.

Low - High Information privacy awareness

Responses from the agencies showed varying levels of Information privacy awareness. Agency A and B (student recruitment agency) showed between high to moderate levels of IPA while, Agency C and D had lower levels of IPA. Based on the questions that were asked regarding data protection practices within their organizations, Agency A and B revealed that their customers are informed before their data is processed, information collected is used for the intended purpose only and in some cases, their clients are asked to sign a GDPR form to allow the agency to process their information to third party companies.

Agency A “There is a data protection notice that pop-up on our website that every visitor, whether new or old, sees when they visit our website. We input our data policy on our biodata forms which we use to request information from our customers.

Likewise: Agency B “If we need to share our student’s information with a third party, then the student will be aware. We will let them know that we want to share their information with a third party. If they give their consent, then we proceed”.

Contrary to Agency A and B, Agency C and D do not necessarily inform their clients about the processing of their information asides from Agency C who has a not so easily accessible data policy on their website. But agency D does not have a data protection policy on its website. In addition, Agency A and B stated that they had staff training on data protection but, Agency C and D showed limited staff training experience on data protection even at branch levels.

Upon asking agency C how their clients are informed about their current data practices the response was thus:

“No information is given to the client; business is done based on trust”.

In contrast, agency A says.

“There is a data protection notice that pops up on our website that every visitor whether new or old sees when they visit our website. We also include our data policy on every biodata form with which we request for customer information”.

Data minimization

During the interview, all the agencies confirmed that they collect only personal data that they require to process their client's information.

Agency A: "We ask for their passport information, phone number, and email address. Then we send them our biodata form and document checklist which they need to use in sending us required documents like academic certificates, transcript, English proficiency result, and other relevant documents".

Similarly, B also shares the same processes as A.

Agency B: "We ask our clients about their academic backgrounds such as qualifications, and a class of degree. We also ask about their financial status to ascertain if they can afford the study plan, bank statements, passport information, family status, and other relevant data".

Contrary to A and B, C and D does not require as many documents for processing the client's request.

Agency C: "We ask for their name as it appears on their passport data page, phone number, and email address. These are the basic information we need for reservation".

Agency D: "We request for their passport data page, we ask if they have a valid visa, and we ask for some travel documents that will be requested by the airline".

However, travel agency A did say that sometimes their clients send them documents that may not be needed. For example, when processing an admission, a client sends both a higher (bachelor's degree) and lower degree certificate (Higher national diploma) which in most cases the bachelor's degree may be suitable for obtaining admission into the university. Nonetheless, Agency A did confirm that they only process the data which is needed and delete the unnecessary ones. Through such practices these agencies minimization data collection according to NDPR policy.

Purpose Limitation

One of the key themes under data protection 'purpose limitation' states that Data collected about customers with their consent should be used for the purpose it was intended for. The travel industry is vast and as such travel agencies often collaborate with other organizations to provide specific services to their client. Agency A is an example of such collaboration.

“Yes, only with third-party organizations that are in the processing pipeline like the businesses we partner with that will enable our delivery services to our clients that cannot be directly provided by us. For example, airport pickup, accommodation services, and ticketing”.

The agency offers services such as accommodation search, pickups, and cargo delivery which are not entirely related. One would think that they would constantly use their customers' data for marketing purposes but, contrary to this assumption, Agency A said that all email marketing content sent to their clients only contains information about the services they offer. Hence, they do not send ads to their client which is outside what the clients know they offer.

Likewise, travel Agency B who does not rely much on ads or email marketing says that they limit the use of the customers' data for the purpose it was intended.

“No. Yeah, well, we're supposed to keep students' information private. We're not supposed to disclose to third parties, the information given to us is supposed to be just for the admission and we are not to use for marketing or advertising”

Contrary to agencies A and B, agencies C and D who are in the same industry may find it difficult to limit the purpose for which data is used. This is because for example if a client purchases a holiday ticket to Dubai, they are likely to purchase another holiday ticket to a similar destination or unrelated destination offering the same service. Such sales possibility may hinder purpose limitation because the client may not be aware that such services exist except an ad containing such services is sent to the client.

In agency D's exact words:

“If we are transferring to a third party it should be amongst us, the customer, and the airline, that is as far as it can go”.

Lawful processing

The concept of lawful processing means that All organizations process the personal data of their customers according to either NDPR or GDPR policies. Due to low NDPR awareness amongst the travel agencies, they do not process customers' data following NDPR. However, their customers' data are still processed safely.

In agency C's exact words:

“ Not at all, because of the nature of what we do and the kind of data that we have, once reservation is made, we send directly to the person that requested that reservation and that it is. Once the person has used the itinerary, that it is.

Similarly, Agency D says, ‘well, we are always careful. Our IT has software that we use. We ensure we don’t share any information outside. with customers data’.

Unlike C and D, Agency A takes further measures to ensure that data is processed safely.

“All our staff is trained to be data protection conscious, and a non-disclosure agreement that all staff must sign which is also renewed at our data protection training every quarter. In addition, we use Google suite which has encryption software that can help to protect a customer’s information. For instance, we can password emails that contain sensitive information and set it to expire within a period we choose, this way the receiver does not hold the information forever”.

However, B approaches it differently

“Well, not straightforward. We just ensure that employees are aware that client’s information must be protected. So, all counselors know, it is part of the training we give to them that this information must be kept safe. It is just for admission and therefore must not go beyond the office. It is part of their employment contract”.

Accountability

The Nigerian data protection regulation requires that all data processors or data controllers have a DPO or a responsible person in charge of handling personal data. Agency A processes 170 customers data on average every year; agency B does 150 yearly; agency C processes over 12,000 yearly, and agency D processes over 2,000 per year. Regardless of the volume of data these agencies process, the focal point is that they process sensitive data.

In these agencies, there are no data protection officers (DPO) however, they all have a responsible person or unit in charge of processing personal data. About the agency’s responses, agency A says:

“All our staffs are trained to be data protection conscious, and we have a non-disclosure agreement that all staffs must sign at the start of employment. We also run a data protection training each quarter”.

Likewise, agency B says:

‘‘We train our staff to keep students’ information safe. It is part of their employment contract that we ask them to sign’’. Some of our customers ask us if their personal information is safe and we tell them yes’’.

Agency C and D have no (DPO) but they have responsible persons in charge of protecting data. In agency C’s exact words:

‘‘We have a central unit called the corporate communications unit where we send all data to after receiving them. The unit oversees protecting customer's data’’.

However, agency D says:

‘‘Everyone in our organization oversees handling personal data’’.

These agencies show reasonable levels of accountability towards protecting their customers' data which is following NDPR requirement

Confidentiality

Not know NDPR has not negatively affected how these agencies handle data because they hold customers' data in strict confidence. In agency D’s exact words:

‘‘ Disclosing the personal data of our customers would be against the customer’s consent’’.

While Agency B says:

‘‘If we need to do that, then the student will be aware. We will let them know that we want to share their information with a third party. If they give their consent, then we proceed’’.

Agency A and B said that their employees sign a confidentiality agreement that is embedded in their employment contract. The confidentiality agreement prohibits employees from sharing customer and company information such as trade secrets, customers' financial information, frequency of travels, etc, to rival companies or family and friends.

Theme II: data protection implementation challenges

Lack of awareness of NDPR poses one of the major challenges of data protection within these agencies. If the agencies are not aware then, they cannot implement what they do not know. During the interview, the agencies were asked if they knew what was expected of them by NDPR and the following responses were recorded.

Agency A, C, and D say they do not know what NDPR requires of them while agency B said:

‘‘No, I do not know but, generally, we are meant to keep students’ information safe and not to disclose to tell parties. The information given to us is meant to be used for the intended purposes only’’.

Some sub-themes were generated from data protection challenges these are: self-education, inadequate technical support.

Inadequate technical support

The agencies reveal that they have different ways of storing data. Some of these are on google sheets, on their laptops, on websites backend, on paper shelves, and email. Considering the level of sensitive information these agencies process, their storage systems are not adequate for safeguarding sensitive data.

Agency A: ‘‘All our staff is trained to be data protection conscious, and a non-disclosure agreement that all staff must sign which is also renewed at our data protection training every quarter. In addition, we use Google suite which has encryption software that can help to protect a customer’s information. For instance, we can password emails that contain sensitive information and set it to expire within a period we choose, this way the receiver does not hold the information forever.’’

The travel agencies were asked what measures they have taken to ensure the security of their customers' data and the following responses were recorded.

Agency C ‘‘ our corporate communications unit gathers the data we get from our website and we ensure we do not share such information with third parties.’’

Agency D ‘‘Well, we are always careful. Our IT has software that we use. We ensure we don’t share any information outside. with customers data’’.

Agency A ‘‘All our staffs are trained to be data protection conscious, and a non-disclosure agreement is signed’’.

Agency B ‘‘We train our staffs to ensure students information are kept safe’’.

The responses showed that these travel agencies do not have the technical support required to safeguard personal data.

Self-education

Evidence from the agencies confirms that they are not aware of the Nigerian data protection regulation. However, they have reasonable general data protection awareness. During the interview, agencies A and B mentioned that they have interactions with international organizations in the UK that are GDPR compliant. These interactions with GDPR compliant organizations made them aware of the need for data protection and greatly affected how they process their customers' data.

In agency B exact words:

'Yeah, because we have agreements or contracts with universities, in the UK, Canada, and all other countries. And we signed an agreement that mandates that there is data protection for the students coming to us. So, we know, we know that their information ought to be kept private. We do not know what laws are available in Nigeria, but we know data protection laws are available in advanced countries''.

Likewise, Agency A says: 'We have become more careful about how we handle data. Now that we know what data protection is, we understand that the impact of a breach of data protection has a more negative effect on the customer than us as a company. This is because the customer can be exposed to the danger of being defrauded or even face hurt. So, we are now extremely careful''.

However, agencies C and D mentioned no impact in their data protection practices because of interaction with foreign bodies.

These agencies rely on self-education and international influence on practicing data protection.

Table 13: A framework for assessing the implementation of NDPR (level 1)

Agencies	Policy	Visibility	Accountability	Sensitization
A	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
B	No	No	Yes	No
C	No	No	Yes	No
D	Yes	Yes	Yes	No

Table 12 showing A framework for assessing the implementation of NDPR (level 1)

- a. Policy

Travel agency A has a data protection policy on their website. Similarly, agency D has a policy on their website, but it can only be assessed if the customers deliberately search for it. Agency B and C do not have a data protection policy on their website.

b. Visibility

After going through all four websites of each travel agency, findings show that only agency A's data protection policy meets the visibility criteria because of the use of a data protection pop-up notification that all customers see when they visit the website.

c. Accountability

All four agencies showed a reasonable level of accountability towards protecting their customers' data.

Agency A "All staff that collects data are responsible for securing it. However, our HR personnel ensures that all staff complies with the company's working policy regarding data protection".

Likewise, agency B says "All counselors handle data because they all handle application processes".

Similarly, agency C "Yes, we have a corporate communications unit that oversees that".

While agency D states that "anyone handling data is responsible for protecting it".

d. Sensitization

Travel agency A had more evidence of effort made towards ensuring that their customer is made aware of their company's data protection policy. In the exact words

"We have become more careful about how we handle data. Now that we know what data protection is, we understand that the impact of a breach of data protection has a more negative effect on the customer than us as a company. This is because the customer can be exposed to the danger of being defrauded or even face hurt. So, we are now extremely careful. We also make our customers aware of data protection through the biodata form we send to them to fill for their application. Sometimes the universities we process to request for a GDPR form to be filled by the student".

Contrary to this, agency B, C and D rely on customers to ask about data protection before they say anything about, this seldom occurs because business is based on trust.

Agency B “Some of them ask us if their information is safe and we tell them yes”.

Summary

The themes that emerged from the individual cases were further categorized into data protection awareness level and data protection implementation challenges. The participating agencies show a willingness to do what is necessary to protect their customers' information. However, low awareness level affects their ability to use effective and safe \data protection methods. How these agencies approach data protection is a reflection of how other agencies might also approach data protection. The findings revealed in **Error! Reference source not found.** that only 50 out of 155 agencies were partly NDPR compliant. Under NDPR compliance levels, all four travel agencies are in level I (NDPR, 2020).

Looking at level one of the NDPR compliance framework, the key requirement is visibility, policy, accountability, and sensitization. Based on these requirements, all four agencies are in level one however, not all satisfied the requirements nonetheless, they are partly compliant based on varying criteria (NDPR, 2020).

Chapter Five: Discussion

1.18 Introduction

In this chapter, the researcher discusses the findings from the collected data and explains them based on the research questions concerning literature and conceptual framework.

“What are the challenges associated with effective legal framework implementation of the Nigeria Data Protection regulation for online and independent travel agencies? Has the government sensitized travel agencies enough to ensure awareness and compliance with NDPR in Nigeria?”

1.18.1 Relating findings to the literature

The different lessons about the principles of data protection are drawn from very sensitive stages of travel agencies' business processes in Nigeria. themes generated from the interview responses will also be discussed. The combination of the regulatory perspective and the travel agency perspective assists us in understanding the Nigerian data protection policy as it is currently. This introduction provides a significant entry point as the main subject, and it will highlight important points concerning the proposed data protection context in Nigeria. This chapter analyzes the empirical and theoretical frameworks of data protection in Nigeria. This is a view to identifying several lessons that can be derived from various travel agencies ' experiences in Nigeria.

1.18.1.1 Lessons from travel agencies

The introduction of Nigeria's Data Protection Regulation (NDPR), brings an end to the era of navigating murky waters of the previous disjointed framework of data protection legislation. The act is a very important milestone that all Nigerians should be proud of. It is the testimony to the commitment of the country to be one of Africa's leaders in promoting and encouraging innovation and recognize the fundamental importance enacted to protect the personal data of everyone.

Travel agencies collect personal data from their clients in Nigeria. It is not possible not to leave personal data footprints in daily interactions. The data collected comprises the client's name, home address, fingerprint, and facial photo. Several travel agencies have a wide range of data protection issues in Nigeria. Unlike other companies, travel agencies can be classified as one of the advanced companies which makes issues of processing of personal data and the

challenges of data protection more complex and advanced. Certain issues in data protection in these traveling agencies are like other companies. The challenges realized in this sector are the consistent demand for information globally. These traveling agencies are the primary collectors of personal information from their clients. The information collected is used with the consent of every individual and for security purposes. According to the agency (A), there is no data policy drafted by their company. Agency (A) assists students who want to study abroad in several countries in different parts of the world, such as the United States of America, Canada, Spain, and Asian countries, to process their admissions and paperwork. While handling the paperwork on admission to international universities, the agency requests information like the name of the student, academic background, qualification, whether he or she is having a bachelor's degree or even a master's degree, the country the student is traveling to, and all the information for financial evidence such as bank statement. One of the issues affecting effective data protection practice identified by the agency (A) is the lack of enough resources to strictly follow the instituted data laws. The gradual increase in the use of unique identifiers has facilitated access to personal data across various departments of the company because there is no data policy.

The major finding of this research is centered on the fact that travel agencies are not aware of the new data protection regulation. One of the key pieces of literature that relate to this finding is Brodin's argument on SMEs' struggle with GDPR implementation. Likewise, the responses from the interviewees suggest that NDPR is more of a guideline that lacks enforcement and legislative backing, and Jemohilun & Akomolede (2015), agrees with this claim in which he argues that the Nigerian government's past effort towards data protection has been merely a bill passed by senate without any legislative backing.

Issues surrounding data protection and security exist everywhere and these research findings reveal that travel agencies are no exception. Travel agencies process a vast amount of data that is needed in rendering services to customers in tourism and hospitality. The introduction of NDPR is a step forward.

Evidence from the interviews conducted and desk research suggests that the travel agencies are not fully compliant.

1.18.1.2 Limited government capacity

The success of data protection in the western can be largely attributed to the government's capacity in enforcing compliance. However, in Nigeria, NITDA – the regulatory body

introduced Data Protection Compliance Organisation (DPCOs) to oversee compliance activities for data processing organizations. The DPCOs can charge a fee for assisting businesses to comply with NDPR. One of the drawbacks of the DPCOs is the amount they decide to charge is not regulated. Hence, it gives room for exploitation. Another drawback is the DPCOs are not penalized for organization non – compliance. The DPCOs are saddled with the responsibility of reaching out to companies but if they decide not to then there is no penalty. During the interview, agency B did mention that they did not have any data protection on their website. She added that her agency had no prior knowledge that having a policy online is an NDPR legal requirement. By privatizing the enforcement of the data protection regulation, the government is at the mercy of the DPCO’s consequently limiting its capacity to enforce the regulation.

1.18.1.3 Lack of awareness

The wave of innovation and invention sweeping through various industries in Nigeria has provided a lot of opportunities as well as an opening for malevolent activities like data loss and porous cybersecurity to occur. Data protection and cybersecurity have remained a major issue, and the lack of awareness has proved a menace to various businesses today, such as travel agencies due to manipulation of data and questionable data security transactions. The complexity and sophistication of current data loss in the travel industry sector require very special attention. Therefore, the National Information Technology Development Agency (NITDA) published and issued data protection regulation that has come to overturn the lack of a tangible framework for data protection and privacy in the country.

The data privacy regulations published are meant to introduce key compliance compulsions for Nigerian travel companies, that includes audit checks, the publication of data protection policies, filing of audit reports amongst other policies, and stipulation of strict penalties for breaching personal data provided by the companies. However, most Nigerians do not understand the regulations that have been published for protecting personal data. This is because of the lack of awareness concerning data privacy. Most of the travel agencies in Nigeria, therefore, keep private personal information provided by their clients in non-data security software due to a lack of relevant knowledge about data protection policies. Many authors have suggested from the literature that awareness is a key concept of data protection (Crossler, 2011), (Booth & Ho, 2017), (Kokolakis, 2017), (Martin & Murphy, 2017) and (Markkula & Rohunen, 2018). Some have argued that low awareness affects the way people

generally behave towards data protection issues (Soumelidou & Tsohou, 2021), (Abdulrauf, 2015). Lack of awareness is consistent across all four travel agencies A, B, C, and D, all confirm that they had never heard about the regulation. If data controllers such as these agencies are not aware, how much more the public. The concept of information privacy awareness suggests that data subjects will behave differently depending on their awareness level. If the travel agencies were aware of the Nigerian data protection regulation, they would have better data protection practices. Like agency B rightly puts “ *there are privacy laws in most countries but, if there are privacy laws in Nigeria, I am not sure they are being rightly followed. People need to be aware that there is a punishment for misusing people’s data. The problem with Nigeria is ignorance* ”.

1.18.1.4 The weakness of the NDPR construct

Nigeria has embraced the EU model of data protection with a comprehensive law that regulates the public and private transport sector data handling activities. However, in Nigeria, no distinction has been made between rights to protection of data and rights to privacy, unlike in the EU. Data protection is a fundamental part of the right to information privacy. The Nigerian approach to data protection is in line with the EU Directive, where the right to privacy is practically connected to data protection. Because of the considerable impact, the EU data protection regime has on Nigeria, and it is argued that the theoretical basis for data protection is similar in both prerogatives. Data protection in Nigeria is to protect the dignity of all Nigerians. Human dignity is a fundamental value in the constitution of Nigeria and has significantly influenced every individual right in the bill of rights. Thus, data protection as an integral part of privacy is also the primary reason for promoting dignity for the people of Nigeria. Nevertheless, they also worry about processing their data by transport companies and travel agencies in both the private and public sectors. It seems that the Nigerian people do not worry a lot about the processing of their data by private firms.

One of the issues which are considered by African data protection scholars is the impact of the African culture on the data protection regime. Data protection is a human right and is based on technology and, consequently, outside the realms of the African culture. In addition, this shows that the suitability of the regulation with the Nigerian culture and business environment was not put into consideration. Many businesses in Nigeria, are still waking up to the digitalization of their business. With this in view, data protection seems like a far-fetched idea. Another point to note is the attitude of the travel agencies towards data protection. Though they were self-

educated in data protection, they did not make efforts to know if data protection like GDPR existed in Nigeria. In a society where people are hardly held accountable for wrongdoings, one would not expect any less of the same attitude towards data protection. If travel agencies or other businesses can get away with data breaches, why then should they care about protecting their customers' data. For instance, in 2017, a lawsuit was filed against MTN a telecommunications company for unsolicited messages from a third party to a subscriber (Punch, 2017) they ended up paying about \$7,000 for damages to the subscriber. If the same approach is given to data controllers and processors, then they would be more conscious of how they process data. However, surprisingly, a penalty for defaulting exists in the regulation which is charged as 2% on annual gross revenue.

1.18.1.5 The Nigerian government priority on other sectors

Nigeria has since 2020 faced many challenges like poverty, unemployment, and now facing insecurity issues. Given these challenges, it would be difficult for the government to make data protection a priority. All available resources are being channeled towards making Nigeria safe again for the public. However, there is no predicted timeframe for when the government will be ready for data protection. Though insecurity poses a major concern for both the public and the government of Nigeria, people are still concerned about the misuse of their data. During the interview, the agencies were asked how they would feel if their personal information was lost or used without their permission. Agency A expressed that he would feel horrible and uncomfortable, agency B stated that she would not like it, especially if her information was made public without her consent. Similarly, agency C mentioned that she would be offended if her information was shared without her consent and agency D expressed that sharing customers' information goes against their company policy. All these responses go to show that Nigerians are still worried about the security of their data.

1.18.1.6 Inadequate technological support for data protection

Agency C mentioned that the government should provide technical support for data protection implementation. It was surprising to see that only 50 out of 155 travel agencies in Nigeria have a website and only 9 out of 50 had a data protection policy. See **Error! Reference source not found.** Looking at the cross-case analysis, agencies C and B did not have a data protection policy on their website. Although they have a good level of data protection practice within their organization, it is still not at acceptable levels when compared with the NDPR compliance checklist. The companies have a long way to go with ticking all the check boxes on the NDPR

compliance checklist. These agencies operated based on trust but when trust is breached, customers are likely to withdraw from patronizing businesses. However, Afroz et al (2013), suggests that there are customers who regardless of what they have been through, would still patronize the same companies responsible for the breach of their data. NDPR in its compliance framework stated that technical support will be provided to organizations processing data through the DPCOs. However, if these DPCOs do not reach out to the travel agencies or any company eligible, it will be difficult for these companies to receive the promised technical support. In summary, these travel agencies are not aware of the Nigeria data protection regulation and as a result, their compliance levels are low.

1.18.1.7 Attitudes of the travel agencies – Conflict of interest

Literature suggests that one of the key drivers for data collection is ‘*economic benefit*’ (Rubinstein, 2013). With the introduction of privacy by design by both the EU GDPR and NDPR, it is difficult to ascertain whether the travel agencies will treat the economic benefit as an opportunity cost forgone to protect their customer’s data. For instance, most travel agencies do not share their clients’ data with third-party companies that are not in their processing pipeline. However, if a business opportunity arises that they cannot market directly to their client, there is no way to guarantee that these agencies will not share their client’s information for the exchange of economic benefits. This puts the data subject at the mercy of the travel agencies to decide whether they have an interest in promoting or even fostering data protection policies or regulations over economic benefits. Protecting personal data should concentrate on the interest of the individual's right to control the processing of his or her data. Protection of data should be treated as a human right rather than other mere interests, which should be competing with other fewer interests. Therefore, the leadership and staff of the travel agencies should be able to take a less self-serving approach in protecting data gathered from their clients while attending to them.

1.18.2 Relating findings to the conceptual framework

‘What are the challenges associated with the implementation of the Nigeria Data Protection regulation for online and independent travel agencies’

Brodin (2019), suggests that small to medium-sized organizations are struggling to implement GDPR requirements. Therefore, he proposed a framework to help SMEs adapt to GDPR. His framework has three stages: analysis, design, and implementation. The theoretical framework

for this study was developed using Brodin's framework. See **Error! Reference source not found.** How the findings relate to the theoretical framework will now be discussed.

1.18.2.1 Analysis stage

The analysis stage of the framework consists of three elements: organization, security, and lawfulness. The organization element in the analysis stage helps an organization to assess whether they process sensitive data. From the interviews conducted, agencies A, B, C, and D all mentioned that they process sensitive data such as names, biometric information, financial status, ethnic information, etc. According to GDPR sensitive information is any data that reveal sensitive details about a data subject. The kind of information that these travel agencies process is highly sensitive. For example, these agencies ask for financial information such as bank statements and biometric information like a passport. If these documents get mistakenly transferred to the wrong party, the customer could be endangered. A passport contains legal names which are also on the bank statement. Nowadays, customers can phone a bank to change passwords to account or make transfers. A customer's bank statement often contains information like address, closing, and opening balance. If a wrong party gets a hold of the customers' information, he can either call the customer in pretense as the bank to retrieve account passwords or call the bank in pretense as the customer to make transfers. After the interview data were analyzed, the results show that all four agencies process sensitive data. In terms of the security of the information they process, none of them had an advance technical system for safeguarding their customer information. Finally, in terms of lawfulness, the agencies did not know what was legally required of them by NDPR hence, they processed data based on self-education and not under NDPR requirements.

1.18.2.2 Design stage

The design stage consists of routines, policies, and templates that aid privacy by design. NDPR requires that every data controller develop its data protection policies following the NDPR guidelines. The findings from the interview revealed that the agencies did not have a template in place to handle breaches or a systematic way of receiving and storing sensitive information. Two out of four agencies – B and C mentioned that everyone in their organization is responsible for handling data except for agency C who stated that they had a corporate communications unit and agency A had a data protection monitoring staff. The NDPR compliance framework requires that a data controller (anyone who processes sensitive data) should design systems in place that can allow customers to request for correction or erasure of their information. All four

agencies did not have such systems or routines in place. See Table 12: **NDPR compliance checklist for travel agencies (National Information Technology Development Agency, 2020)**. In addition, only two out of four agencies in the case study had data protection on their website, while only nine out of fifty travel agencies from the desk research had a data protection policy on their website. This is a sad reflection of how data protection is perceived in Nigeria.

1.18.2.3 Implementation stage

The implementation stage has to do with training, communication, and adjustment. According to Brodin (2019), this stage is aimed at ensuring effective data protection practice within organizations. The travel agencies in this study had low levels of training regarding data protection, particularly agency C who was not aware that her agency had a data protection policy on their website. This shows a deficiency in data protection training within the organization. For data protection practice to work, there should be an integration of training, regular communication of data protection policies, and adjustments of policies where there are deficiencies. In contrast, agencies A and B mentioned that their staffs receive training for data protection but not following NDPR requirements.

1.19 Summary

This section has answered the research questions as set out in the introduction section which is: *‘‘What are the challenges associated with effective legal framework implementation of the Nigeria Data Protection regulation for online and independent travel agencies??’’* and *‘‘Has the government sensitized travel agencies enough to ensure awareness and compliance with NDPR in Nigeria?’’*.

Findings from the interview with four travel agencies representing the key sectors in the travel industry suggest that the travel agencies are not aware of the Nigerian data protection regulation. Furthermore, the lack of awareness posed a major challenge in the implementation of effective data protection practices following NDPR. In addition, agencies A and B who were partly compliant had prior knowledge on general data protection from international organizations that were GDPR compliant. Using the knowledge derived from these international organizations, they implemented a level of data policy in their agencies. However, the practice was limited because it did not encompass all aspects of NDPR. NDPR had key aspects of its regulation such as data retention period, right to be forgotten, and right to be informed. Since the travel agencies were not aware, these aspects were not considered. Furthermore, the NDPR made efforts towards aiding compliance by introducing DPCOs who were responsible for activities such as, training data controllers, and auditing data compliance reports, etc. Adding to the fact that these travel agencies were not aware that these DPCOs exist, there is no evidence of the DPCOs carrying out such training activities for data controllers. In summary, these agencies were not aware that NDPR existed, which led to non-compliance, resulting in implementation challenges.

Chapter Six: Conclusion

When EU GDPR was introduced, not every country had an active data protection regulation in place including Nigeria. The need for data protection became very evident as fraud cases increased and people become scared of sharing their data. Many works have been done in the western context regarding data protection and frameworks have been suggested however, these past studies do not fit into the Nigerian context. On January 25th, 2019, the Nigerian government introduced the Nigerian data protection regulation which was an attempt to provide a guideline that informs data controllers of the responsibility laid out for them within the regulation. But the strategy to implement the regulation was a bit vague. The Nigerian government later in 2020 introduced a scheme that allowed private individuals to register and get licensed as Data Protection Compliance Organisations (DPCOs) for a fee. Since the introduction of the scheme, the regulatory body has only registered and licensed 103 organizations to act as DPCOs. Considering a population of over 200million+ and over 155 registered travel agencies with 500+ independent travel agencies in active operation in Nigeria, 103 DPCOs is a considerably small number. With over one year of the regulation coming into force, not many agencies were aware of it. Thus, this thesis explored the effectiveness of the Nigerian data protection practice in Nigeria and used four travel agencies as a case study to gain a deeper insight into the issue. With consideration of the findings, the researcher recommends an action plan for the government and a step-by-step implementation guideline for the travel agencies which will aid effective data protection practice in Nigeria.

The first research question is: ‘‘To what extent does legislative backing, direct towards governing data protection existent in Nigeria for online and independent travel agencies?’’ The above questions were answered by reviewing past works of literature which covered the past and the present attempt made by the Nigerian government towards ensuring that data is protected. The literature suggests that the government, in a view to foster data protection, created some bills such as Electronic Fraud Prohibition Bill (2008), the Computer Security and Critical Information Infrastructure Protection Bill (2005), The Cyber Security and Data Protection Agency Bill (2008), among many others. However, all these bills were not specifically directed towards data protection and had no legislative backing till NDPR was introduced.

The second research question is: ‘‘What are the challenges associated with effective legal framework implementation of the Nigeria Data Protection regulation for online and

independent travel agencies’”? This question brings to notice the key challenge as highlighted in past research to be unawareness on the part of customers especially in developing countries like Nigeria. Unawareness about what NDPR is all about is the major challenge and its evident from interviews carried out by the researcher. There was a very low level of compliance because of unawareness that NDPR exists in the first place. In the western context, the organization being able to carry out GDPR practices in full understanding is a major issue. One of the issues highlighted by Brodin (2019) was the fact that SMEs are struggling to follow up GDPR because they do not fully understand what is expected of them. Another challenge was the lack of technical know-how on advanced security such as the use of encryption software by data controllers. In Nigeria, it might be costly for agencies to implement advanced security measures.

The third research question is: ‘‘Has the government sensitized travel agencies enough to ensure awareness and compliance with NDPR in Nigeria?’’ This question points in the direction of what the government has done in terms of the introduction of data protection compliance organizations which, is a scheme to allow private individuals to register as data protection officers who will be saddled with the responsibility of training, sensitizing, filing, and auditing for data controllers (travel agencies). However, there is no regulation on how much data controllers should be charged. This is an enabling ground for monopoly, and It gives room for corrupt practices to happen. Therefore, this chapter will present the key findings, the implication of the research (for NDPR regulatory authority, travel agencies, and data subject), limitations of the research, recommendation and future research.

1.20 Key findings of the study

After concluding the literature review, desk research and analysis of the interviews, the findings were:

- I. All four agencies were not fully compliant based on the conceptual framework for assessing NDPR compliance (see figure 6).
- II. All four travel agencies are not aware of the Nigerian data protection regulation based on interview responses.
- III. Out of 155 registered travel agencies, 59% did not have a data protection policy in place, 20% had a policy but only 3% were partly compliant based on the NDPR accessibility criteria.

1.21 Implications of the research

For researchers

The findings of this research on data protection practice in the Nigerian context enabled an extension of the current existing model of data privacy like Brodin's model to suit the Nigerian context.

Previous existing models were only applicable in the western context but, because of the findings gotten from this research, future researchers can develop new models to suit the target research area just as it was done in the Nigerian context.

For the government

The findings from the research suggested that NDPR adoption is slow due to lack of awareness and just as Brodin mentioned in his research, organizations do not fully understand what is required of them by GDPR.

Likewise, in the Nigerian context, the travel agencies had similar challenges. For instance, agency B mentioned her agency was not aware that they were even in breach of any regulation, adding that the major problem in Nigeria is ignorance.

Therefore, the government needs to take more active steps towards using a system that is suitable for Nigeria's style of business because one rule does not fit all.

For agencies

The findings suggest that the agencies had a lackadaisical attitude towards data protection, largely due to unawareness. Nonetheless, the findings from this research will make travel agencies more aware of data protection. In addition, it will foster a good working relationship between travel agencies and their customer and help to achieve the common goal of the government which is data protection. Nigeria is a multi-cultural society with a high level of technology in Africa hence, prone to more data protection issues because of the sophisticated nature of Nigerian societies. The issues surrounding data privacy may not be a limitation to many companies in the country as the level of technological development is steadily growing. However, with the contribution of this research to awareness levels among travel agencies, data privacy will surely improve.

For customers

Customers are the center of data protection and as such, the findings from this research affect them as well. If the agencies can adopt the recommended step-by-step approach in implementing NDPR then, their behavior towards data protection will change consequently, positively affect how they treat their customers. Customers will benefit from agencies or organizations' improved overall data protection awareness.

1.22 Limitation of the research.

The researcher does not imply that this research can be applied to other industries however, it supports the evidence from current literature which suggests that low data protection awareness is a key challenge in data protection practices. The research was based on a limited sample size due to covid 19 restrictions. Hence, many of the agencies that would have participated in the interviews were unwilling to do so because they were focused on recovering from the financial losses caused by the pandemic. In addition, the research is based on the researcher's perspective and experience due to the nature of the researcher's job.

1.23 Recommendation

1.23.1 For the government

Given the issues surrounding the data protection practices in Nigeria, and the insights gotten from the case study interviews, the researcher recommends some measures which will promote effective data protection practices within travel agencies in Nigeria for the government and a step-by-step implementation guide for the data controllers.

Collaboration between travel agencies, NDPR and EFCC

Considering the data gotten from the Nigerian civil aviation authority website, there are 145 registered travel agencies. However, figures from NANTA vary, amounting to 5000 registered travel agencies and over 25,000 independent travel consultants. These figures show that there is much access to the data of a large populace of travelers. In addition, the literature reveals that most successful financial fraud or scam cases have been largely successful due to access to sensitive information. Furthermore, the popularly known 'yahoo boys' like to travel in luxury and style. Because of the above information from the literature, the researcher recommends that a collaboration between the travel agencies, NDPR, and EFCC will help to

minimize fraud cases. This can be achieved through the same method the bank and the EFCC uses. Nigerian banks alert the commission of the economic and financial crime (EFCC), anytime a customer requests to withdrawal up to 5million naira in cash. Though the customer may not be immediately arrested, the request is placed on hold until EFCC completes its investigation. The same method could work between travel agencies, NDPR, and EFCC such that the regulators could be alerted when a non- frequent traveler with zero travel history buys a first-class ticket. This could work because travel agencies often hold sensitive information such as bank statements.

The introduction of compliance certificates for online and offline display

Travel agencies are required by the NDPR to display their data protection policy on their website for their customers to see and read. Based on the requirement, the researcher recommends that the NDPR introduce a compliance certification for travel agencies which can be displayed on their website. This will make the customer aware that there is such a thing as data protection and that they can trust the certified agency with their information. For instance, Trustpilot helps to boost customers' confidence on websites where they are present through reviews given by customers about a particular company. In the same way, if the travel agencies have an online or offline display of data protection compliance certificates, it will help customers spot non-compliant agencies who might make their data susceptible to risk.

Adopting a mandatory approach for data protection compliance organizations (DPCOs)

The current NDPR compliance framework allows private firms to register to become a licensed data protection compliance organization at a fee. In addition, the license given by NDPR will allow approved DPCOs to provide the following services to data controllers: advisory services, training and awareness, contract drafting, breach remedies, and support, privacy breach impact assessment, outsourced data protection officer (DPO), and information privacy audit. DPCOs are asked to pay a licensing fee of 50,000 naira annually (National Information Technology Development Agency, 2020). However, DPCOs are not held accountable for non-compliant companies. This is more like a reporting body than a compliance aid.

The authority given to the DPCOs is such that data controllers cannot file their compliance report without a verification statement from the DPCOs which, creates dependence on the DPCOs. Despite this, if a data controller decides not to file its compliance report, no provision within the NDPR compliance framework mandates the DPCOs to carry out checks. Therefore,

the researcher recommends that data processing organizations should be made more responsible by making training of data controllers a mandatory responsibility rather than an option for DPCOs. In addition, DPCOs can be given licenses that are sectioned covering specific trading industries of all data controllers and processors with a target to achieve a certain yearly registration for all data controllers and processors. If the DPCOs are unable to meet their target consistently over a period, their license should be revoked. Likewise, the DPCOs should be empowered to sanction companies who refused to be NDPR compliant. By so doing, the DPCOs would have no choice but to reach out to companies who process data to train, sensitize them about data protection as well as assist in filing their reports. If this can be implemented, data awareness will spread faster amongst organizations and at the same time increase customer awareness.

1.23.2 For the travel agencies

1.23.2.1 Data protection pop-ups for travel agencies staffs

The interview findings reveal that the travel agencies did not have sufficient training for data protection practices. Because of this, the researcher recommends that the travel agencies use a data protection prompt software which will be embedded in all staff work laptops. This software will pop-up reminders to staff anytime a sensitive document is opened. This will help constantly remind staff about the importance of data protection and by so doing minimize the risk of breaches or misuse of customers' data.

1.23.2.2 Step by Step implementation guide for data controllers

The NDPR compliance framework contains requirements that may be challenging for implementation at once. The interview findings reveal that the travel agencies did not have sufficient training for data protection practices. Given this, the researcher recommends a step-by-step guide for data controllers to implement NDPR with consideration of the NDPR compliance levels.

Table 14: Step-by-step guide for data controllers to implement NDPR

Compliance levels	Practical steps to achieve it
Level I (Basic stage of compliance)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Have a data protection policy. - Make data protection policy easily accessible to the customer via offline and online display depending on where business activities are carried out. - Integrate data protection pop-up for the customer if using a website. - Conduct quarterly data protection training for all staff. - Appoint a data protection officer within or without the organization. - Password-sensitive documents when sharing (google mail has this feature). - Attend data protection sensitization meetings to keep up with industry trends. - Decide on a data retention period (how long you would keep a customer’s data before deleting it forever). - Inform customers of their right to request erasure or correction via published documents. - Mandate staff to read out a concise data policy to all new clients. - Limit sharing of files to those who need it.
Level II (moderate compliant stage)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Save documents on cloud servers - Discourage staff from saving customer information on personal laptops - Reset password frequently (this can be done using a password generator). - Install antiviruses and specialized firewall software e.g., Windows protect,

	<p>MacAfee internet security, Norton security, etc.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Engage the services of encryption solution providers for digital security. - Train staff on how to use installed data security software
Level III (fully compliant stage)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Register with a licensed DPCO who will provide more advanced data protection training and assist with filing compliance reports.

The table above shows a recommended step-by-step guide for data controllers to implement NDPR with consideration of the NDPR compliance levels.

The researcher recommends that the travel agencies use a data protection prompt software which will be embedded in all staff work laptops. This software will pop-up reminders to staff anytime a sensitive document is opened. This will help constantly remind staff about the importance of data protection and by so doing minimize the risk of breaches or misuse of customers' data.

1.24 Future research

This research brings a unique and significant contribution to the body of knowledge in data protection topic, especially since the NDPR is a new regulation, and no paper has been written in this aspect. Nonetheless, the researcher believes that there are more areas worth researching to contribute to the body of knowledge, especially in the Nigerian context.

- I. This research case study was limited to four due to the global pandemic. Therefore, it will be interesting for future researchers to explore the effectiveness of data protection on a larger scale using a more diverse sample size. This will bring more insight, understanding, and significant contribution to literature.
- II. The research was focused on the travel agencies however, access to sensitive data is not restricted to travel agencies alone. Other entities such as financial institutions like banks, microfinance, loan companies, the police, economic and financial crimes commission, etc use sensitive data. It will be valuable to research data protection practices in these entities.

- III. Findings also suggest that culture affects customers and agency attitudes towards data protection in practice. It will be worthwhile to investigate how culture may create bias in agencies' behavior towards an issue like data subject request for the erasure of their data, and attitude towards breach of data policy because of culture.
- IV. This research was based on the agency's perspective, a little in government perspective through enacted policies. It will, however, be of great benefit if the perspective of Nigerian customers towards data protection is investigated. In addition, the government is perceived as weak so obtaining government perspective on their challenges with the implementation challenges will be a rich contribution to the body of knowledge.

1.25 Summary

This thesis has reviewed data protection from different perspectives and authors. Some were based on customers' privacy while others were focused on privacy from organizations' perspective. However, there are few studies done to explore the challenges faced by travel agencies in implementing the Nigerian data protection regulation. Hence this research has filled that gap. In the context of developed countries like the EU, one of the key factors that led to the success of the GDPR is the government's capacity to enforce the regulation nevertheless, in Nigeria, the government's enforcement capacity is limited to the DPCOs. Both GDPR and NDPR encourage privacy by design which allows organizations to decide what their data policy will contain under the regulation. Due to the diversity of business industries, privacy by design is still the most suitable approach to the implementation of data protection policy due to its flexibility. Data protection appears to be the second agenda for most companies due to little public concern and awareness for data protection. Thus, there is an urgent need for data re-orientation on the basis and significance of data protection among various businesses and companies and in particular travel agencies. More effort should be made from the regulators, data controllers, and customers in enabling a smooth transition from a non-conscious privacy world to a more aware privacy world.

References

- Abdulrauf, L. (2015) 'The legal protection of data privacy in Nigeria: lessons from Canada and South Africa. Ph.D. University of Pretoria.
- Adeneyo, A. (2019) Instagram deletes Linda Ikeji's blog account. Kemi Finali News. [Online]. Blog. Available: <https://www.kemifilani.ng/2019/03/instagram-deletes-linda-ikejis-blog-account.html> [Accessed 13 Jun 2019].
- African Union (2021) List Of Countries Which Have Signed, Ratified/Acceded To The African Union Convention On Cyber Security And Personal Data Protection [Online]. ebook. African Union. Available: <https://au.int/sites/default/files/treaties/29560-sl-AFRICAN%20UNION%20CONVENTION%20ON%20CYBER%20SECURITY%20AND%20PERSONAL%20DATA%20PROTECTION.pdf> [Accessed 6 Feb 2021].
- Afroz, S., Islam, A., Santell, J., Chapin, A. and Greenstadt, R. (2013) How Privacy Flaws Affect Consumer Perception. 2013 Third Workshop on Socio-Technical Aspects in Security and Trust.
- Alan Bryman. (n.d.) Social Research Methods, 2nd Ed. Oxford University Press.
- Altman, I. (1975) The environment and social behavior. Monterey, Calif.: Brooks/Cole Pub. Co.
- Anderson, G. (2002) Fundamentals of educational research. London: Routledge Falmer.
- Ang, P. (2001) The Role of Self-Regulation of Privacy and the Internet. Journal of Interactive Advertising. Vol.1 (2), pp.1-9.
- Anon. (2018) Forbes. [Online]. Available: <<https://www.forbes.com/sites/forbestechcouncil/2018/12/19/data-privacy-vs-data-protection-understanding-the-distinction-in-defending-your-data/#6dafa80750c9>> [Accessed 6 Aug 2021].
- Ataei, M., Degbelo, A., Kray, C. and Santos, V. (2018) Complying with Privacy Legislation: From Legal Text to Implementation of Privacy-Aware Location-Based Services. ISPRS International Journal of Geo-Information. Vol.7 (11), p.442.
- Baker, S., Gentry, J. and Rittenburg, T. (2005) Building Understanding of the Domain of Consumer Vulnerability. Journal of Macromarketing. Vol.25 (2), pp.128-139.

- Barry, C., Britten, N., Barber, N., Bradley, C. and Stevenson, F. (1999) Using Reflexivity to Optimize Teamwork in Qualitative Research. Qualitative Health Research. Vol.9 (1), pp.26-44.
- Baxter, P. and Jack, S. (2015) Qualitative Case Study Methodology: Study Design and Implementation for Novice Researchers. The Qualitative Report.
- Beersma, B. and Van Kleef, G. (2011) How the Grapevine Keeps You in Line: Gossip Increases Contributions to the Group. SAGE Journals. Vol.2 (6), pp.642-649.
- Bélanger and Crossler (2011) Privacy in the Digital Age: A Review of Information Privacy Research in Information Systems. MIS Quarterly. Vol.35 (4), p.1017.
- Bihari, E. (2018) GDPR – A Y2K-II for Business?. EDPACS. Vol.57 (2), pp.1-9.
- Booth, C. and Ho, S. (2021) Does the cloud have a silver lining? Privacy concerns and perceived risk in cloud technology adoption [Online]. Hdl.handle.net. Available: <http://hdl.handle.net/2142/96712> [Accessed 7 Apr 2020].
- Braghin, C. and Del Vecchio, M. (2017) Is Pokémon GO Watching You? A Survey on the Privacy-Awareness of Location-Based Apps' Users. 2017 IEEE 41st Annual Computer Software and Applications Conference (COMPSAC).
- Brandimarte, L., Acquisti, A. and Loewenstein, G. (2012) Misplaced Confidences. Social Psychological and Personality Science. Vol.4 (3), pp.340-347.
- Brodin, M. (2019) A Framework for GDPR Compliance for Small- and Medium-Sized Enterprises. European Journal for Security Research. Vol.4 (2), pp.243-264.
- Buchenscheit, A., Könings, B., Neubert, A., Schaub, F., Schneider, M. and Kargl, F. (2014) Privacy implications of presence sharing in mobile messaging applications. Proceedings of the 13th International Conference on Mobile and Ubiquitous Multimedia - MUM '14.
- Buttarelli, G. (2016) The EU GDPR as a clarion call for a new global digital gold standard. International Data Privacy Law. Vol.6 (2), pp.77-78.
- Bank of Scotland's fined for repeated fax blunder. (2021) [Online]. The Economic Times. Available: <https://economictimes.indiatimes.com/news/international/bank-of-scotland-s-fined-for-repeated-fax-blunder/articleshow/21627654.cms> [Accessed 14 Jan 2020].

- Coronavirus and the impact on the UK travel and tourism industry. (2021) [Online]. Office for national Statistics. Available:
<<https://www.ons.gov.uk/businessindustryandtrade/tourismindustry/articles/coronavirusandtheimpactontheuktravelandtourismindustry/2021-02-15>> [Accessed 6 Jan 2021].
- Chang, Wong, Lee, LY and SF (2015) Understanding perceived privacy: research gate. A privacy boundary management model.
- Chatzipoulidis, A., Tsiakis, T. and Kargidis, T. (2019) A readiness assessment tool for GDPR compliance certification. Computer Fraud & Security. Vol.2019 (8), pp.14-19.
- Chen, Y. and Barnes, S. (2007) Initial trust and online buyer behaviour. Industrial Management & Data Systems. Vol.107 (1), pp.21-36.
- Christensen, C. and Carlile, P. (2009) Course Research: Using the Case Method to Build and Teach Management Theory. Academy of Management Learning & Education. Vol.8 (2), pp.240-251.
- Cole, J. (2000) The impact of the internet on our social political and economic life. The UCCLA Centre For Communication Policy, Los Angeles.
- Collier, G. (1995) Information privacy. Information Management & Computer Security. Vol.3 (1), pp.41-45.
- Coraggio, G. and Zappaterra, G. (2018) The risk-based approach to privacy: Risk or protection for business?. Data Protection & Privacy. Vol.4 (1), pp.339-344.
- Culnan, M. (1993) "How Did They Get My Name?": An Exploratory Investigation of Consumer Attitudes toward Secondary Information Use. MIS Quarterly. Vol.17 (3), p.341.
- Culnan, M. and Bies, R. (2003) Consumer Privacy: Balancing Economic and Justice Considerations. Journal of Social Issues. Vol.59 (2), pp.323-342.
- Denzin, N. and Lincoln, Y. (1994) Handbook of qualitative research. Thousand Oaks: Sage Publications.
- Dinev, T., Xu, H., Smith, J. and Hart, P. (2013) Information privacy and correlates: an empirical attempt to bridge and distinguish privacy-related concepts. European Journal of Information Systems. Vol.22 (3), pp.295-316.

- DSS arrests EFCC acting Chairman, Ibrahim Magu. (2021) [Online]. GistReel. Available: <https://www.gistreel.com/dss-arrests-efcc-acting-chairman-ibrahim-magu/> [Accessed 6 Aug 2021].
- Easterby-Smith, M., Thorpe, R. and Lowe, A. (1991) Management research: An introduction. Sage publication London.
- Eisenhardt, K. (1989) Building Theories from Case Study Research. The Academy of Management Review. Vol.14 (4), p.532.
- FSA fines former commercial broker £472,000. (2012) [Online]. Insurance times. Available: <https://www.insurancetimes.co.uk/fsa-fines-former-broker-almost-05m/1397769.article> [Accessed 20 Jan 2021].
- FSA fines Zurich Insurance £2,275,000 following the loss of 46,000 policy holders' personal details. (1986) [Online]. FCA. Available: <https://www.fca.org.uk/news/press-releases/fsa-fines-zurich-insurance-%C2%A32275000-following-loss-46000-policy-holders-personal> [Accessed 6 Aug 2021].
- Feinberg, M., Cheng, J. and Willer, R. (2012) Gossip as an effective and low-cost form of punishment. Behavioral and Brain Sciences. Vol.35 (1), pp.25-25.
- Thom, H. (2021) Big Data: Opportunities and Privacy Challenges [Online]. arXiv.org. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/1502.00823> [Accessed 7 Sep 2019].
- Finch, J. (1986) Research and policy. The flamer press, London.
- Fisher, C. (2003) Researching and writing a dissertation for business students.
- Flavian, C. and Guinaliu, M. (2006) 'Consumer trust, perceived security and privacy policy: Three basic elements of loyalty to a web site. Industrial Management & Data Systems. Vol.106 (5), pp.601-620.
- Flyvbjerg, B. (2006) Five Misunderstandings About Case-Study Research. Qualitative Inquiry. Vol.12 (2), pp.219-245.
- Gadatsch, A. (2017) Big data - data analysis as a ticket to the future. big data for decision-maker, Springer Vieweg, Wiesbaden.

- Garcia-Murillo, M. and Annabi, H. (2000) Customer knowledge management. Journal of the Operational Research Society. Vol.53 (8), pp.675-884.
- Garson, G. (2021) Guide to writing empirical papers, thesis, and dissertations. 1st ed. New York: CRC Press.
- Gebert, H., Geib, M., Kolbe, L. and Riempp, G. (2002) Towards customer knowledge management: Integrating customer relationship management and knowledge management concepts. The institute of information management.
- Gibbert, M., Leibold, M. and Probst, G. (2021) 'Five styles of customer knowledge management and how smart companies use them to create value'. European Management. Vol.20 (5), pp.459-469.
- GIGYA (2017) THE 2017 state of consumer privacy and trust.
- Gilmore, T., Krantz, J. and Ramirez, R. (1986) Action based modes of inquiry and the host-researcher relationship. An international Journal. Vol.5, pp.160-176.
- Grundstrom, C., Väyrynen, K., Iivari, N. and Isomursu, N. (2019) Making sense of the general data protection regulation. four categories of, HICSS.
- Gudmundsdottir, G. (2014) The Online Self: Memory and Forgetting in the digital age. European Journal of Life Writing. Vol.3, pp.42-54.
- Gummesson, E. (1991) Qualitative Methods in Evaluation. Sage Publication.
- GDPR Penalties and Fines | What's the Maximum Fine?. (2020) [Online]. Itgovernance.co.uk. Available: <https://www.itgovernance.co.uk/dpa-and-gdpr-penalties> [Accessed 28 Jan 2021].
- GDPR personal data – what information does this cover? GPDR. (2021) [Online]. GDPREU. Available: <https://www.gdpreu.org/the-regulation/key-concepts/personal-data/> [Accessed 6 Aug 2021].
- Hert, P., Vagelis, P. and Malgieri, G. (2021) 'The right to data portability in the GDPR: Towards user-centric interoperability of digital services'. Computer Law and Security Review. Vol.34 (2), pp.193-203.

- Homebase plans to close 42 stores and cut 1,500 jobs. (2021) [Online]. BBC News.
Available: <https://www.bbc.co.uk/news/business-45180984> [Accessed 5 Aug 2021].
- Intention to fine British airways £183.39m under GDPR for data breach. (2019) [Online].
Information Commissioner's office. Available: <<https://ico.org.uk/about-the-ico/news-and-events/news-and-blogs/2019/07/statement-ico-announces-intention-to-fine-british-airways/>> [Accessed 6 Aug 2021].
- International data transfers: European Commission Standard Contractual Clauses – Jose Caballero Gutierrez. (2019) [Online]. Jlcaballero.com. Available:
<https://jlcaballero.com/en/international-data-transfers-european-commission-standard-contractual-clauses/> [Accessed 6 Aug 2021].
- Internet fraud: Nigerian scammer 'pulls off \$1m heist' from prison. (2021) [Online]. BBC News. Available: <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-africa-50480495> [Accessed 5 Aug 2021].
- James, S. (2011) The internet and society. Polity.
- Jarvenpaa, S. and Teigland, R. (2017) Introduction to trust, identity and trusted systems in digital environments minitrack. In Processings of the 50th Hawaii International Conference on Systems Sciences. pp.5812-5816.
- Jemilohun, B. and Akomolede, T. (2015) Regulations or Legislation for Data Protection In Nigeria? A Call for A Clear Legislative Framework. Global Journal of Politics and Law Research. [Online] Vol.3 (4), pp.1-16. Available: <https://www.eajournals.org/wp-content/uploads/Regulations-or-Legislation-for-Data-Protection-in-Nigeria1.pdf> [Accessed 2 Mar 2019].
- Johnson, D. (1994) Research methods in educational management. Longman Group.
- Kokolakis, S. (2017) 'Privacy attitudes and privacy behavior: A review of current research on the privacy paradox phenomenon. Journal of Computer Security. Vol.64, pp.122-124.
- Kolah, A., Foss, B. and Hickey, J. (2015) What should UK and US marketers do to prepare for the biggest threat to business continuity for a decade. Journal of Direct, Data and Digital Marketing Practice. Vol.17 (2), pp.86-92.

- Kraemer, K. and Pinsonneault, A. (1993) 'Survey research methodology in management information systems: An assessment. Journal of Management Information Systems. Vol.10, pp.75-105.
- Kraut, R., Patterson, M., Lundmark, V., Kiesler, S., Mukopadhyay, T. and Scherlis, W. (1998) 'Internet paradox: a social technology that reduces social involvement and psychological wellbeing. American Psychologist. Vol.53 (9), pp.101-731.
- Krystlik, J. (2017) 'With GDPR, preparation is everything'. Computer Fraud & Security. Vol.6, pp.5-8.
- LaSalle (2021) Guarding and growing personal data value [Online]. ebook. Available: <https://www.accenture.com/_acnmedia/pdf-4/accenture-guarding-and-growing-personal-data-value-pov-low-res.pdf> [Accessed 6 Jul 2019].
- Leary, M. (2021) 'Emotional responses to interpersonal rejection. Dialogues in Clinical Neuroscience. Vol.17 (4), pp.435-441.
- Lee, A. and Baskerville, R. (2003) Generalizing generalizability in information systems research. Information Systems Research. pp.221-243.
- Lowry, P., Dinev, T. and Willison, R. (2017) 'Why security and privacy research lies at the centre of the information (is) artefact: proposing a bold research agenda. European Journal of Information Systems. Vol.26 (10), pp.546-563.
- Lyon, D. (2015) The Snowden stakes: challenges for understanding surveillance today. Surveillance & Society. Vol.13 (2), pp.139-152.
- List of licensed data protection compliance organizations. (2021) [Online]. National Information Technology Development Agency. Available: <<https://nitda.gov.ng/wp-content/uploads/2021/07/V7.3-DPCO-LIST-19072021.pdf>> [Accessed 15 Feb 2021].
- List of registered travel agents. (2020) [Online]. Nigerian civil aviation Authority. Available: <<https://old.ncaa.gov.ng/directorates/air-transport-regulation/list-of-registered-travel-agents/>> [Accessed 6 Apr 2021].

- Madge, R. (2021) Five loopholes in the GDPR [Online]. Medium. Available: <https://medium.com/mydata/five-loopholes-in-the-gdpr-367443c4248b> [Accessed 7 Mar 2019].
- Markkula, J. (2018) Development of personal information privacy concerns evaluation. 4th ed. Pennsylvania: IGI GLOBAL.
- Martin, D., Borah, A., and Palmatier, R. (2017) Data privacy: Effects on customer and firm performance. Journal of Marketing. Vol.81 (3), pp.36-58.
- Martin, K. and Murphy, P. (2017) The role of data privacy in marketing'. Journal of Academy of Marketing Science. Vol.45 (2), pp.135-155.
- Martin, P. and Turner, B. (1986) Grounded theory and organizational research. The Journal of Applied Behavioral Science. Vol.2 (22), pp.141-157.
- Martone, M., Garcia-C, A. and Vandebos, G. (2018) Data sharing in psychology. American Psychological Association. Vol.2 (73), pp.111-125.
- Mejía Trejo, J., Sánchez Gutiérrez, J. and Maldonado Guzman, G. (2016) The customer knowledge management and innovation. Contaduría y Administración. Vol.61 (3), pp.456-477.
- Miles, M., Huberman, A. and Johnny, S. (2014) Qualitative data analysis. 3rd ed. United States of America: Sage publication.
- Moore, N. (2018) The four key attitudes to sharing data and how to engage with the different types [Online]. Available: <<https://www.experian.co.uk/blogs/latest-thinking/marketing/four-key-attitudes-sharing-data/>> [Accessed 15 Sep 2020].
- Morgan, G. and Smircich, L. (1980) The case for qualitative research. The Academy of Management. pp.491-500.
- Morrison, G., Ross, S. and Kemp, J. (2010) Designing effective instruction. 6th ed. Baltimore.
- Myers, M. (1999) Investigating information system with ethnographic research. Communication of the Association for Information System. Vol.2 (23), pp.1-20.

- Neuman, W. (2000) Social research methods: Qualitative and quantities approaches. 4th ed. Boston: Allyn and Bacon.
- Nie, N. (2000) Study of social consequences of the internet. Stanford institute of the quantitative study of society.
- Nigel, M., Hunn, A. and Fox, N. (2000) Using Interviews in a research project. Research Approaches in Primary Care. pp.113-134.
- Nir, K. (2017) Cybersecurity in India. Regulations, governance, institutional capacity and market. Vol.8 (1), pp.64-76.
- Nissenbaum, H. (2010) Privacy In Context. Technology, Policy, and the integrity of social life.
- National Association of Nigerian Travel Agencies. (2020) [Online]. NANTA. Available: <<https://nanta.org.ng/>> [Accessed 2 Aug 2019].
- National Information Technology Development Agency. (2021) [Online]. Ndpr.nitda.gov.ng. Available: <https://ndpr.nitda.gov.ng/Content/Doc/ImplementationFramework>. [Accessed 20 May 2020].
- Nigeria Data Protection Regulation 2019: Implementation Framework. (2021) [Online]. National Information Technology Development Agency. Available: <<https://ndpr.nitda.gov.ng/Content/Doc/ImplementationFramework.pdf>> [Accessed 7 Mar 2020].
- Nigeria Population (2021) - Worldometer. (2021) [Online]. Worldometers.info. Available: <https://www.worldometers.info/world-population/nigeria-population/> [Accessed 7 Apr 2020].
- Nigerian National Brought to U.S. to Face Charges of Conspiring to Launder Hundreds of Millions of Dollars from Cybercrime Schemes. (2020) [Online]. Justice.gov. Available: <https://www.justice.gov/usao-cdca/pr/nigerian-national-brought-us-face-charges-conspiring-launder-hundreds-millions-dollars> [Accessed 6 Jul 2020].
- Ojeme, V. (2019) CAC extends 50% reduction in cost of registration fee for business names [Online]. vanguardngr. Available: <https://www.vanguardngr.com/2019/08/cac->

extends-50-reduction-in-cost-of-registration-fee-for-business-names/ [Accessed 18 Nov 2020].

Olivero, N. and Lunt, P. (2004) Privacy versus willingness to disclose in e-commerce exchanges. The effect of risk awareness on the relative role of trust and control. Journal of Economic Psychology. Vol.25 (2), pp.243-262.

Orlowski, J. (2020) The social dilemma [Online]. Netflix official site. Available: <<https://www.netflix.com/gb/title/81254224>> [Accessed 15 Dec 2020].

Ouwerkerk, E. (2021) Beware of GDPR - Take your Cyber Risk Responsibility More Seriously.

Patton, M. (2002) Qualitative research and evaluation methods. 3rd ed. CA: Sage Publications.

Pedersen, D. (1987) 'Psychological functions of privacy. Journal of Environmental Psychology. Vol.17 (2), pp.147-156.

Plachkinova, M. and Maurer, M. (2018) 'Security breach at target. Journal of Information Systems Education. Vol.29 (1), p.7.

Politou, E., Alepis, E. and Patsakis, C. (2018) Forgetting personal data and revoking consent under the GDPR: Challenges and proposed solutions. Journal of Cybersecurity. Vol.4 (1).

Personal Data Protection Guidelines for Africa | Internet Society. (2021) [Online]. Internet Society. Available: <https://www.internetsociety.org/resources/doc/2018/personal-data-protection-guidelines-for-africa/> [Accessed 5 Aug 2021].

Reidenberg, J. (2003) Privacy Wrongs in Search of Remedies [Online]. FLASH: The Fordham Law Archive of Scholarship and History. Available: https://ir.lawnet.fordham.edu/faculty_scholarship/36 [Accessed 7 May 2019].

Rubinstein, I. (2013) Big Data: The End of Privacy or a New Beginning? International Data Privacy Law. Vol.3 (2), pp.74-87.

Saunders, P., Lewis, D. and Thornhill, A. (2003) Research methods for business students. 3rd ed. London: Pearson Education.

- Sayre, S. (2006) Qualitative methods for marketplace research. Thousand Oaks, Calif: Sage.
- Schulze, H. (2018) GDPR compliance report [Online]. Crowd Research Partners. Available: <https://crowdresearchpartners.com/portfolio/gdpr-compliance-report> [Accessed 5 Apr 2020].
- Shim, S., Eastlick, M., Lotz, S. and Warrington, P. (2001) An online prepurchase intentions model. Journal of Retailing. Vol.77 (3), pp.397-416.
- Slyke, C., Shim, J., Johnson, R. and Jiang, J. (2006) Concern for Information Privacy and Online Consumer Purchasing. Journal of the Association for Information Systems. Vol.7 (6), pp.415-444.
- Soumelidou, A. and Tsohou, A. (2021) Towards the creation of a profile of the information privacy aware user through a systematic literature review of information privacy awareness. Telematics and Informatics. Vol.61, p.101592.
- Steinke, G. (2002) Data privacy approaches from US and EU perspectives. Telematics and Informatics. Vol.19 (2), pp.193-200.
- Stringfellow, A., Nie, W. and Bowen, D. (2004) CRM: Profiting from understanding customer needs. Business Horizons. Vol.47 (5), pp.45-52.
- Signup. (2021) [Online]. Instagram. Available: <https://www.instagram.com/> [Accessed 7 Oct 2020].
- Smartphone users in Nigeria 2014-2025 | Statista. (2021) [Online]. Statista. Available: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/467187/forecast-of-smartphone-users-in-nigeria/> [Accessed 7 Jan 2020].
- Special category data, Information Commissioner's Office. (2021) [Online]. Information Commissioner's Office. Available: <<https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/guide-to-data-protection/guide-to-the-general-data-protection-regulation-gdpr/lawful-basis-for-processing/special-category-data/#scd1>> [Accessed 6 Aug 2021].
- The four key attitudes to sharing data and how to engage with the different types. (2021) [Online]. Experian UK. Available: <https://www.experian.co.uk/blogs/latest-thinking/marketing/four-key-attitudes-sharing-data/> [Accessed 6 Aug 2021].

- Tankard, C. (2016) What the GDPR means for businesses. Network Security. Vol.2016 (6), pp.5-8.
- Tavani, H. and Moor, J. (2001) Privacy protection, control of information, and privacy-enhancing technologies. ACM SIGCAS Computers and Society. Vol.31 (1), pp.6-11.
- Tikkinen-Piri, C., Rohunen, A. and Markkula, J. (2018) EU General Data Protection Regulation: Changes and implications for personal data collecting companies. Computer Law & Security Review. Vol.34 (1), pp.134-153.
- Timothy, R. (2017) You can trust me: a multi-method analysis of the Nigerian email scam. Security. Vol.31 (3), pp.1-9.
- Trochim, W. and Donnelly, J. (2008) Research methods knowledge base. Mason, Ohio: Atomic Dog/Cengage Learning.
- UNdata | record view | Mobile-cellular telephone subscriptions per 100 inhabitants. (2020) [Online]. Data.un.org. Available: <https://data.un.org/Data.aspx?q=nigeria&d=ITU&f=ind1Code%3aI911%3bcountryCode%3aNGA#ITU> [Accessed 15 Mar 2020].
- Unsolicited messages: Appeal court awards damages against MTN. (2017) [Online]. Punchng.com. Available: <https://punchng.com/unsolicited-messages-acourt-awards-damages-against-mtn> [Accessed 20 Jun 2020].
- US names Nigerians in massive fraud investigation. (2021) [Online]. BBC News. Available: <https://www.bbc.co.uk/news/world-africa-49446845> [Accessed 5 Aug 2021].
- Venkatesh, A. (2021) A Conceptualization of the Household/Technology Interaction [Online]. Acrwebsite.org. Available: <https://www.acrwebsite.org/volumes/6382/volumes/v12/NA-12> [Accessed 7 Mar 2019].
- Verginadis, Y., Michalas, A., Gouvas, P., Schiefer, G., Hübsch, G. and Paraskakis, I. (2017) PaaSword: A Holistic Data Privacy and Security by Design Framework for Cloud Services. Journal of Grid Computing. Vol.15 (2), pp.219-234.
- Vollmer, N. (2021) Article 4 EU General Data Protection Regulation (EU-GDPR). Privacy/Privazy according to plan. [Online]. Privacy-regulation.eu. Available:

- <https://www.privacy-regulation.eu/en/article-4-definitions-GDPR.htm> [Accessed 7 Nov 2020].
- Wachter, S., Mittelstadt, B. and Floridi, L. (2017) Transparent, explainable, and accountable AI for robotics. Science Robotics. Vol.2 (6), p.eaan6080.
- Waldman, A. (2016) Privacy, Trust, and the Propensity to Disclose. SSRN Electronic Journal.
- Warren, S., Brandeis, L. and Childress, S. (n.d.) The right to privacy.
- Westin, A. (1968) Privacy And Freedom. Washington and Lee Law Review. [Online] Vol.25 (1), pp.101-106. Available:
<https://scholarlycommons.law.wlu.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=3659&context=wlulr> [Accessed 6 Mar 2019].
- Whitley, E. (2009) Informational privacy, consent and the “control” of personal data. Information Security Technical Report. Vol.14 (3), pp.154-159.
- Wirtz, J., Lwin, M. and Williams, J. (2007) Causes and consequences of consumer online privacy concern. International Journal of Service Industry Management. Vol.18 (4), pp.326-348.
- Who be Woodberry wey Dubai police arrest wit Hushpuppi - BBC News Pidgin. (2021) [Online]. BBC News Pidgin. Available: <https://www.bbc.com/pidgin/53272014> [Accessed 5 Aug 2021].
- Witness indicts EFCC, Magu in Abdulrasheed Maina’s trial. (2021) [Online]. Vanguardngr. Available: <https://www.vanguardngr.com/2021/03/witness-indicts-efcc-magu-in-abdulrasheed-mainas-trial/> [Accessed 11 Apr 2021].
- World Wide Web Consortium (W3C). (2021) [Online]. W3.org. Available:
<https://www.w3.org> [Accessed 7 Apr 2019].
- Xu, H., Dinev, T., Smith, J. and Hart, P. (2011) Information Privacy Concerns: Linking Individual Perceptions with Institutional Privacy Assurances. Journal of the Association for Information Systems. Vol.12 (12), pp.798-824.
- Yin, R. (1984) Applications of case study research. CA: SAGE Publications.

Yin, R. (2009) Case study research: design and methods. 5th ed. London: Sage Publication.

v. Appendices

a. Transcription of Interviews

Agency A: Education Student Recruitment

Interviewee Profile: Business Manager

A. General questions about travel agency business activities

1. What kind of services do you offer?

Response: We process admission and visa applications on behalf of international students to universities abroad. We also aid in ticketing, accommodation, and airport transfers.

2. Do you own a website and offer services online?

Response: Yes, we have a website.

3. How many customers, on average, do you provide your services to yearly?

Response: 170

4. What percentage of your customers patronize your online services?

Response: 100% of our customers patronize us online.

5. How many requests involving customers' data do you process daily?

Response: 40

6. What information do you request from your customers to make their travel arrangements?

Response: We ask for their passport information, phone number, and email address. Then we send them our biodata form and document checklist which they need to use in sending us required documents like academic certificates, transcripts, English proficiency results, and other relevant documents.

B. General discussion into awareness of Nigeria's Data Protection Regulation

7. Do you know what data protection is?

Response: Yes, I do.

8. If I was asked to identify you as a person, what information could best describe you?

Response: Date of birth, nationality, and name.

9. How would you feel if such data is made public?

Response: If my data is made public without my consent, I would feel horrible and uncomfortable.

Core discussion into awareness of Nigerian Data Protection Regulation

10. To the best of your knowledge, has the Nigerian government made any law in an attempt to secure the personal information of Nigerians?

Response: None that I am aware of.

11. Have you heard about the Nigerian Data Protection Regulation?

Response: No.

12. Do you know what is required of your agency by the Nigerian data protection regulatory authority regarding data protection?

Response: No.

13. What challenges have you had concerning the implementation of data protection within your agency?

Response: None

14. Do you have a data protection policy in place on your website?

Response: Yes, we do.

15. Would you say that the absence of such a policy is a delay in compliance?

Response: Not for us. But for other companies, without it, yes.

16. How are your clients informed about your current data protection policy?

Response: There is a data protection notice that pop-up on our website that every visitor, whether new or old, sees when they visit our website. We input our data policy on our biodata forms which we use to request information from our customers.

17. How does data protection awareness affect how you operate?

Response: We have become more careful about how we handle data. Now that we know what data protection is, we understand that the impact of a breach of data protection has a more negative effect on the customer than us as a company. This is because the customer can be exposed to the danger of being defrauded or even face hurt. So, we are now extremely careful. We also make our customers aware of data protection through the bio-data form we send to them to fill their application. Sometimes the universities we process requests for a GDPR form to be filled by the student.

18. What measures have you taken to ensure the security of your client's data?

Response: All our staff is trained to be data protection conscious, and a non-disclosure agreement that all staff must sign is also renewed at our data protection training every quarter. In addition, we use Google suite which has encryption software that can help to protect a customer's information. For instance, we can password emails that contain sensitive information and set it to expire within a period we choose, this way the receiver does not hold the information forever.

19. Who in your organization is responsible for handling data?

Response: All staff that collects data are responsible for securing it. However, our HR personnel ensures that all staff complies with the company's working policy regarding data protection.

20. Do you share your client's data with a third party?

Response: Yes, only with third-party organizations that are in the processing pipeline like the businesses we partner with that will enable our delivery services to our clients that cannot be directly provided by us. For example, airport pickup, accommodation services, and ticketing.

D. Core discussion on personal experiences of a data breach

21. In your agency, have there been any cases of a breach?

Response: No

22. Has any information held by you about any of your clients been lost?

Response: No

23. Are you aware of the penalty for breach of the data protection regulation?

Response: I know about GDPR, but I am not aware if Nigeria has any such penalties.

24. In what way do you feel the law can be improved?

Response: People need to be informed about it, especially those who process data. There are dangerous risks involved in data breaches. So, data protection is a necessity.

b. Transcription of Interviews

Agency B – Education: Student Recruitment

Interviewee Profile: CEO & Founder

A. General questions about travel agency business activities

1. What kind of services do you offer?

Response: Basically, we assist students who are willing to study abroad. We have several countries, UK, US, Canada, Australia, Ireland, several other European countries as well as some Asian countries to process the admissions, paperwork involved, entry requirements. We supply basic information that helps to get them the admission, and we help with the admission processing. We also assist them with visa counseling, required documentation, filling out the application form, and eventually getting their visa from the beginning to the end. Do you own a website and offer services online?

Response: Yes, we have a website and social accounts such as Instagram, Facebook, and Twitter. We offer our services to students online as well.

2. How many customers, on average, do you provide your services to yearly?

Response: 150 on average.

3. What percentage of your customers patronize your online services?

Response: 80% of our customers patronize us online.

4. How many requests involving customers' data do you process daily?

Response: 50

5. What information do you request from your customers to make their travel arrangements?

Response: We ask them about their academic backgrounds such as qualifications, and a class of degree. We also ask about their financial status to ascertain if they can afford the study plan, bank statements, passport information, family status, and other relevant data.

B. General discussion into awareness of Nigeria's Data Protection Regulation

7. Do you know what data protection is?

Response: Yes, I do.

8. If I was asked to identify you as a person, what information could best describe you?

Response: Yes, my data such as my name, date of birth, home address, office address, family information, and qualifications.

9. How would you feel if such data is made public?

Response: I would not like it, especially if it is done without my permission

Core discussion into awareness of Nigerian Data Protection Regulation

10. To the best of your knowledge, has the Nigerian government made any law in an attempt to secure the personal information of Nigerians?

Response: Well, the laws are there but I am not sure if they are being followed. They are not enough resources to ensure that these laws are followed.

11. Have you heard about the Nigerian Data Protection Regulation?

Response: No.

12. Do you know what is required of your agency by the Nigerian data protection regulatory authority regarding data protection?

Response: No. Yeah, well, we're supposed to keep students' information private. We're not supposed to disclose to third parties, the information given to us is supposed to be just for admission and we are not to use it for marketing or advertising

13. What challenges have you had concerning the implementation of data protection within your agency?

Response: None.

14. Do you have a data protection policy in place on your website?

Response: Well, we don't know. Not yet. We don't have an adequate policy on it.

15. Would you say that the absence of such a policy is a delay in compliance?

Response: Well, we don't have any such rules for now saying he has to be on the website. So, we're not sure whether we are breaking rules or not right, and I don't think there's any rule that says you need to have a warning saying anything about the data protection for now

16. How are your clients informed about your current data protection policy?

Response: Some of them ask us if their information is safe and we tell them yes.

17. Does data protection awareness affect how you operate?

Response: Yeah, because we have agreements or contracts with universities, in the UK, Canada, and all other countries. And we signed an agreement that mandates that there is data protection for the students coming to us. So, we know, we know that their information ought to be kept private. We do not know what laws are available in Nigeria, but we know data protection laws are available in advanced countries.

18. What measures have you taken to ensure the security of your clients' data?

Response: Well not straightforward. We just ensure that employees are aware that client's information must be protected. So, all counselors know, it's part of the training we give to them that this information must be kept safe. It is just for admission and therefore must not go beyond the office. It is part of their employment contract

19. Who in your organization is responsible for handling data?

Response: All counselors handle data because they all handle application processes

20. Do you share your client's data with a third party?

Response: If we need to do that, then the student will be aware. We will let them know that we want to share their information with a third party. If they give their consent, then we proceed.

Core discussion personal experiences of a data breach?

21. In your agency, has there been any case of a breach?

Response: No, but if there is, there is a senior supervisor who will investigate that.

22. Has any information held by you about any of your clients been lost?

Response: No, it hasn't happened before.

23. Are you aware of the penalty for a breach of the data protection regulation?

Response: No, I am not aware

24. In what way do you feel the law can be improved?

Response: I think people need to know. There is a lot of ignorance. Many people do not know if whether these laws exist. There should be aware. People should be made aware that these laws are there? If these laws are broken, what kind of punishment do they get? People need to know. I think it's basic ignorance, lack of information. That's the main thing.

C. Transcription of Interviews

Agency C – Travel and Leisure

Interviewee Profile: Operations Team Lead

A. General questions about travel agency business activities

1. What kind of services do you offer?

Response: We offer ticketing for flights, hotel bookings, insurance, visa assistance, and protocols.

2. Do you own a website and offer services online?

Response: Yes, we have a website.

3. How many customers, on average, do you provide your services to yearly?

Response: 12,000 per branch on average.

4. What percentage of your customers patronize your online services?

Response: 80% of our customers patronize us online.

5. How many requests involving customers' data do you process daily?

Response: 50 - 75

6. What information do you request from your customers to make their travel arrangements?

Response: We ask for their name as it appears on their passport data page, phone number, and email address. These are the basic information we need for a reservation.

B. General discussion into awareness of Nigeria's Data Protection Regulation

7. Do you know what data protection is?

Response: Yes, I do. I feel data protection is just a way of protecting people's data.

8. If I was asked to identify you as a person, what information could best describe you?

Response: My name of course.

9. How would you feel if such data is made public?

Response: I might be offended if it is done without my permission. But if I give permission then it's fine.

Core discussion into awareness of Nigerian Data Protection Regulation

10. To the best of your knowledge, has the Nigerian government made any law in an attempt to secure the personal information of Nigerians?

Response: I don't know so much about that, but I know most Nigerians are not comfortable with disclosing their personal information probably for security reasons.

11. Have you heard about the Nigerian Data Protection Regulation?

Response: No, I don't

12. Do you know what is required of your agency by the Nigerian data protection regulatory authority regarding data protection?

Response: No, I don't know.

13. What challenges have you had concerning the implementation of data protection within your agency?

Response: None.

14. Do you have a data protection policy in place on your website?

Response: No, I do not know.

15. Would you say that the absence of such a policy is a delay in compliance?

Response: Yes, it is.

16. How are your clients informed about your current data protection policy?

Response: No information is given to clients. Business is done based on trust.

17. Does data protection awareness affect how you operate?

Response: Yes

18. What measures have you taken to ensure the security of your client's data?

Response: So, we have a corporate communications unit. The department collates all the data we have gotten from people who have visited our website at some point. We have those details with us, and we do not share them with any third party.

19. Who in your organization is responsible for handling data?

Response: Yes, we have a corporate communications unit that oversees that.

20. Do you share your client's data with a third party?

Response: No, we don't

D. Core discussion personal experiences of a data breach?

21. In your agency, has there been any case of a breach?

Response: Not at all, because of the nature of what we do and the kind of data that we have, once a reservation is made, we send it directly to the person that requested that reservation, and that it is. Once the person has used the itinerary, that it is.

22. Has any information held by you about any of your clients been lost?

Response: Not at all. Like I said the kind of data we have are data that people willingly give us either through making inquiries or visiting our website to make a reservation on the platform.

23. Are you aware of the penalty for breach of the data protection regulation?

Response: No, I am not aware.

24. In what way do you feel the law can be improved?

Response: The government can work with the telecommunications companies to ensure they do not sell people's information because there are many cases of people receiving unsolicited messages.

d. Transcription of Interviews

Agency D – Travel and Leisure

Interviewee Profile: Sales Officer

A. General questions about travel agency business activities

1. What kind of services do you offer?

Response: We offer ticketing for flights, hotel bookings, tours, vacation packages, and visa assistance.

2. Do you own a website and offer services online?

Response: Yes, we have a website

3. How many customers, on average, do you provide your services to yearly?

Response: 2000 per branch on average

4. What percentage of your customers patronize your online services?

Response: 70% of our customers patronize us online.

5. How many requests involving customers data do you process daily?

Response: 200 - 300

6. What information do you request from your customers to make their travel arrangements?

Response: We request for their passport data page, we ask if they have a valid visa, and we ask for some travel documents that will be requested by the airline.

B. General discussion into awareness of Nigeria's Data Protection Regulation

7. Do you know what data protection is?

Response: Yes, I do. I know it is for safeguarding important information from corrupt files and compromise.

8. If I was asked to identify you as a person, what information could best describe you?

Response: Name, sexuality, status, and nationality.

9. How would you feel if such data is made public?

Response: Such details would be against my consent.

Core discussion into awareness of Nigerian Data Protection Regulation

10. To the best of your knowledge, has the Nigerian government made any law in an attempt to secure the personal information of Nigerians?

Response: I have heard of data protection law for safeguarding people's information. I stumbled upon some law some time ago.

11. Have you heard about the Nigerian Data Protection Regulation?

Response: No.

12. Do you know what is required of your agency by the Nigerian data protection regulatory authority regarding data protection?

Response: No, I don't know

13. What challenges have you had concerning the implementation of data protection within your agency?

Response: No, I can't say.

14. Do you have a data protection policy in place on your website?

Response: No, I do not know.

15. Would you say that the absence of such a policy is a delay in compliance?

Response: Yes, it is.

16. How are your clients informed about your current data protection policy?

Response: Not aware

17. Does data protection awareness affect how you operate?

Response: Not aware

18. What measures have you taken to ensure the security of your client's data?

Response: Well, we are always careful. Our IT has software that we use. We ensure we don't share any information outside. with customers' data.

19. Who in your organization is responsible for handling data?

Response: Anyone handling data

20. Do you share your client's data with a third party?

Response: If we are transferring to a third party it should be amongst us, the customer, and the airline, that is as far as it can go.

D. Core discussion personal experiences of a data breach?

21. In your agency, has there been any case of a breach?

Response: Not that I am aware of

22. Has any information held by you about any of your clients been lost?

Response: Not that I have heard of.

23. Are you aware of the penalty for breach of the data protection regulation?

Response: No, I am not aware

24. In what way do you feel the law can be improved?

Response: The government should provide security software to prevent breaches.

a. NVivo Word Cloud

